

The Other as Part of Us

Pope Francis hugging the man with neurofibromatosis (2013)
St Francis kissing the leper (1205/6)

THE CONSTITUTIVE OTHER
The Other as Part of Us

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Editorial - The Constitutive Other: The Other as Part of Us

We tend to see the other as opposed to ourselves or as rivals. Sometimes we even treat them as our enemies. At the same time, the challenge we face in our pluralistic and diverse world is to befriend the other, recognise the otherness in the other with respect and compassion.

In phenomenology, the terms the Other and the Constitutive Other identify the other human being, in their differences from the Self, as being a cumulative, constituting factor in the self-image of a person; as acknowledgement of being real; hence, the Other is dissimilar to and the opposite of the Self, of Us, and of the Same. The Constitutive Other is the relation between the personality (essential nature) and the person (body) of a human being; the relation of essential and superficial characteristics of personal identity that corresponds to the relationship between opposite, but correlative, characteristics of the Self, because the difference is inner-difference, within the Self (Wikipedia contributors, 2021).

The condition and quality of Otherness (the characteristics of the Other) is the state of being different from and alien to the social identity of a person and to the identity of the Self. In the discourse of philosophy, the term Otherness identifies and refers to the characteristics of Who? and What? of the Other, which are distinct and separate from the Symbolic order of things; from the Real (the authentic and unchangeable); from the aesthetic (art, beauty, taste); from political philosophy; from social norms and social identity; and from the Self. Therefore, the condition of Otherness is a person's non-conformity to and with the social norms of society; and Otherness is the condition

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of disenfranchisement (political exclusion), effected either by the State or by the social institutions invested with the corresponding socio-political power. Therefore, the imposition of Otherness alienates the person labelled as “the Other” from the centre of society, and places him or her at the margins of society, for being the Other.

The term Othering describes the reductive action of labelling and defining a person as a subaltern native, as someone who belongs to the socially subordinate category of the Other. The practice of Othering excludes persons who do not fit the norm of the social group, which is a version of the Self; likewise, in human geography, the practice of othering persons means to exclude and displace them from the social group to the margins of society, where mainstream social norms do not apply to them, for being the Other.

In the very provocative book, *Oneself as Another* (Ricoeur, 2008), the French existentialist Paul Ricoeur provides a stimulating examination of the role of personal identity and presents a brilliant insight into Ricoeur’s own views on subjectivity and the hermeneutics of the self.

According to Ricoeur, selfhood, far from referring to something concrete, discrete and fully understood, implies otherness to an unacknowledged degree. To speak of “the self” implies a relationship between the same and the other which the Cartesian cogito (“I think, therefore I am”) does not include. Unlike the cogito, which functions as a statement of knowledge, the hermeneutics of the self can only lead to an attestation of truth. However, Paul Ricoeur claims that such an attestation of belief is not inferior to knowledge, but merely expresses a different type of certainty (Greenaway, 1986).

The attesting of belief is a form of testimony, whereby the individual self, a verbal sign and assurance that the self believes in the truth of what it claims. From this defense of attestation Ricoeur moves on to discuss the dialectic relationship between selfhood and sameness. Sameness denotes a numerical identity, a qualitative identity or it may also denote an uninterrupted continuity. Selfhood, on the other hand, refers to the identity which belongs to one self and not another, or, more interestingly, one self as another.

According to Ricoeur our narrative identity is defined by the complex interplay between sameness and selfhood. The identity of an individual within a narrative is their narrative identity and to be in

possession of such an identity implies a capacity for action. Furthermore, a character in a narrative is an individual who may be re-identified as being the same. This becomes more complex as Ricoeur moves on to his discussion of responsibility. For a self to be responsible, it must be the same self which is believed to be the acting agent in any given situation, but still capable of change. Ricoeur singularly manages to turn the self into the self as other with the deliberate aim of provoking a new ethical awareness. Personal identity is inseparable from ethics (the aims of our personal behaviour) and morals (how this behaviour is carried out in the social realm.)

Ricoeur's careful untangling of the self allows the reader to see how conception of selfhood materially impact how we treat others (Greenaway, n.d.). Understanding oneself as another involves treating the Other when encountered in the world with empathy and respect – a new “solicitude” rather than any kind of moral solipsism whereby not only can we see ourselves as another, but we can also see the other as ourselves.

In this sense, we do have a collective responsibility for the other. To protect and promote the others (in their otherness) is our sacred responsibility. In view of these developments Jnana Deepa, Institute of Philosophy and Theology, Pune, organised an international Conference on Befriending the Other on November 24-28, 2015. Some of the papers were published in 2016 issue of *Jnanadeepa* (Vol 20/1-2) The papers in this volume are revised presentations of that Conference, which attempts to acknowledge, respect and befriend the other.

The Editor

Referenece

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The Otherness in the Other

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Abstract: The hierarchy and structuring of India maybe viewed in logocentric linear manner. Such a view often legitimizes reigning hierarchies and regimes of oppressions. It imposes a static lens of sameness on the entire process of that formed and is forming our society. In contrast to this view, we take up a non-linear, non-hierarchical, horizontal and immanent view in this study by critically scrutinizing otherness. To enter this dynamic terrain, we take a walk into the ecology of thought of Gilles Deleuze and Pierre-Félix Guattari. We shall first study the material processes and discern the relation between repetitions, resemblance and equivalence. Then we deepen our study through a scrutiny of Immanence. Next we deal with three ecological registers: the environment, society and subjectivity. Finally we discuss the dynamic flows of our Indian society in a rhizomatic way.

Keywords: Other, Otherness, Repetition, Resemblance, Plane of immanence, Territorialisation and Deterritorialization, Desiring Machines, Body-without-organs, Rhizome

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The structural and cultural complexities of India maybe viewed in logocentric linear manner. Such a view often legitimizes reigning hierarchies and regimes of oppressions. It imposes a static lens of sameness on the entire process of that formed and is forming our society. In contrast to this view, we take up a non-linear, non-hierarchical, horizontal and immanent view in this study by critically scrutinizing otherness. Otherness is not static. It is important to understand how the other emerges from as dynamic and multiple flows of otherness. The other is an emergent property of the unstable otherness. This unstable otherness reaches some level of unstable stability in the shape of being other. The ontic other that we experience irrupts from an ontological dynamic volcano. It is from the depth of otherness that its other emerges which then in relations to its dynamic 'out bursting' otherness leads to a new level wherein another other bursts on the scene and the process marches on as the multiple possibilities open the dynamic otherness that reaches a kind of unstable closure. The logocentric underpinnings of our thought comfortably essentialize sameness and privilege it against difference. Unfortunately, this difference is constructed in the horizon of sameness. Hence, in this context I find that Deleuzian rendering of sameness and difference in a dynamic mould of repetition can untie these knots and allows the dynamics of sameness and otherness shine to its full potential. Hence, it is important to understand how both difference and repetition rises from a dynamic interiority which operates only in the multiple and determines multiplicities. Hence, the other of otherness is an effect or a product of mobile relations.

We cannot black box sameness and difference in a static mould and then relate them mathematically so to say. There is no stable sameness or difference. There is only a dynamic repetition and differentiating difference. Sameness is not a subtraction of otherness. We need to step into the dynamic dance of intensive flows and multiple energies that allow repetition and difference to burst on the scene. It is in this dance that always spreads from a decentred centre and displaced periphery that we can trace the

zone of the other in the otherness. To enter this dynamic terrain, we take a walk into the ecology of thought of Deleuze and Guattari. They offer a new thought that strives to bring a new materialism that does not begin from an imposition of human values, meaning and culture upon material processes. They explore the role of material processes in the emergence of three ecologies: the environment, society and subjectivity.

We shall first study the material processes and discern the relation between repetitions, resemblance and equivalence. Then we deepen our study through a scrutiny of Immanence. Next we strive to deal with three ecological registers: the environment, society and subjectivity. Finally we shall try to discuss the dynamic flows of our Indian society in a rhizomatic way.

Repetition, Resemblance and Equivalence

There is irreducibility in repetitions. Repetitions are not resemblances. There is a radical difference between the two. The equation of repetitions to resemblance is a subtraction of difference. It is based on the calculus of exchange or substitution. This apparent exchange or substitution is possible only if one views repetition through a static and generic terms. Often resemblance and difference is thought in a cyclic mode of thought. Although, it brings dynamism to resemblance but it exterminate difference, it's other. Hence, the logocentric thinking of identities and their relations to alterities has to be deconstructed.

Repeating the Unrepeatable

Repetitions are concerned with relations that are non-exchangeables or non-substitutable. There is a paradox in repetition in as much as it seeks to repeat the unrepeatable. This is why repetitions are non mathematical, economy of exchange. Repetitions are different in kind. Psychoanalytically repetition is born out of insatiability and a sense of incompleteness. Even a simple human act cannot fully reduplicate itself. That is, there is somehow a counterfeit dimension in all repetitions. In other

words repetition is repeating the unrepeatable. That is why resemblance does not belong to nature but is a second nature. It is a habit of our thinking and speaking and hence acquired at the cost of the murder of dynamism of being. Therefore, we need to put metaphysic in motion. Movement is repetition. Repetition cannot be represented. In repetition, we experience pure forces, dynamic lines in space act in a manner we cannot really describe. It acts without intermediary. It is like language which speaks before words or gestures which develop before organized bodies, or masks before faces, sceptres and phantoms before characters. Repetitions produce movements or leaps. This means it escapes fixation. David Hume had already shown that repeated series such as AB, AB, AB....themselves produce something new, namely a habit and expectation. Hence he says when A appears we habitually expect B (Smith 2013).

Repetition as Singular

Repetition cannot be replaced. It is singular. Deleuze uses the metaphor of a gift or theft to draw the singularity of the repetition. Repetition is about unexchangeable and unsubstitutable singularities. For instance, one cannot exchange one's soul. Exchange is the criterion of resemblance and equivalence. Hence, there is economic difference between repetition and resemblance and singular (Deleuze, 1994: 1). Deleuze states that to repeat is to behave in a certain manner but in relation to something unique and singular which has no equal nor equivalent (Deleuze, 1994: 1). Thus, festivals do not add the first time to the second time to the first but carry the first time to the nth power. Therefore it is on 15th August that commemorates the Independence of our country. But it is the independence that repeats and celebrates on every 15th August. There are two types of languages. The language of science is dominated by the symbol of equality and hence each term may be exchanged by another while in a lyrical language every term is irreplaceable and can only be repeated (Deleuze, 1994: 2). The law belongs to the order of resemblance while transgression of the law belongs to the order of repetition. It puts

all law, including the law of nature into question. It denounces its nominal and general character in favour of more profound and more artistic reality (Deleuze, 1994: 3). Deleuze succinctly teaches this when he says, 'expecting repetition from the law of nature is the 'Stoic' error.'

Differential Fields the Ground of Repetition

Differential fields are structures that are conditions of genesis of creative transformation of things. The differential fields are inhabited by multiple flows and intensities that produce mutual re/de territorialisation. The differential fields are constituted of multiplicities. Multiplicities give rise to thresholds that lead to the emergence of singularities. Thus, for instance, in a game of football it is differential relations of the ground, sphere, players and rules that enables the sphere to emerge as a football or the players as footballers and field of play as a football ground. It is the differential relations and intensities that open the virtual (possible) to become actual as the players move, advance and retreat in the course of the game. These relations can be seen as strewn singularities that led the ball move from players to players across the football field. But football is just one actualization of the differential relations. Change the rules slightly and you have hand ball or rugby etc. Thus, it is the distribution of the flows and intensities in the differential fields that becomes the ground of difference as well as unrepeatable repetitions. The unrepeatable difference is (un)substitutable. Thus, my reflection in the mirror is a repetition of me but cannot substitute me. My friends will not relate to my reflection but would need me. Repetitions express persistence of difference that can be viewed as immanent variability or cadence. The harmonious musical composition (cadence) is a result of differential fields of intensities of the dance of notes that makes it possible.

Thinking Immanence

Deleuze reads philosophers like Spinoza and Bergerson through the lens of immanence. Immanence is a complex notion

and is at play at several levels in Deluzian thought. It is an ontological notion that forms the basis of Deluezian thought. It becomes the horizon from where thinking takes place. It constitutes the internal condition of thinking. Thinking produces concepts which Deleuze calls intensive events where thought crystallizes into a specific formulation responding to specific problem at stake for a thinker . All thinking emerges from what he calls the plane of immanence.

Plane of Immanence and Thinking

Deleuze teaches that the main task of the philosophers is the generation of concepts. He notes that concepts are always composite and multiple. Thus, for instance Cogito is composed of a certain idea of thinking, being and the self. Concepts not only attempt to provide us solutions to specific problems, they become tools rendering possible the elaboration of the problem in question. Precisely because they have to be created and are not found, they require a milieu out of which they can be created. Deleuze calls it the plane of immanence. The relation between the concept and the plane of immanence is one of mutuality. No concept can be generated without the plane of immanence which grounds them, yet, the plane of immanence cannot be thought without the concept that inhabits it. That is why the plane of immanence is often thought as pre-philosophical, not in terms of something pre-existing philosophy but as that which constitutes the unspoken, the unthought internal conditions of thinking itself. Each plane of immanence is outlined in such and such a way depending on the nature of question. Being pre-philosophical, it cannot be thought as such yet it constitutes thought. Deleuze terms it as an image of thought

The Plane of Immanence, Thought and Chaos

Energies within the plane of immanence that provides consistency to it. The counterpoint of the plane of immanence is not transcendence but chaos. The plane of immanence makes consistency possible while chaos is that which has no

consistency and is that which constitutes a continuous dissolution of consistency. Chaos is perpetually chaotizing where nothing has yet taken form neither as thought or nature and in the same way threatens to dissolve all that is formulated and wrought into form. Thus, chaos is not static, inert or in stationary state. It is in a constant mode of chaotizing. While still being immersed into the chaos that thought begins by precisely instituting the plane of immanence which is nothing but a section of chaos. This means what we call thinking occurs as tensive relation between chaos and immanence where chaos ungrounds thought and immanence makes it possible to ground it and yet maintains chaotic speed. By letting thought be formulated as a continuous tension relation to chaos, we have an essential groundlessness of the thought or philosophy itself. This means there are no fixed points and no given questions, concepts or problems for thought. The very absence of givenness, of world, subject, consciousness or God constitutes the horizon of thought. The plane of immanence enables the creation of meaning against the background of chaotic non-meaning that underlines all life.

Plane of Immanence, Territorialisation and Deterritorialization

Territory in an ethological sense is viewed as an environment of the group that cannot be objectively located but is constituted by the patterns of interaction which enables the group to acquire a certain stability and location. Hence, a territorial process is continuously going on everywhere. The Plane of immanence continuously becomes the earth or deterritorialization on which it creates its concepts. The plane of immanence provides us two sides: extension and thought. It means it provides us the power of being and powers of thinking. Hence, the plane of immanence is in a continuous process of deterritorialization. It is phase space of a system. The plane of immanence has multiple layers that sometimes knit together and sometimes separate. The plane is never given as such but it is given only in through what it gives. This means it can only be inferred in what it gives. What it gives

is differential actualizations that come from the world of virtual tendencies (phase space). The virtual constitutes a domain that is much larger and is teeming with potentials. This means that plane of immanence is never given and is never present. The differential calculus formalizes the virtual into the actual. That is, the plane of immanence is a ground of morphogenesis. It is on the plane of immanence under which intensities that tend to cancel each other are brought into actuality. It has the power to organize infinitely. This infinitely complex process brings the locking of intensities (intensities may be viewed as points of attractors, bifurcators, zone of sensitivity that based the theory of self-organizability) into system of resonance and redundancy. Always there is a loss of something in the process of actualization (deterritorializations).

The Ecology of the Environment

Matter and form do not exist in isolation but are intimately intertwined. They express themselves by stratifying themselves. Every strata expresses without signifying anything because it is based in to the power to organize infinitely. We attempt to primarily listen to the dance of Differentiation. (differentiation in the Heideggerian sense)

Differentiation and Differentiation

In *Difference and Repetition* and the *Logic of Sense*, Deleuze argued that the virtual is self-differentiating or difference in itself. The virtual realm is not undifferentiated chaos but is a realm of regional ontologies laying out the multiple possibilities for 'a' society, 'a' language and 'an' animal, and so forth can exist. Deleuze calls triggering of a bifurcator as an Event that unleashes an 'emission of Singularities' (Protevi, 2001). It means a bifurcator provides for the new set of attractors or patterns of behaviour. This process is named as differentiation by Deleuze in contrast to differentiation which names the process of actualization (Protevi, 2001). Actualization is a process of becoming of exclusive disjunctions which involves the selection

of a series of singularities whose actualization precludes (prevent from happening) the simultaneous actualization of others. These would then have the status of ‘road not taken’ (Protevi, 2001). Within this train of thought, we are challenged to view phase space as dynamic and virtual as creative or productive. Scholars like Stuart Kaufmann of Santa Fe Institute positions a ‘mutual bootstrap’ effect between the ‘landscape’ of a particular phase space and specific trajectories inhabiting it (Protevi, 2001). In this way the actual agents serve to transform the virtual field creating new singularities , ‘fitness peaks’ or attractors that will let differentiation reach a new level of emergence (Protevi, 2001). Hence, the virtual is not static but a differentiating chaoticizing .

Selective Accumulation

The intensive flows at the level differentiation are permeated with unstable, unformed, open and nomadic singularities. Thus, for instance at the scale of geological stratification, it consists of process that inhabits territorialisation, sedimentation and fixation of intensities and singularities- through which structures (or stable forms) emerge and molar assemblages (Substances) take place. At the level of sedimentation, cyclical sediments are laid whose homogeneity is a result of ‘sorting out mechanism’ through which a highly improbable distribution is achieved. Within this complex mechanism of sedimentation, we can understand the role of rivers , which bring rocky materials from the mountains to the ocean. During this process of transit, pebbles of different weight, size and shape are variously affected by water that transports them. It is these effects in the context of moving water that sorts them out with the smaller pebbles reaching the ocean faster than the larger ones. Once this laying out of the pebbles takes place, a second process sets in and transforms the loose pebbles into sedimentary rocks. This process is carried out by soluble substances like silica that penetrate the sediments through the pores in the pebbles. This process steadily lets the pebbles emerge as more or less permanent architectonic structure

that evolves into a new entity, the sedimentary rocks (Beistegui, 2010: 55-57).

Isolative Consolidation

Besides the phenomenon of accumulation, coagulation and sedimentation, we have to draw our attention to a process of isolative consolidation. To understand this important process, let us take the example of morphogenesis of genes. Neo-Darwinists teach that a species is formed by gradual accumulation and selection of genes. Genes are not distributed or deposited at random but are sorted out by variety of selection pressures like climate change, the action of predators, parasites and effects of male and female mating choices. Thus like the geological stratification the genetic accumulation also goes through the process of consolidation. The genetic consolidation occurs as a result of reproductive isolation. Reproductive isolation is a process that leads to the closure of a gene pool, when a given subset of population becomes incapable of mating and reproducing along with the rest. It is through the dual process of selective accumulation and isolative consolidation, a population of an individual organism emerges as a species. It is within what we have called the plane of immanence that where alluvions, sedimentations, coagulations, foldings and recoilings that lead to the emergence of an organism (Beistegui, 2010: 58-59).

Ecology of Society

From the Freudian point of view society, desire and sexuality revolve around the oedipal event. This Freudian oedipal triangle is questioned by many thinkers today. The social codes come along with its base desire in what is prohibited or something that is lacking. For the boy it is the mother that is prohibited so he would seek substitutes for her and for the girl what is lacking is the Phallus and she would seek those who may give her one. Desire here is a desire for the forbidden fruit. Deleuze and Guattari turn desire on its head. They develop the notion of desire that does not feed from its representation in terms of an object that we want

or something the subject lacks. Deleuze teaches that one never simply desire a person or an object. What one desires is an entire scenario, landscape, mode of existence or episode expressed in the person or the object. Desire is productive and has connective abilities.

Unconscious as a Site of Production of Desire

Deleuze and Guattari abandon the Freudian notion of unconscious as a site of repression of oedipal desires. They present the unconscious as rhizomatic rather than arborescent. It operates as networks or fields of operation rather than as a site that is steeped in repressed desires that are created after the resolution of the Oedipus Complex. The new notion of unconscious allows us to open the possibilities for a multiplicity of desires that may be oedipal, non-oedipal and beyond oedipal. This brings us to the possibility of living beyond the law of the father. Beyond the oedipal and oedipalized territories (Family, Church, School, Nation, Party), particularly the territoriality of individual, and the new notion of unconscious evoke deterritorialized flows of desire, the flows that have not been reduced to the oedipal codes and the neuroticized territorialities and as such can escape these codes through lines of escape that lead elsewhere. Desire as productive connects desire (desiring machine) an object to some other object giving us the possibility to discern desire in everything and everywhere.

The Desiring Machine

Deleuze and Guattari use the term desiring machines not in its literal sense but in a metaphorical sense. They are not discussing machine as configuration of pre-existing parts nor do they think of them in a mechanistic sense. Machines to them are some things that connect that do not necessarily belong together, things that were not necessarily designed for each other. Thus, for instance, the pianist uses his hands to connect the keys of the piano and uses his feet on the pedals to produce music. The flow of music is produced by a music machine that consists of hands,

feet, pedals, and the sheet of music that is being read. The desiring machine does not operate linearly and does not have specific task or time line. Desire connects objects to other objects (the pianists to piano, writer to books and paper, and writing tools) and is not limited to Oedipus complex and can break away from the oedipal triangle. Desire leads us to become body without organs by shunning away the organized, hierarchized and pre-given pre-existing body. Desire rides an attempt to become-molecular (not molar which presupposes a pre-given identity). Becoming molecular is not unified and cannot be identified because it has no identity and is rhizomatic .

Desire and Schizophrenic

Deleuze and Guattari teach that schizophrenia reveals the profound nature of desire. While developing a positive and immanent of desire, they found a blueprint in Spinoza and were compelled to engage with the dominant discourse on desire. In their work, *Anti-Oedipus*, they attempt to render, desire or unconscious immanent. They suggest that unconscious is the faculty of desire and venture into an immanent critique of its powers and uses and establish philosophy as Schizoanalysis. They teach that the faculty of desire does not relate to its own object through correspondence, conformity or what phenomenology calls intentionality but through a relation of causality. This means they hold that the representation of the object is the cause of that object. Therefore, they argue that desire cannot be said to be missing anything or lacking in anyway. Besides, they do not link desire with pleasure or satisfaction. They view desire as productive, what we can do and the extent to which we can express through action, thought and creation. It is the infinite power of substance in Spinozian sense. Hence, unconscious becomes a site of production and not representation. Desire does not express anything in linguistic-semantic sense (it is not a signifier). It does not express in myths, tragedies and dreams which has to be carved out through interpretation. Desire is an engine that drives history. It is not wrapped and hidden in the

Interest of class. It is not limited to oedipal triangle but is social and even cosmic. Desire is schizophrenic. It moves to become body without organs. Body without organs is the site that records the production of desire. It is on the body without organs that everything glides where connective and disjunctive energies collide resulting into a production or emergence of higher intensities and singularities.

The Body Without Organs and Indian Society

The body without organs is a field of immanence of desire. It is the plane where differentiation sets in the process of dynamic actualization the social sphere of our country. This brings us to the dynamism and fluidity of morphogenesis of everything that makes India. The India that we are living in is in the making. This process of actualization has not and will not follow a readymade path but is a product of spontaneous organization of several contingent factors that led the process of territorialisation, de-territorialisation and re-territorialisation.

The Rhizomatic Flow of Indian Civilization

The evolution and development of Indian civilization can be viewed as rizomatic flow. Our civilization did not develop merely in a linear hierarchical fashion as some ultra-nationalists think. India has emerged on a rhizomatic lines of flights. There is no point on a rhizome but only lines. Rhizome ceaselessly establishes connections between semiotic chains, organizations of power etc., which forms assemblages that form plateaus. Deleuze and Guattari call plateau any multiplicity connected to other multiplicities by superficial underground stems so as to form or extend a rhizome. The multiple points of intersections, overlaps, convergences, twistings and infinite folds have collectively produced our society. Hence, rhizomatic flows take us into horizontal overflows and not in a vertical hierarchical mode of social formation. The interweaving of our civilization has not occurred in isolation as the essentialist modes of thought makes us to believe but in a Rhizo-India way in connection

with its various flows both from within and from outside. The Rhizo-India mode, makes us to accept the geological flows, the formation of the Himalayas and the formation of Indian peninsula coupled with the human habitation resulting in the deforestation, the great Indus valley civilization, the migration of the Aryans and Vedic tradition, the rise of Sanghas leading to the birth of Magadha, the tribals and their cultures, the religious movements like Jainism, Buddhism in conflict with Brahminism, the invasion of Alexander, the great, the rise of the Mauryas, Asoka and the spread of Buddhism, the Gupta age, Harshavardhana, Rajputs and the Afghan-Turkish Sultans, Mughals, Marathas and the kingdoms of the south like the Pandyas, the Vktakas, Ikshvakus, the Kadambas, Chalukyas, Rashtrakutas, the Pallavas, the Bhamani Kingdom and the Vijaynagara have their share in the making of our country. Besides, the colonizers from the West: the Portuguese, the British and the French, the freedom movement, the cultural churning of RSS, and reformers of Hinduism, the two nation theory and the Hindu-Muslim conflict, the partition of Indian, the democratic rule, the birth of Bangladesh, along with the caste, religions, languages, sacred and secular literature and art forms, economic and political ideologies led to the formation of plural and vibrant India (Dalal, 2014). All this have to be seen in an emergent rizomatic way. Thus, for instance, if colonization was not to take place we out not have Hinduism or India of this shape.

The Death Drive and Indian Society

Body without organs has the death drive. It is a castrated body. Deleuze and Guattari teach that body without organs is synonymous with Freud's death instinct. Body without organs is what desire desires not as an object but as a state of being. It is the direction and the way in which desire moves. Indeed, the body without organs come into being as an effect of desiring. Hence, it does not pre-exists desire. It is a desire to be in a state of organless body. The desire is governed by the unconscious and hence the body without organs is also a product of the unconscious. It can

be best thought of as Being Degree Zero: that which stubbornly remains resisting all negation even when positive quality has taken way. It is neither an integral whole nor emptiness but rather remains an undifferentiated fluidity. It produces nothing but has to be reinserted in the production. Within this scheme of things, we can understand the logic of body without organs at play in the making and unmaking of Indian society. It becomes the 'socius', the full body of social production. In our country the 'socius' is the plural ethos that sustains the life and breath of our society. Upon this plural ethos that plurality and multiplicity in our country evolves and produces our social life. But there is the reverse movement that occludes the vibrant plural ethos of our country which homogenizes, essentializes part of it and leads us into the illusion of being nationalistic and more Indian than others. Thus, body without organs becomes a surface on which both the forces and agents of plural affirmation as well as negation are at play. The forces of negation of the plural ethos of our country become a clear expression of the death drive that can eventually destroy the vibrant plural ethos of our country. Thus, the champions of Hindutva and Hindu Rashatra become the visible portrayal of desire that is attempting to convert India into a body without organs. But there are secular forces that constantly de-territorialize and check the death drive injected by the Hindutva forces.

The Schizophrenic Desire and Indian Society

Deleuze and Guattari place desire in the social formation of production and production in the unconscious psychological realm of desire. This form of desire has no subject that causes production but it is production that causes further production. Such production results in the production of collective subjectivity of us Indians. Indian subject is an enduring self but is constantly changing and forming connections with the collective subjectivity. This means self of Indians are psychically and socially continuously de-territorialised. Thus, in several ways, we are 'schizophrenics'. Some of us are Christians ,

Goans, and Indians all at the same time. This is the case of every Indian. Schizophrenia is seen as a line of escape completely free from constraints of social representation and based entirely on experience. We can see how some cultural police are trying to impose what they selectively deem as Indian culture and position it as noble and national. These powers are erecting the law of the father to all of us. Those who do not accept their version of culture and nationalism are orphaned and denationalized. But a schizo has the strength to disown all of it. He is an anti-Oedipus and refuses to be disowned by the several laws of fathers erected in our society. In fact an Indian is challenged to disown the 'father' and continuously invent his /her Self. This means we Indians are challenged to become anti-Oedipus and save the plural ethos of our country. We have to resist the voices and forces that force us to oedipalize. This is the way the minorities in particular can liquidate and de-territorialize the powers that attempt to orphanize and de-nationalize them.

Conclusion

The dynamic metaphysic of difference of Deleuze and Guattari leads us away from linear, vertical and hierarchical understanding and leads us to a non-logocentric, horizontal and rhizomatic way. We are enabled to view an Rhizo-India that can liberate us from intolerance, hate and violence. This can enable us to understand the otherness of the other, which necessarily constitutes the 'non-other' self of the subject.

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Otherring Myself: Multiply Cultured, Differently Abled and Spiritually Hybrid

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Abstract: The author is convinced that other begins with one's own self. We are in fact not one monolithic self, but a multiplicity of even contradictory and ambiguous selves. At the postcolonial level, we can speak of the multiple discourses (conflicting and entangled narratives) governing us and so the othering of the other starts with the othering of my own self. For this we take two authors, Arundhati Roy and David Malouf, who will show the complex and nuanced identities of oneself. After realising this complex identities, we can try to enter into dialogue with the other, who is equally complex. This will help us to befriend the other.

Keywords: Arundhati Roy, David Malouf, Multiple Citizenships, Remembering Babylon, Multiple Identities.

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Inspired by “*Intimate Enemy: Loss and Recovery of Self Under Colonialism*” (Nandy, 2015), I want to reflect on the fact that the other begins with my own self. We are in fact not one monolithic self, but a multiplicity of even contradictory and ambiguous selves. At the postcolonial level, we can speak of the multiple discourses (conflicting and entangled narratives) governing us and so the othering of the other starts with the othering of my own self. For this we take two authors, Arundhati Roy and David Malouf.

1. Multiple Citizenships and Commitments

Going beyond hybridity and identities, we study the committment to multiple citizenships drawing insights from Arundhati Roy and David Malouf. This section will enable us to appreciate the role played by the people who are marginalise and disprivileged in the post colonial discourses.

a. Arundhati Roy: Globalising Dissent

Arundhati Roy is one of the most familiar faces of India. Though her book *The God of Small Things* has made her famous, her later writings have made her controversial. “Contested and upheld, denounced and defended, global change wrought by the globalization of neoliberal economic doctrine has come to mean different things in different contexts—the promotion of world integration and opportunity for growth, as well as the reproduction of inequalities old and new” (Grewal, 2009: 143). The latter has provoked local–global activism from players with varying agendas, which in turn has enabled spirited debate in university classrooms and academic journals, international board rooms, and local communities, raising deep questions of human agency, social justice, and equity. We can situate Arundhati Roy’s work as part of the wider response of civil society, at local, state, and global levels, whose aim is to “mediate between government and the power of capital” in order to “claim and retain the rights and entitlements of state and global citizenship” (Grewal, 2009: 143).

Roy's is a voice from the global South purposefully undoing Sanctioned ignorances, crossing borders of gender, caste, and class, of the nation state, of the South/North divide. Breaking taboos against complicating the lives of the haves and the have-nots—breaking the decorum of the institutionalized academy—Roy's writing lays bare the workings of power without permission from “the experts.” A feminist, but no bourgeois one, she gives herself to the cause of the people while expressing her wariness of the “traditional, mainstream” and “strangely unbending” Left with its rigid ideology. No wonder Roy ruffles so many feathers and is often looked down by the bourgeoisie.

What makes Roy compelling in our context is that she stakes her claim in multiple citizenships and in the accountability or responsibility that attends them—Indian citizenship; global capitalist citizenship (or as a “subject of Empire”); and a democratic feminist-humanitarian people's citizenship of the world. Few have *publicly* claimed multiple citizenships so flamboyantly, claiming all of her citizens' “rights to express dissent” (Roy, 2001: 87). It is no surprise that she is the acclaimed writer of the growing global justice movement: she has staged herself as a global citizen voicing the discourse of human rights in a bold, lyrical, and impassioned way.

It is insightful to trace how the author of *The God of Small Things* (Roy, 1997) become the advocate of big things like democracy and justice? According to Gurleen Grewal, there is a continuity between these two aspects of Roy. In fact it is by continuing to do “in the public sphere what she had done with the private sphere of home and family in her novel,” (Cited in Grewal, 2009: 144) that Roy has given voice to the colonised. Uma Narayan's definition of the feminist daughter's political enterprise, to “retell the story of a mother-culture in feminist terms,” is highly appropriate for understanding Roy's work as a whole: “It is a political attempt to tell a counter-story that contests dominant narratives that would claim the entire edifice of ‘our Culture’ and ‘our Nation’ for themselves, converting them into a peculiar form of property, and excluding the voices, concerns,

and contributions of many who are members of the national and political community” (Grewal, 2009: 144).

It may be noted that Roy is the latest among an increasing number of global feminist voices that have interrogated the neoliberal policies of economic globalization. For Roy, the questions are basic and important: who benefits? Who pays the cost? “What is it [globalization] going to do to a country like India, in which social inequality has been institutionalized in the caste system for centuries? In which three hundred million people are illiterate” (Roy, 2001:13–4). Roy’s analysis of the predicament of the poor in India has been preceded by that of feminist scholars who have worked in the areas of development for over two decades: the work of Gita Sen, Peggy Antrobus, Rajni Kothari, Bina Agarwal, Vandana Shiva, and others (Grewal, 2009).

In the epigraph to *The God of Small Things*, Roy quotes John Berger: “Never again will a single story be told as though it is the only one.” In a sense, Roy’s novel is about the ecology of being, showing how everything and everyone is interconnected, and how each life is shaped by what happens to others. The novel is moving because it gives nearly all the characters, even the oppressive ones, a vulnerability and humanity: a character may be twisted, but not inherently evil.

The author of *The God of Small Things* has become a passionate critique and a powerful voice for the subaltern and for the marginalised in a post-colonial situation. This takes us to a more powerful story situated in Australia.

b. David Malouf: Remembering Babylon

Another unique approach to the use of cultural hybridity in a postcolonial text has been utilized by David Malouf, in his novel *Remembering Babylon* (Malouf 1993). Malouf writes of the formative years of an Australian settler colony, and he uses a very unique character, that of Gemmy, to illustrate the vast differences between the settlers and the aboriginals, and,

eventually, between the settlers themselves. Gemmy is a white man who has grown up amongst the aboriginals. He has been away from Western society for so long that he is unable to communicate competently, or effect legitimate social discourse with the other whites. He comes to live with a young settler colony, and Malouf uses him to illustrate differences between all members of this colony. As each member of the colony tries to analyze the differences between themselves and Gemmy, they come to realize fundamental differences amongst them all. As Mr. Frazer writes in his logbook, “We must rub our eyes and look again, clear our minds of what we are looking for to see what is there” (Malouf 130 and Hybridity 2010).

Surely, each member of a postcolonial society would love to encounter one specific voice which could articulate their particular suffering and oppression under the colonial institution-one voice which would articulate their own sense of national identity. But exploration of these societies, and the literature produced by postcolonial authors and poets illustrates that there is a veritable infinite number of differing circumstances inherent in each postcolonial society, and, consequently, in each piece of literature produced by postcolonial writers. If one is to read this literature in a way which will shed some light on the postcolonial condition, one must understand and adopt the theory that we are all walking amalgamations of our own unique cultures and traditions. We are all always struggling with our own identities, personal and national. We must understand that there is no “one true voice” representing an easily identifiable postcolonial condition, but, instead, each author is his or her own voice and must be read as such (Hybridity 2010).

The story takes place in the mid-19th century in a remote settlement of Queensland, Australia. One day as a group of children are playing at the edge of the village, a remarkable figure stumbles out of the bush. This dark, unkempt person (Gemmy) turns out to be a white man who fell from a ship 16 years earlier (when he was a 19-year-old sailor) and has lived with an aboriginal tribe ever since (Coulehan, 2012). He hardly

remembers English, and his culture and sensibility have become those of his adopted people.

At first Gemmy creates a sensation in the settlement and people want to help him, despite his obvious savage mentality (after all, he isn't even embarrassed by nakedness!). He goes to live with the McIvor family, whose daughter, Janet, and nephew, Lachlan Beattie, were among the children who found him. While Mrs. McIvor accepts Gemmy with Christian love, her husband Jock is sceptical (Coulehan, 2012).

In fact, it soon becomes clear that there are major tensions in the village regarding Gemmy. Has he really become "one of them" (a black)? Can he be trusted? He seems harmless enough--almost a pleasant imbecile--but perhaps it is all a subterfuge. Perhaps he is in contact with THEM (Coulehan, 2012).

Among the European settlers, there are two views of how to handle the blacks. One group believes they should simply be wiped out--every one of them killed--because they are savage, worthless, and couldn't possibly become (real) Christians. A second group has a more romantic view. They think the black people could be "tamed" and become their servants. They envision themselves as owners of large plantations (as in the southern United States) worked by multitudes of happy and harmless black servants (Coulehan, 2012).

Representatives of both groups try to win Gemmy's confidence and obtain information regarding the whereabouts and plans of the black tribes. He, however, remains silent about these matters, although pleasant and deferential toward everyone. An uneasy truce holds until one day two aboriginal people are observed visiting with Gemmy on McIvor's property. This creates an uproar, which eventually leads some of the God-fearing whites to commit acts of vandalism and to injure Gemmy (Coulehan, 2012).

To preserve the peace, the McIvors send Gemmy to live with Mrs. Hutchence, an eccentric woman who lives on the margin of

the settlement. However, he soon disappears into the wilderness, but not until he retrieves--and destroys--what he thinks are the seven pieces of paper on which Mr. Frazier, the minister, had written Gemmy's life story soon after he had emerged from the bush (Coulehan, 2012).

2. Reflections

This novel portrays a cultural chasm, rather than a cultural clash. Gemmy, imbued with the mysticism and earth-centeredness of the native Australians with whom he has spent 16 years, is (precisely as the settlers fear) no longer "white." Gemmy cannot identify with the European culture that was once his by heritage. No wonder he can hardly remember how to speak the English language (Coulehan, 2012).

The Europeans, secure in their conviction that the aboriginal people are sub-human savages, cannot even consider treating them as persons. Some of the settlers want to eliminate the blacks completely (genocide), while others would prefer simply to rule them. Gemmy slowly comes to the realization that to save himself he must return to his aboriginal "roots." Ironically, this escape doesn't work--an epilogue to the story implies that Gemmy comes to a bad end.

How much goodness is there in the human spirit? This novel primarily explores the casual, unthinking darkness that threatens to engulf us all. Yet, the story also reveals glimmers of light in many individual persons (Coulehan, 2012).

Remembering Babylon, as its title suggests, shares the earlier novel's preoccupation with language, and both explore what happens when a stranger, reared in totally other cultural circumstances, is introduced into a small, beleaguered community held together largely by a common fear of all that surrounds it (Taylor, 1993: 123-25).

Remembering Babylon's title remains an enigma until its final chapter. The bulk of the novel is set in a tiny settlement of

Scots immigrants in Queensland north of Bowen in the middle of last century (Taylor, 1993: 123-25). They are surrounded – and threatened – by rainforest inhabited by hostile Aboriginals. Everything about them is creepy, and at night they sleep as close to their guns as they do to their spouses.

And then, in a page of breathless, seemingly endless prose which it would be murder to condense, something balances on that crucial dividing fence at the edge of the rainforest, balances there for a moment, confronted by a white child with a stick aimed like a rifle, and tumbles out of the terrifying unknown into the white settlement.

Gemmy Fairley is a London slum child who survived the appalling conditions of the Industrial Revolution by becoming the “boy” (we are left to imagine some of his duties) of a London rat catcher. Escaping to sea, he is thrown overboard near the Queensland shore and lives for ten years with an Aboriginal tribe. He can neither read nor write, and can barely speak any English, but is induced to tell his story to the local parson and schoolmaster who, to his fascination, write it down.

Taken in and cared for by the family of the child who “discovered” Gemmy, he is given work, taught again to speak English, and partially integrated into the community. This is helped along by two strange women who have built a real house – as distinct from the crude shacks of the Scots – and who establish a kind of genteel “salon” which includes not only the young school teacher and some of his pupils, but also Gemmy (Taylor, 1993: 123-25).

It all falls apart. Fear grows – and violence with it – that Gemmy might be an infiltrator and spy for hostile Aboriginals. He disappears, taking with him a handful of the children’s school exercises which, being illiterate, he thinks is his appalling life as it was written down by the teacher on his arrival. And the novel leaps, for its final chapter, fifty years or so (Taylor, 1993: 123-25).

This is where the novel's title makes sense: *Remembering Babylon*. Gemmy Fairley was another language injected into the settlers' world: he was once Cockney, he was more particularly Aboriginal, above all else he was Threat. Having proved that he could exist there, he came out of Nowhere and, therefore, demonstrated that others could too. He divided the unanimity of the settlement, made them argue amongst themselves. He set tongue against tongue, and created Babel. And remembering? One of the children who encountered Gemmy that day was a girl who became a nun. The boy with the stick, her cousin (like Gemmy, an orphan, but a luckier one), became a member of State Parliament. His career is compromised, during the Great War, by the revelation that his cousin has been corresponding with a German.

The topic? How bees communicate, a subject that she has been researching in her convent. The authorities think she may be dealing in code (Taylor, 1993: 123-25).

The sudden leap in time near the book's conclusion is only one of its audacities. Some may find it unsettling; others utterly compelling. Another is the actual conclusion, as positive as anything in modern fiction in English. But then Malouf has never been afraid of the grand statement so few of his contemporaries would dare. He can do it gently, subtly, with the force of a revelation rather than a pronouncement.

Malouf's reputation is so secure nowadays that he might almost get away with anything. The real reason why he can get away with what he does is because he gets it right. *Remembering Babylon* is yet another demonstration of how right he gets it. Truth and language do not fit so well as Kant hoped they would. But in a language of great subtlety and beauty, Malouf suggests that there may be another way of bridging the gap between our minds and what we are trying to understand, so that the world can be "in touch now with its other life". Of discovering, in other words, the truth about itself.

3. Two Features of Post-Colonial, Multiple Identities

From our discussion above we pick up just two features of postcolonial identities: hybridity and utopian vision with a view to appreciate an elaborate, complex and even conflicting identities. For this we base ourselves mainly on Malouf.

Hybrid Identities through Difference

Resistance or response from a member of a colonised community: David Malouf's *Remembering Babylon* strictly speaking, a post-colonial text. Most would agree with Malouf it is certainly not an example of resistance or response from a member of a colonised community in the same vein as, several themes running through the novel which constitute elements of post-colonial discourse, leading to a possible empowerment of both the colonisers and the colonised.

The power of language: The construction of this new identity would both privilege and discriminate against the other smaller (elite) communities, who in turn took advantage its opportunities and resisted its constraints. So the identity is tied to language, which has unimaginable power.

Hybrid Culture

There is a pervasive sense of colonial guilt throughout *Remembering Babylon*, an awareness of the suspect morality of the colonial process. Like *Great Expectations*, *Babylon* recognises Australia as a potential utopia for the industrious European immigrant – unlike Dickens, however, Malouf asserts that the success of the project rests not on merely exploiting the resources available (while ignoring or displacing the indigenous people), but on reaching a kind of harmony and exchange with the landscape and with the colonised. This hybrid culture represents, for Malouf, the ideal ultimate outcome of the colonial process (Dunlop, 1997).

4. Concluding Remarks

“Our first business will be to supervise the making of fables and legends, rejecting all which are unsatisfactory; and we shall induce nurses and mothers to tell their children only those which we have approved.” – Socrates in Plato’s *Republic*

For generations, humans gathered around hearth and fire to tell and retell stories. Much of cultural transmission was in the form of storytelling. Today, people are more likely to gather around the cool glow of the television, but we are no less storied creatures. Some imaginary calculations of the amount of time and money spent on the entertainment, news, and publishing industries should give us pause to think about how central storytelling is to our humanity. To this add the everyday interactions with friends and families in which people recount events and share gossip. By my rough estimation, perhaps fifty percent or more of our waking hours is involved in storytelling. In the words of sociologist Christian Smith, humans are “animals who make stories but also animals who are *made* by our stories” (Smith, 2003: 64).

Stories always have normative content, describing what is important, what is unimportant, what is better, what is worse, what is good, and what is bad. Charles Taylor argues that stories about self and society are how humans construct the “horizons of meaning” that form the critical background for social relations and life choices. Narratives always represent a kind of movement in moral space. Narratives are the way that humans have of constructing coherence and continuity in our lives. (Taylor 1989). So they help us fashion our selfhoods through differences.

It is important to emphasize that humans can hold multiple narratives, sometimes mutually exclusive. We mix and match. The conservative Roman Catholic narrative is incompatible with the narrative of Liberal Democracy, but that does not prevent most conservative Roman Catholics from being enthusiastic supporters of Liberal Democracies. The Christian narrative appears incompatible with capitalist virtues, but that does not prevent Christians from living the bourgeois life. The eco-

romantic narrative appears incompatible with much of modern technology, but that does not prevent environmentalists from using soon to be obsolete laptops and flying around the world to enjoy ecotourism. Each generation reinterprets these narratives in different situations, even as each generation is also constituted by these received stories. People are not passive recipients of these narratives, but active reinterpreters.

The idealized past narrative above contrasts sharply with progressive, future oriented narratives, for instance the Scientific Enlightenment narrative or the Capitalist Prosperity narrative. This nostalgia narrative is woven into many of the fundamentalist religious movements today whether in the East or West, the North or South. One can argue with this nostalgia narrative, but evidence alone cannot compel someone to believe otherwise. Like all of the narratives listed and described by Christian Smith, it involves a certain reading of history and a certain set of assumptions about what really matters in life (Smith, 2003).

As contemporary philosopher William Grassie shows the greatest untruths will always be the unconscious lies that we tell ourselves, the mistaking of our own limited perspectives with the Absolute. Reinhold Niebuhr summed it up, when he quipped “The doctrine of original sin is the only empirically verifiable doctrine of Christianity” (Niebuhr 1941). To avoid sin, we should be humble, rigorous, courageous, and creative in pursuing truth (and beauty and goodness), wherever it leads. And the goal of intellectual nonviolence and postcolonial assertion of identities is to set out in as many different directions as possible, to be multiply converted to diverse metanarratives, inhabiting their truths, forgiving their failures, taking the best, and leaving the rest. This enables us to fashion multiple (even conflicting) selfhoods, respect differences and so understand ourselves – colonisers, colonised and their hybrid children – deeper.

The paradoxical observation of William Butler Yeats (1865-1939) is apt here (Yeats: 1919):

Things fall apart; the centre cannot hold;
Mere anarchy is loosed upon the world,
The blood-dimmed tide is loosed, and everywhere
The ceremony of innocence is drowned;
The best lack all conviction, while the worst
Are full of passionate intensity.
Surely some revelation is at hand...

Drawing from the multiple postcolonial identities, can we still reduce the individual and collective violence – both real and imagined – we inflict on ourselves and others due to our imaginary identities, constructed selfhood, derived self-fashioning and amplified differences? So the challenge now is to realise our own multiple and conflicting identities of the self and those of the other. Then we can enter into a creative and complex dialogue between them, enabling us to befriend the “others” in the Other and “Otherness”.

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Notes

1. This article is adapted from my paper published in Ferrao, V., & In Ponniah, J. (2013). Identity, difference and conflict: Postcolonial critique : papers presented at the ACPI Annual Research Seminar held at Jnana-Deepa Vidyapeeth, Pune, 26-29 October 2012.
2. Grewal, 2009: 146. Arundhati Roy is not only an accomplished novelist, but equally gifted in unraveling the politics of globalization, the power and ideology of corporate culture, fundamentalism, terrorism, and other issues gripping today's world. This volume – featuring prominent scholars from throughout the world – examines Roy beyond the aesthetic parameters of her fiction, focusing also on her creative activism and struggles in global politics. The chapters travel to and fro between her non-fictional works – engaging activism on the streets and global forums – and its underlying roots in her novel. Roy is examined as a novelist, non-fiction writer, journalist, activist, feminist, screenwriter, ideologist, and architect. This volume presents Roy's interlocking network of the ideas, attitudes and ideologies that emerge from the contemporary social and the political world.

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Growing as a Person: From Befriending the Self to Befriending the Other

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Abstract: Growing as a person often entails a long journey from befriending the self to befriending the other. This journey may be depicted in terms of a wide spectrum that consists of numerous states of awareness. One pole of the spectrum is an extreme form of self-absorption, while the other pole is an expansive sense of being other-oriented. There are three broad ranges of awareness on this spectrum: befriending the self, befriending others largely within one's community and befriending others beyond one's community.

Personal growth is an ongoing task and challenge, in order that higher ranges of this spectrum may gradually characterize the general state of one's consciousness. For this to happen, there is need for adequate situational or contextual grounds for growth to thrive, as well as the need for personal discernment, so that higher levels of awareness are experienced at a greater frequency, intensity and duration.

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Keywords: Personal growth, befriending the self, befriending the other, states of awareness, transpersonal growth, trans-community growth.

Human growth entails a long and often tedious journey involving many elements: discovering oneself, relating with others, living in community and being open to transcendent realities and values. Living a wholesome human life thus entails some form of success in processing intrapersonal, interpersonal, communitarian and transcendent experiences in a salubrious manner.

This article will focus on what it takes to live a wholesome personal life, in the larger context of the human, cosmic and divine world. The main thesis proposed is that an optimal trajectory or hierarchy of states of growth extends from a basic mode of befriending oneself at a lower extreme, towards ultimate human fulfillment in some self-transcendent form of befriending the ‘other,’ at a more refined and wholesome extreme. The operative presupposition is that optimal personal growth needs to factor in community concerns and relationships, as well as the larger cosmic and divine world of meaning and value.

We will first consider a few of the more obvious features – or general conditions or observations – related to the theme of personal growth. We will then identify a few of the more necessary normative principles that govern growth, keeping in mind that personal growth needs to take into account larger realities such as communitarian, global, cosmic and divine dimensions. The main feature of the article then follows, viz., a presentation of ten states of consciousness which delineate this range of possible levels of growth. A brief clarification and explanation of this apparently linear progression of these states of consciousness then follows.

1. Primary Facets of Personal Growth

There are many features and aspects related to the theme of personal growth. Some are more central, while some may

be considered to be more peripheral. I will present some of the more obvious features or characteristics of personal growth, as a necessary background in order to understand more adequately the nature and status of the states of consciousness which represent increasingly more wholesome ways of being human.

1.1. Personal Growth is a Mystery

The journey from being born a human animal towards the realization of the fullness of being human may be best described as a “mystery.” It does not require much observation or research to realize that while some persons make easy leaps and bounds in terms of growth, others find growth to be an extremely slow and even painful process.

While specific professions, programmes and processes oriented towards personal growth seem to abound, growth is not something that can be mechanically or systematically induced. One of the main theses in Gerald May’s insightful book titled, *Simply Sane* (May, 1993), is that professional exercises geared towards engineering personal growth do not typically meet with expected success. This is not for want of good expertise on the part of the diverse professionals employed, but rather because of the nature of the object under consideration and exploration, viz., the human person. The person is more a mystery to be understood wisely, rather than a problem to be examined, explained and experimented with statistically or scientifically.

Those who appear to be delinquent or deviant may often show signs of growth under more salubrious conditions and circumstances, while those who appear to be more integrated and centred may likely have arrived at this point in their personal journeys after long personal and social struggles. This is in keeping with the popular adage that “saints have a past, and sinners have a future.” Even the best human beings are influenced by what some theorists like Jung refer to as “shadow” dimensions of the self. There are aspects to human existence that do not easily fit

into the categorizations that one understandably employs in the human or social sciences.

When growth is forced towards specific objectives, tragic results may be generated, especially in cases of forced socialization or brainwashing. This often happens in social movements which are ultra right in conviction and orientation. Such programmes and processes often result in violent forms of social expression, and often do untold damage to persons who come within their ambit and influence. This is because the human person cannot be reduced to the same status as an object in the natural realm, or a merely passive recipient of programmes of indoctrination.

1.2. Growth is Contextually Influenced

While there is no doubt that personal growth remains a mystery, it is also quite evident that salubrious social contexts undeniably aid the progress of growth, especially during the first few years of human development. Healthy economic, political and cultural factors are very important as supportive conditions for personal growth. On the other hand, social discrimination and marginalization based on gender, race, class, caste, religion, etc., all have a very important part to play in stunting human growth. A girl child growing up in a heavily patriarchal society hostile to female development has much more of a hurdle to face than one growing up in more egalitarian cultural contexts.

Besides culturally discriminatory and oppressive forces, political instability, economic uncertainty, forced migration and war – all of these leading to physical hardship, deprivation and violence – constitute even more severe conditions for human wellbeing to take place. Some human beings have a privileged start – especially a vast majority of those in materially developed nations – so experience better conditions for growth to take place effortlessly and steadily. However, there is no guarantee that those who live in healthier social climes will *ipso facto* experience better growth trajectories.

1.3. Growth Requires Personal Effort

While extraneous circumstances have a lot to contribute towards the growth of individuals, the disposition and effort that the individual invests in his or her own development has perhaps the most part to play in personal growth. At the beginning of the human journey, unlike other animals, the human animal requires a lot of attention merely for physical survival. At later stages of the human journey, this extraneous support needs to be mirrored by an internal support process, involving consistency and tenacity of effort, resilience or the ability to bounce back from adverse situations.

There are numerous examples of individuals who have suffered tremendous social hardships, yet have bounced back in order to make a personal success of their lives as well as to productively contribute to society. Hence, social context is not the sole category which determines a trajectory of growth. Besides social conditions, individual differentiation has a large part to play when it comes to personal growth. Most parents will easily agree that while the social resources placed at the service of their children were very similar, each sibling turned out quite differently from the others. This is the psychological and spiritual challenge to sociological, anthropological and statistical generalizations. This is also in continuity with thesis 1.1. above, viz., that personal growth is a mystery and not something that can be easily mastered or even fully comprehended.

1.4. Growth may be Measured by Different Parameters

The issue of personal growth is a highly contentious one, with different schools abounding in different social or human sciences, each of them proposing competing parameters or criteria by which growth may be measured. Among the more well-known theories of personal development are the psychodynamic theory proposed by Freud and developed by Erik Erikson, and the cognitive-structuralist theory proposed by Jean Piaget and developed by Lawrence Kohlberg. While some theories give more importance

to the experiences of early childhood, others give importance to cognitive capacities, while yet others pay more attention to social adaptability and capacity building, such as the cultivation of emotional and social intelligence.

This divergent approach is mirrored by different cultural estimations with regard to how human beings ought to manifest growth patterns. Some cultures give more importance to conformity with traditional practices, while others value independence and autonomy at an early age of adulthood. Among the former, which stress the communitarian dimension, are tribal or indigeneous societies – and also a growing tendency among right-wing ideologues and activists, which some attribute to a reaction against globalization. Other cultures, which are more influenced by urban and capitalistic lifestyles and attitudes, favour individualism and personal autonomy as more authentic indicators of growth. The former or more traditional focus highlights what the person owes to his or her society, while the latter or more liberal focus highlights what the person achieves or contributes to society, by way of creativity, enterprise and risk.

2. Normative Principles Governing Personal Growth

Determining the criteria governing the issue of personal growth or “human development” is a complex and sometimes contentious process. Among the diverse theoretical schools dealing with personal development, the psychologically influenced ones give importance to personal dimensions of growth, while the sociologically influenced ones give importance to social relatedness and productivity and the spiritually influenced ones give importance to sensitivity towards transcendent and divine reality.

In this exercise we move from the descriptive realm of the ‘is’ to the prescriptive or normative realm of the ‘ought.’ While proposing norms – and later, a hierarchy of states of consciousness based on these norms – for determining personal growth, I have taken into consideration various psychological,

social, moral and spiritual aptitudes requisite for integral and ongoing development.

At the *personal level*, primary among the indicators of growth is integrity, or having and living by strong and upright moral principles and convictions. This requires emotional and spiritual intelligence and depth. Reliability and consistency of character is a strong indicator of integrity. When these principles and convictions are increasingly autonomous and not only dependent on social convention or pressure, the quality of integrity gets even more refined. Besides integrity, an important quality is resilience, or the ability to bounce back from adverse circumstances. Resilience is generally founded upon a core optimistic or positive outlook towards life. Finally, persons of integrity may be relied upon as being responsible for tasks assigned to them. Also, such persons assume responsibility for their actions and their outcomes, and do not easily attribute blame to others or social situations.

At the *interpersonal level*, integrity is manifested in honesty or truthfulness in communication. The principle of the Golden Rule – present in diverse forms in various cultures and religions – is adhered to, with mutuality and justice given a high premium in relationships. Beyond duty and justice, a spirit of sensitivity and compassion, and a concomitant valuation of mercy above justice are further indicators of a heightened quality of interpersonal relationships.

At the *social level*, personal and professional transparency is esteemed, associated with the value of accountability. The desire to contribute productively to society – and to “give back,” especially from a situation of privilege – is also given a high premium. Establishing a social situation that features fraternity and harmony within one’s primary communities and with persons of other communities in general is also valued. The idea of the “common good” takes precedence over the narrow, privatized idea of the “individual good.”

Finally, at the *trans-human and trans-social level*, respect for nature and natural resources is increasingly gaining ground as a moral imperative today. Beyond and beneath this, a sensitivity, receptivity and collaborative disposition towards the presence and working of transcendent and ultimate spiritual realities are also important factors in furthering personal growth.

3. States of Growth

Growing as a person may ideally be depicted in terms of a trajectory that consists of numerous states of awareness. One pole of the trajectory is an extreme form of self-absorption, while the other pole is an expansive sense of being other-oriented. Beyond a deficient or dysfunctional state of existence in which one is not able to even befriend oneself, there are three broad spectrums of awareness on this trajectory: befriending the self, befriending others within one's community (being at home within one's community's horizon of meaning and purpose) and befriending others beyond one's community (being at home with communities and concerns that transcend one's own and one's community's horizon of meaning and purpose).

3.1. Individually Focused Growth: Befriending the Self

Befriending oneself is not as easy as it seems, given the stresses and strains of family and social life. A primal, yet prevalent state of existence that many human beings find difficult to transcend is that of a nagging self-doubt, self-pity and even self-loathing. Beneath these sentiments lies a range of emotions such as fear, shame and unhealthy guilt. In these circumstances, it is difficult to befriend even oneself, leave aside the other. This state of existence may be characterized as *phobic*, as many of the emotions experienced are related to some form of fear or anxiety. Psychoanalytic theorists pay special attention to early childhood experiences – especially related to different forms of fear – to help explain later dispositions and behaviour patterns. However, besides personal wounded memories and lack of opportunities for freedom and flourishing, there may be various oppressive

social situations which cause phobia: economic uncertainty, political strife, cultural marginalization – all of these are factors which do not easily allow people to go beyond this dysfunctional state of consciousness.

The most basic manner of befriending oneself may at first be manifested in *egotistic* or severely self-centred, narcissistic behaviour. This may seem personally and socially dysfunctional, but it is somewhat better than being plagued by powerful negative forces (at the *phobic* level) that leave one psychospiritually scarred and crippled. While narcissism may have its origins in personal life narratives, it may also be caused by strong cultural factors. For example, living in a strong capitalistic milieu naturally gives rise to a spirit of competition for goods and services. In such situations, educational institutions and corporate industries encourage pitting oneself against others in diverse fields of productive enterprises.

The next state beyond the egotistic may be termed the *aesthetic*, in the limited and technical sense in which Kierkegaard uses it as a primal or basic stage of human flourishing. This state of consciousness corresponds to a life driven by the pursuits of varied pleasures. There is a need to get out of one's skin in order to engage with the larger world, even though this engagement may largely be characterized by instrumental relationships. It is important to differentiate this form of aestheticism from a higher form of aesthetic enjoyment, in which the focus is not the self but rather the aesthetic object in itself – or even better, the aesthetic experience, which goes beyond subject-object duality.

Beyond the pursuit of pleasure, perhaps the best state of awareness within the limited spectrum of “befriending the self” is that of *authentic* living, understood as strategically planning and achieving one's personal goals, and thus satisfying one's ambitions in life. Some forms of existentialist thought which advocate authenticity – and in a different light, contemporary corporate culture which encourages personal achievement and success – foster this self-oriented outcome of personal choices

and achievement as a wholesome goal of human existence. While the thought of the early Heidegger may well represent the ideal of authenticity from an existentialist perspective (Heidegger, 1962), the objectivist philosophy of Ayn Rand may best represent the wisdom of living from this type of consciousness at the social, corporate and even ideological level.

When egotism, aesthetic pleasure and personal success are relativized in terms of a more important and wider value or focus, then one's consciousness automatically moves to a higher realm. This may be either furthering the interests of a community or communities with which one is identified, or even beyond, manifesting a concern about the larger human community or the trans-human realm of meaning and value.

3.2. Community-Focused Growth: Befriending the Other as Self

Growing as a person can hardly come to a terminus by merely fulfilling self-oriented goals. The impetus to befriend oneself needs to graduate to a higher level, to include befriending those with whom one shares common interests, a common vision and purpose of life, shared community practices, a collective cultural and religious background, etc. However, while affirming all of these commonalities, there is a movement to befriend the other to a large extent because the other mirrors – or is viewed as an extension of – the self. This type of awareness may then be properly termed, “befriending the other *as self*.”

Within this broad spectrum of “befriending the other as self,” there are at least three types of awareness. The most basic level is an *organic* awareness, in which one recognizes the need for social, legal and institutional order and one's place in such a shared order. Middle order managers, or those who desire to see that everything is in order and that the system runs smoothly are those who especially appreciate such a consciousness. Such a consciousness also features as a default initial state of mind for a majority of tribal or indigenous communities the world over,

in which a collective sense of belonging is valued far above individual attention, pleasure or achievement.

Beyond this basic affirmation of a commonly ordered life is a more refined *moralistic* awareness, where one is convinced of and reifies core moral – and often religious – values associated with law and order. Most culturally and religiously based traditional societies lay great emphasis on the cultivation of such a consciousness. However, there may also be dysfunctional forms of operating from this consciousness, e.g., that which is found among right wing groups, be they religiously bigoted, narrowly nationalistic or culturally chauvinistic.

When one is able to relativize and transcend the narrow observance of the law for its own sake – and for a greater social or moral good – this leads to a more radical understanding of befriending the other. Such a disposition may be termed *empathetic*, as personal compassion prevails over legal, social and moral perfection, and mercy prevails over justice. From such a position, persons are judged to be more important than principles, relationships more important than rules and regulations, and the expression of personal care more important than the mere execution of one's duty.

3.3. Trans-Personal and Trans-Community Focused Growth: Befriending the Other as Other

This interpersonally refined empathetic state of awareness is a threshold towards – and sets the conditions for – an even more evolved state, in which one is able to allow for personal and communitarian differences with one's own horizon of meaning and purpose. It is this level of awareness that may generally be referred to as “befriending the other,” but more properly as “befriending the other *as other*.” This form of awareness too may be broken down into at least three discrete types. An *altruistic* awareness is the most basic, in which one recognizes the value of “alterity” or “otherness.” This entails an admittance that there are persons and communities who live by different values, and

are possessed of a different vision and purpose in life, and that all of these have a unique status and value and ought not be reduced to one's own way of life. Based on this consciousness of alterity, contemporary currents of postmodern critique point towards many glaring instances of discrimination based either on a binary polarization (male-female, white-'coloured', clergy-laity) or a hierarchical system (class, caste). This heightened consciousness is able to recognize and affirm the mutual rights of other communities.

However, a mere admittance or recognition of "otherness" does not automatically entail that one has the inclination or the ability to genuinely empathize with people of other communities. This requires a more proactive *agapeistic* awareness – an extension of the empathetic attitude towards the other as other. Compassion and concern for those of other communities and the cultivation of companionship – etymologically, "breaking bread together" – with the other are constitutive elements of this state of awareness. One of the clearest examples of a person operating from such a consciousness is Mother Theresa, who cared for the lowly and the dispossessed from all religious, cultural and national communities. There are many non-governmental and non-profit organizations whose members also operate from such a consciousness, thus transcending the limited concern exhibited by governmental and corporate agencies – the former operating from national interests, and the latter largely from monetary interests.

Beyond even this benevolent disposition lies perhaps the highest state of awareness that humans may reach in terms of personal development. At this level of being, it is quite likely that the awareness of a self which is separate from any other reality breaks down. In this *mystic* state of awareness, one is suffused with an ecstatic experience that may be characteristic of a wide variety of ultimate values – based on one's fundamental spiritual orientation – such as love, beauty, goodness, wellbeing, existential truth and unity (harmony, interconnectedness). Numerous examples of great mystics from the different religious

traditions abound: Plotinus, John of the Cross, Sankaracharya, Ramakrishna Paramahansa, Aurobindo. However, there are numerous instances in the lives of ordinary human beings which may also feature flashes of this overcoming of duality between the self and the other, and a momentary experience of some form of transcendent reality, which in many cases may be indescribable or even unable to recall with accuracy (Egan, 1989 & Carse 1995).

Beyond these examples of extraordinary and ordinary mystics, are numerous examples of persons who systematically moved beyond individual and community wellbeing, and embraced trans-community or universal wellbeing as their goal, e.g., Buddha, Socrates, Jesus, Gandhi, Mother Theresa. Many such people found themselves living at a heightened state of human consciousness. Unfortunately, some of these – and many others – had to pay with their lives for the novel and radical vision and values they propagated to their contemporaries.

4. The Tenuous Nature of the Different States of Growth

It is tempting to consider these states of consciousness in terms of linear and progressive *stages* of growth. Also, we often assign a “character” to persons who seem to operate from a particular state of consciousness. However, regression to lower states of consciousness is always possible – and likewise, progression to higher states. Even if a person operates from a particular state of consciousness in a regular and sustained manner, it is quite possible that he or she goes through diverse experiences ranging from the phobic to the mystical during the course of a day. This will largely depend on extenuating circumstances and how one decides to respond to these circumstances. Thus, while it may appear to be natural that growth takes place in a linear manner – that is, moving from one state to the next in a steady progression – the extenuating conditions governing human life and corresponding personal responses to them introduce

necessary nuance and ambivalence into an otherwise apparently progressive perception of human growth.

People living in urbanized, capitalistic governed societies may largely be driven to live their lives at a more individualistically focused level, while those who live in rural, traditional or indigenous (tribal) societies which value communal belonging and interconnectedness over individual achievement, will by default live at higher levels of consciousness on the normative scale provided. However, a more integral pathway towards a full human life seems to naturally include all these three types of befriending: befriending oneself, befriending others in one's community and befriending the 'other' beyond oneself and one's community. A person living at higher states of consciousness will not ideally negate or repress previous experiences associated with lower states. Instead, he or she needs to build upon the past by organically synthesizing or integrating past experiences at lower states into subsequent experiences at more refined and wholesome states of consciousness.

Conclusion

Personal growth is an ongoing task and challenge, in order that higher ranges of the spectrum of growth proposed may gradually characterize the state of one's awareness. For this to happen, one needs to ensure that there are adequate external or circumstantial conditions for higher states of awareness to thrive. Besides fostering these situational conditions for growth, however, it is also necessary to discern how to respond to external stimuli – especially in adverse circumstances – in an enlightened manner, so that higher levels of awareness may be experienced at greater frequency, intensity and duration.

The attainment of consciousness at more refined states is both a task and a gift, and one cannot be assured that such a state persists without conscious effort. There is thus need for regular discernment or some form of ongoing awareness exercise, to sustain a higher level of consciousness and wellbeing. Growing

as a person is a lifelong personal project. But it is also a spiritual, moral and social obligation. Because the journey of growth from befriending oneself to befriending the other is not just an exercise in personal or interpersonal growth – it is also a spiritual, moral and social imperative.

Notes

1. Besides professional spiritual directors, counselors, psychologists and psychiatrists, the number of “life coaches”—especially in urban, materially developed contexts—is increasing exponentially, hardly meeting the need and demand of those who are willing to pay exorbitant amounts for the therapeutic mentoring exercises offered by these experts.
2. See also Marcel, 1951:149, where Marcel asserts that, “we must reject the idea of there actually being a legitimate answer, an objectively valid answer, to the question: ‘Who am I?’ . . . [It is] a riddle that, at the human level, simply cannot be solved: it is a question that does not imply, and cannot imply, any plain answer.”
3. This is the wisdom in having growth-oriented remedial programmes in places of incarceration, so that prison inmates may look towards a humane life after serving their term.
4. See Francois O’Kane, *Sacred Chaos: Reflections on God’s Shadow and the Dark Self*. Toronto: Inner City Books, 1994, which is an application of Jung’s understanding of the shadow to human, and even to divine life.
5. Peter Berger and Thomas Luckmann point out to possibilities of brainwashing in the context of the differentiation between primary and secondary socialization. See *The Social Construction of Reality: A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge*. London: Penguin, 1966, 149 ff.
6. See Thomas, 1997, for a summary description of various theories dealing with human development, from a secular as well as religious point of view.

7. See D'Souza, 2014: 301-23, for a philosophically-based schema of these ten states of consciousness, and D'Souza, 2015 for a theologically and religiously-based schema of these states.
8. While the emotions of shame, guilt and grief are apparently discrete from that of anxiety or fear, all of these emotions in some way stem from the imagined possibility of losing something valuable: name and status (in the case of shame), integrity (in the case of guilt) and a significant or prized relationship (in the case of grief).
9. According to Françoise O'Kane, in *Sacred Chaos*, 15, "those symptoms and reactions described as characteristic of a narcissistic personality can also be viewed from a different perspective: they are part of an attempt at survival, a way for the individual to confront despair over a life that, for whatever reason, has been dominated by shadow and destruction."
10. Besides the aesthetic or pleasure-oriented stage (exemplified by Don Juan and Faust), the more advanced stages are the ethical (exemplified by Socrates) and the religious (exemplified by Abraham). See Kierkegaard 1992 & 1992a for a description of these three types of stages.
11. See Rand, 1993 for a good overview of her philosophical position advocating individual flourishing.
12. The Pharisees depicted in the Gospels—who considered themselves to be upright or "righteous" (Mk. 7: 1-23; Mt. 15: 1-3)—are a good example of people assiduously living by such a consciousness.
13. The various conflicts over the interpretation of Sabbath laws between Jesus on the one hand and the Scribes and Pharisees on the other (Mk. 2: 1-12, 23-28; Mk. 3: 1-6) are a good example of conflict between one who operates from empathy (Jesus) and one who gives more importance to the adherence of contemporary social and moral codes (the religious leaders who opposed Jesus).
14. One of the main differences between these stages of consciousness and Lawrence Kohlberg's six moral stages of growth—which has been the original framework which I have worked

upon to posit these ten states—is that Kohlberg seemed to have a more rigid cognitive understanding of the nature of these stages, besides not allowing room for regression to take place. For other differences between Kohlberg’s six stages and these ten states, see D’Souza 2014

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“Today, when the networks and means of human communication have made unprecedented advances, we sense the challenge of finding and sharing a ‘mystique’ of living together, of mingling and encounter, of embracing and supporting one another, of stepping into this flood tide which, while chaotic, can become a genuine experience of fraternity, a caravan of solidarity, a sacred pilgrimage. Greater possibilities for communication thus turn into greater possibilities for encounter and solidarity for everyone. If we were able to take this route, it would be so good, so soothing, so liberating and hope-filled! To go out of ourselves and to join others is healthy for us. To be self-enclosed is to taste the bitter poison of immanence and humanity will be worse for every selfish choice we make.” - Pope Francis

Science and Theology: Befriending Each Other Epistemically

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Abstract: The author wants to indicate the need for dialogue between science and religion for the sake of human wellbeing. Science and theology have ever been the two most powerful and influential enterprises of humans determining the properties of their very being and defining the destiny of the humanity at large. The dictums and contours of the world of their meaning have been extensively processed by science and theology. The apparent dissonance between them, as was vivid in the past and even today, leaves one amused as to their meaning-making task besides raising several serious fundamental questions. Given the interwoven and overarching framework of their enquiry, what justification is there for the discordant note that they strike with each other? The tension between the religious experience and the quest for an absolute and certain knowledge, does it betray a fundamental dichotomy in the very structure of our rationality or our failure to reconcile the seemingly opposing elements of our knowledge-process? The

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belief in the fundamental unity of human rationality and the concern of science and theology with fundamental questions refuse to admit a fundamental dichotomy at their conceptual domains. There can be no tension between truth and truth. Once we discover the unitary conceptual grounds and frameworks of interaction, we will be able to identify the real problem in the apparent discordance between science and theology. The author argues that the assimilation and integration between science and religion becomes an imperative for the humanity as well. He agrees with Whitehead that “When we consider what religion is for mankind, and what science is, it is no exaggeration to say that the future course of history depends upon the decision of this generation as to the relations between them”

Keywords: Science-religion dialogue, Epistemological crisis, Revelation revisited, Science as hermeneutics, Common quest

Science and theology have ever been the two most powerful and influential enterprises of humans determining the properties of their very being and defining the destiny of the humanity at large.¹ The dictums and contours of the world of their meaning have been extensively processed by science and theology. The apparent dissonance between them, as was vivid in the past and even today, leaves one amused as to their meaning-making task besides raising several serious fundamental questions. Given the interwoven and overarching framework of their enquiry, what justification is there for the discordant note that they strike with each other? The tension between the religious experience and the quest for an absolute and certain knowledge, does it betray a fundamental dichotomy in the very structure of our rationality or our failure to reconcile the seemingly opposing elements of our knowledge-process? The belief in the fundamental unity of human rationality and the concern of science and theology with fundamental questions refuse to admit a fundamental dichotomy at their conceptual domains. There can be no tension between truth and truth. Once we discover the unitary conceptual grounds and frameworks of interaction, we will be able to identify the real problem in the apparent discordance

between science and theology. Once the problems are identified we learn to ask the right questions on issues of dissonance.

Revelation Revisited

Traditionally theology has been defined as “the faith seeking understanding.” The data of this enterprise come from revelation and tradition. The revelation that has taken place in history is encoded in the Scripture. Personal experience of God and its expressions in various forms constitute the norm of truth and authority to which believers respond in faith. The language of revelation, so fundamental to religious epistemology is a profound proclamation before the humanly constructed epistemological modalities testifying to the non-rational and supernatural horizons of truth, over and above the rational and natural domains. Revelation comprehended in its proper sense will be a holistic activity subsuming and subserving all other modes of knowing. For this, the hermeneutical matrix and the interpretative tools of revelation must be as holistic and as dynamic as the content of any authentic revelation. The process of understanding the “historical” revelation will be an ongoing hermeneutical enterprise so as to encounter the trans-historical aspects of the divine mysteries.

Nevertheless, the apologetic writings relying heavily on rational and historical evidences for the legitimization of revelation have tended to enclose it into quite parochial frameworks of reason, history, etc. The categories of revelation have been conceived of as products than processes. When the language of revelation is conceived as complete in itself, a beleaguered recourse to faith alone becomes the only way to comprehend them. This realist approach towards revelation with its consequent faith reductionism have forced the compartmentalization of itself as yet another mode of knowing, often in tension with other modes, perpetuating a radical dichotomy at the heart of the activity of knowledge. Truth has been considered as an object to be preserved in custody. The extreme reliance on faith and static outlook towards truth seem to have alienated the revelatory truth from cognitive and natural credibility.

The final outcome was a systematically produced disillusionment in at least some of the hearers of revelation.

The claims of the supremacy of authority was evident in the statement of Pope Pius XII: "Investigations in science may go forward as long as all are prepared to submit to the judgment of the Church...." (Pius XII, 1990: 181). The claims of the supremacy of revealed knowledge on supernatural grounds is very vulnerable to critical assault, because the parochial understanding of theology of the supernatural as well as natural rules out the critical analysis of the fundamental assumptions of its own categories. An adequate knowledge of the material, physical, and biological aspects of the object of description ever escaped the attention of dogmatic formulations. Hence at the basis of theological knowledge was a set of static categories.

This is not to overlook the hermeneutical or mystical consciousness of theology. Despite the awareness of the historical and cultural dependence of the theological statements, a serious consideration of the material and the organic matrix and the laws and principles governing it which permeate every animate and inanimate being still eludes theology. The Scripture had underscored the role of the created realities in unraveling the mystery of the creator. "They shall not hurt or destroy in my entire holy mountain; for the earth shall be full of the knowledge of the LORD as the waters cover the sea" (Is.11:9 RSV). "Ever since the creation of the world, the invisible existence of God and his everlasting power have been clearly seen by the minds understanding of created things" (Rm.1:20). In the fourth century St. Augustine had called nature the prime Word of God. However it is doubtful whether these verses have obtained sufficient attention in Christian thinking more than their rhetorical and aesthetic values, except for a few mystical traditions.

In the modern times, the serious challenge to the taken-for-granted assumptions of the theological fundamentals comes from physics and philosophy. Although history and historical categories are fundamental to Christian theology, except for the cultural

and social dimensions, the more fundamental nuances of being historical like space, time, etc., seem to have eluded Christian theology. The ever progressive understanding of the scientific fundamentals like space, time, matter, energy, etc., can revise the often static and deterministic nature of such concepts in theology. And as we discover the full nuances of the very fundamentals of theology many of the supernatural might turn out to be quite natural or some of the “natural laws” might be proved to be only “human laws.”

A thousand years ago, Western philosophy had raised the splendid question: what is a thing? The epistemological crisis that still haunts the Western philosophy has shown that asking “what is a thing” is also to ask “what does it mean ‘to be’?” (Isham, 1993: 81-82). As the foundations of science and philosophy are shaken by the epistemological “revolutions” of the times, a credible theological proposition that does not submit itself to such serious and fundamental epistemological scrutiny will not be able to withstand the test of the times. Unless the natural and inward dynamisms of revelation are explored with critical acumen, revealed set of truths, the very starting point of theology itself would be proved to be a secondary reality. Such an introspective operation would reassert revealed knowledge itself as not that non-cognitive or non-objective as we have made it of. This will be the great epistemological awakening into the unity of knowledge dispelling the stubbornly persistent illusion of the dichotomy between reason and faith.

There are schools of thought which still uphold the supremacy of religious premises on a discordant note. “Religious thought is concerned with language and with the riddle of life, and has no need to defer to highly specialized and marginalized forms of technical expertise (like science)” (Cuppitt, 1990: 4): “Yet it is not clear if viewing God ‘within’ nature (as implied by the scientific worldview) is any better than seeing him ‘outside’ of nature...” (Langsfeld, 1997: 111). These statements only betray the intellectual addiction to the traditional dualistic epistemology. It is

slightly surprising that St. Augustine had a challenging response to such thinking in the fourth century itself:

It often happens that even a non-Christian knows a thing or two about the earth, the sky, the various elements of the world, about the movement and revolution of the stars and even their size and distance.... How are they going to believe our books concerning... the kingdom of heaven when they think they are filled with fallacious writing about things which they know from experience or sure calculation? There is no telling how much harm these rash and presumptuous people bring upon their more prudent brethren when begin to be caught and argued down by those who are not bound by the authority of our Scriptures, and when they then try to defend their flippant, rash, and obviously erroneous statements by quoting a shower of words from those same Sacred Scriptures, even citing from memory those passages which they think will support their case (Cited in Macior, 1997: 30-31).

It is an optimistic fact that the Church has come to this realization, as evident in the words of Pope John Paul II: "It (Theology) must be in vital interchange today with science.... Theology will have to call on the findings of science to one degree or another as it pursues its primary concerns for the human person,.... Can we not hope that the sciences of today,... may invigorate and inform those parts of the theological enterprise that bear on the relation of nature, humanity and God?" (Cited in Russell, 1990: M11, M12).

Another imperative for the intersection of science and theology is generated by culture. The praxis of modern culture, including its life-styles, values, metaphors, language, myths, etc., have been generated and dominated by science. The scientific culture is universal because, as Peacocke has rightly judged, "today one of the universal languages of humanity cutting across all cultural boundaries is that of science" (Peacocke, 1989: 11). The meaningful articulation of the theological truth in a scientific age necessitates an integration of the reliable scientific insights into theology. "We need to apply our reason to our sources - the Bible, the tradition.... The contemporary person needs to hear the word that is eternally

uttered by the creator to his creation in a language that he or she can understand and respond to” (Peacocke, 1989: 11). Thus science can enable theology for a praxis based cross-cultural theology. The moral values and standards advocated by theology without scientific plausibility will be theologically arbitrary and socially unappealing.

Science as Hermeneutical

As regards science, the necessary corollary of the awareness of the unity of knowledge is openness for constructive dialogue with theology. The methodic and epistemic challenges in the self understanding of science, as discussed earlier, have dispelled the unjustified claims associated with physical and mathematical realism. Physicist Despagnat’s classic distinction between “the meaningful” and “the scientifically meaningful” as suggested by the terms themselves provide a solid analogy to the demarcation between the finite horizons of meaning possessed by science and the infinite horizons transcending it. Given that the megalomaniac claims of the scientific theories of the past are untenable and also given the new metamorphic and evolutionary understanding of them, science itself is to be viewed as a dynamic hermeneutic enterprise. More than a custodian of truth, it is a candidate for reality always open to modification and correction from the data, more accurate concepts and models.

An extrinsic dynamism that can enhance the scientific picture of reality is recognition of the relation of its truth with the religious truths. “A scientific community that ignores the relation of its truth and its life to law, to morals, and to fundamental religious symbols... only makes itself and its culture vulnerable to ideological capitulations. Ignorance of the religious in both its demonic and its creative forms can be even more fatal for a scientific culture than ignorance of new scientific and technological developments” (Gilkey, 1986: 68).

It is necessary that those scientifically trained thinkers venturing on the coupling of the scientific discoveries with theology have the

preliminary knowledge of theology as well. One author's serious contention is that the number of individuals in the universe must be finite if God is to be able to exercise care for each (Ellis, 1988: 384-386). Another author's crucial anxiety is "can God escape the consummation of the world?" (Worthing, 1996: 159). Physicist Davies Paul thinks that the speculated presence of humans on other planets causes serious problems to the Christian doctrine of incarnation whereby Christ was born only on this earth (Davies, 1987: 11). Such theological anxieties only betray the unequipped and unreflective juxtaposition of science and theology.

There is much more a broadening of the scientific horizons necessary for a full length appropriation of the theological beauty into the sciences, although it may be presumptuous to imagine so much and science may not be science as such as understood today at such a level of knowledge. The scientific assumptions on uncertainty, indeterminacy, etc., are not to be viewed as a retreat to the human pursuit after truth, but as an awakening into the innumerable polyvalence of truth and reality. This is a momentum towards the replacement of the reductionist strategies with the holistic approaches. It is in completing the picture of truth that faith and theology come to the aid of science. Unlike the age-old theological intrusions into science through the God of the gaps, today the new scientific scenario is much conducive to a constructive accommodation of the rich theological metaphors. The God of the physicists, as some physicists would say, is the cosmic order. Science also has the profound insight into the inherent harmony of the entire creation. But, will science ever be able to call this order as a principle of love? Or, to identify this harmony as a supreme ultimate, say, the Father of Jesus Christ? The rich elusiveness of theology has many things at stake whereby it can play a vital role in complimenting, bettering, and even perfecting the picture of truth portrayed by the natural sciences. Vitalising the scientific reductionist caricatures and sweeping away the vacuum of the nihilist know-how-s of science are possible only with the collective elusiveness of the religious and theological themata.

Paul Davies must be right in saying that science offers us “a surer path to God than religion,” a path that can lead to several hitherto unknown polyvalence of truth. This is not a path that neither begins fully in sciences nor that ends fully with sciences, but a path that passes through the sciences. It is a path extending down through the history of the intellectual curiosity of the humanity. The scientific colouring of this path is so tempting and fascinating that it rejuvenates and re-invigorates any passer-by on it.

The Common Quest

The unity of experience entails the fundamental unity of the expressions. The unity of experience invalidates an ontological dichotomy in reality. A true apprehension of the metaphysical unity of beings enables us to look beyond the conceptually constructed dichotomies of expressions to the unifying thread among them, while preserving the methodic and epistemic distinctiveness of the diverse modes of expressions. This hermeneutical dialectic has been reinforced by the philosophical openings provided by modern sciences. The more-than-scientific contents of the scientific questions today is an authentic assertion of the ontological unity of the scientific formulations and theological expressions. “Every great scientific synthesis stimulates efforts to view the whole of reality in its terms.... But the views of reality that originate in this way are not in themselves scientific...” (Greene, 1962: 132). This new epistemological awareness of the metaphysical One in the many can very much remedy the conceptual polarizations and discontinuities of the theological knowledge. In transcending such polarizations we learn that there is more to revelation than we have so far “seen” or “heard.” God’s intervention in history is not an occasional or irregular activity, but the God who governs history is in a way the history itself. The mountains and plains where He has appeared and spoken give us the very vision and voice of God Himself. Metaphorically speaking, creation cannot be “finished” in just six days or the number of the patriarchs cannot be restricted to three.

The scientific analysis of the world discloses to us the metaphysical fabric of the unified milieu of mystery, experience and expression with its “de-materialization” of matter and “mystification” of the world and thereby the re-enchantment of the whole of reality. This tempting metaphysical fabric of natural knowledge in a way conceives of the entire cosmos as a metaphor in congruity with the metaphorical insinuations of the revealed knowledge. It enables us to articulate meaningfully the summit points of Christian revelation like the Holy Trinity, the Incarnation, the humans as the image of God, eschatology, etc. Our faith affirmations, confessional formulae, ethical exhortations, etc., would acquire broader implications and deeper applications in this endeavor.

As the deceptively held epistemological dichotomy between science and theology gets dispelled, we realize the pseudo nature of their conflict. “Never mind whether religion and science were really in conflict; they were increasingly *thought* to be in conflict.” Once the pseudo nature of the problem is identified there emerge the domains of substantive and constructive interaction between science and theology. If God is the all-encompassing reality, the biological, chemical and physical languages also will be evocative of a deeper experience of God. The theological claim of the divine unity of creation necessarily entails a coherent and unified conception of reality. As this totalistic view of reality begins to be mutually implicated and structurally shared by science and theology, both would transcend their finite horizons into the overarching horizons of truth and reality. Tremendous will be the implications of this fusion for the perennial issues of the human pursuit after truth, viz. God, world, and human. That sets the agenda for the rest of our inquiry. The assimilation and integration of it becomes an imperative for the humanity as well. As Whitehead has remarked: “When we consider what religion is for mankind, and what science is, it is no exaggeration to say that the future course of history depends upon the decision of this generation as to the relations between them” (Whitehead. 1981: 111)

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Befriending the Other Religions: Vatican II and the New Orientations

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Abstract: in this paper the author wants to show that Vatican II has brought about radical changes in the Church's attitude to other Christian Churches, other religions and the modern world. These changes and innovations can be clearly seen if we keep in mind the totally different attitude which prevailed in the Church before the Council. Remarkably, the Council has taken several steps to befriend the non-Catholic Christians and their Churches, the non-Christians and their religions and the modern world. It is upto the Catholic faithful now to imbibe the spirit of this great Council and establish cordial relations with non-Catholic Christians, the followers of other faiths and the modern world.

Keywords: Vatican II, The Church's Openness to Other Religions, Befriending the Other Churches, Befriending the World

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In this paper I shall contend that Vatican II has brought about radical changes in the Church's attitude to other Christian Churches, other religions and the modern world. These changes can be clearly seen if we keep in mind the totally different attitude which prevailed in the Church before the Council.

The situation of the Church during the last four hundred years (before Vatican II) was largely due to the impact of the Council of Trent. After pointing out that this Council had succeeded in stemming the tide of the Reformation that threatened to destroy Catholicism and in starting a process of Church renewal, Giuseppe Alberigo observes:

But the price paid for this successful orientation cannot be overlooked; it can be summed up as a drastic isolation of Roman Christianity, now cut off and insulated from any interaction with the other Christian traditions of East and West, condemned to an attitude of defensiveness toward the modern world and, finally, surrounded by a *cordon sanitaire* to prevent contamination from alien cultures. Never in the history of Christianity had the *massa damnata* been made to include so much and so many; never had Christianity so extended and exacerbated its own estrangement from the fortunes of the human race (Alberigo, 1987: 13-14).

The Council of Trent had an enormous impact on the Church for about four centuries. During this period the Church's isolation from the other Christian Churches grew. The struggle with the Protestant Reformation and the opposition to modern culture led to the development of "the 'closed' ecclesiology of the post-tridentine period in which the Church is a fortified castle, jealous of its purity and bristling with condemnations" (Alberigo, 1987: 13-14). There was a strong resistance to all attempts break out of this fortress mentality and open up lines of communication with various cultures or to build bridges between the Church and the common human condition. The French Revolution and Vatican I only aggravated the situation. "Ecclesiocentrism thus reached levels that were new in relation to the entire Christian tradition" (Alberigo, 1987: 15).

Looking back on the Council and carefully examining its documents one can clearly see that its basic thrust was the Church's recovery of the integral Christian tradition and the establishment of cordial relations with the other Christian Churches, the diverse religions and cultures of humanity and the modern world.

1. Befriending the Other Churches

From Anathema to Acceptances

From the beginning of Christianity divisions began to take place in the Church. These divisions led to the emergence of different Churches. By the middle of the 5th century all the churches other than the Greco-Roman Church were shut out of the Catholic Church. In the 11th century the Greek Church got separated from the Roman Church. In the 16th century the Roman Church itself was split. As a result of the Reformation several Churches came into existence – Lutheran Churches, Reformed Churches of Calvin, Zwingli and so on.

The reasons for division in the Church were many and varied. First of all, there were theological reasons. Sometimes doctrinal differences paved the way for the emergence of new churches. Disciplinary matters too caused division. But there is reason to believe that social and cultural factors also caused division in the Church. This was quite evident in the separation between the Greek Church and the Roman Church. Diversity of culture may have played a role in Luther's revolt against Rome – the Germanic culture against the Latin culture. As Christopher Dawson has observed: "Most of the great schisms and heresies in the history of the Christian church have their roots in social and national antipathies, and if this had been clearly recognized by the theologians the history of Christianity would have been a very different one" (Dawson, 2002: 32). Joseph Neuner calls attention to another factor: "Luther's revolt is not primarily a theological challenge of traditional doctrines but a revolution

against the domination of the Christian people through the clergy in a spirit totally alien to Jesus Christ” (Neuner, 1983: 13).

The way the Catholic Church reacted to the members of these Churches were also alien to the spirit of Jesus Christ. They were condemned quite harshly. In the Church there developed a feeling of animosity towards the members of these Churches. They were anathema to the authorities of the Catholic Church.

Befriending Non-Catholics

All this changed with Vatican II. The Council sought to befriend non-Catholic Christians and their churches. It admitted that the divisions in the Church were caused both by the Catholics as well as non-Catholic Christians and hence “both sides were to blame” (UR 3). In unmistakable terms Vatican II declared:

However one cannot impute the sin of separation to those who at present are born into these Communities and are instilled therein with Christ’s faith. The Catholic Church accepts them with respect and affection as brothers and sisters. For men and women who believe in Christ and have been properly baptized are brought into a certain, though imperfect, communion with the Catholic Church. Undoubtedly the differences that exist in varying degrees between them and the Catholic Church – whether in doctrine and sometimes in discipline, or concerning the structure of the Church – do indeed create many and sometimes serious obstacles to full ecclesiastical communion. These the ecumenical movement is striving to overcome. Nevertheless, all those justified by faith through baptism are incorporated into Christ. They therefore have a right to be honoured by the title of Christian and are properly regarded as brothers and sisters in the Lord by the sons and daughters of the Catholic Church (UR 3).

In this text two statements are quite significant: (1) The Catholic Church accepts the members of these Churches with respect and affection; (2) They are properly regarded as brothers and sisters by the children of the Catholic Church.

This was the first step in the process of befriending non-Catholic Christians. The second step was to recognize the non-Catholic Christian communities as Churches. In an earlier draft of the Dogmatic Constitution on the Church there was a statement which totally identified the Church of Christ with the Roman Catholic Church.” The Church of Christ *is* the Roman Catholic Church” (LG 8). This was based on the teaching of Pope Pius XII that the Church of Christ, the Roman Catholic Church and the Mystical Body of Christ are one and the same thing (Neuner & Dupuis, 2008: 847, 858). The Council changed this statement to: “The Church of Christ *subsists* in the Roman Catholic” (LG 8). It then observed that “many elements of sanctification and of truth can be found outside of her visible structure” (LG 8). Whatever be the exact meaning of this changed formulation, it does imply that the Catholic Church does not exhaust the ecclesial possibilities of the Church of Christ. These ecclesial possibilities are realized in the other Churches. Hence the Council calls them Christian Churches (LG 15, UR 3).

These Christian Churches have many elements in common with the Catholic Church: Sacred Scripture, faith in the Triune God and Jesus Christ the Saviour. They celebrate baptism and some of the other sacraments. Many of them have the episcopate and venerate the Blessed Virgin Mary.

The Council took a third step when it declared that these Churches have significance in the mystery of salvation. The Spirit of Christ uses them as means of salvation for their members (UR 3).

In its effort to befriend the other Churches, the Council took two more steps. While speaking about dialogue within and without the Church, Vatican II states: “Our hearts embrace also those brothers and communities not yet living with us in full communion” (GS 92). The Council also expresses its desire to collaborate with the members of the other Churches:

Cooperation among all Christians vividly expresses that bond which already unites them, and it sets in clearer relief the features of Christ the Servant. Such cooperation, which has already begun in many countries, should be ever increasingly developed, particularly in regions where a social and technical evolution is taking place. It should contribute to a just appreciation of the dignity of the human person, the promotion of the blessings of peace, the application of gospel principles to social life, and the advancement of the arts and sciences in a Christian spirit (UR 12).

Such collaboration is to be extended to the fight against social evils like poverty and illiteracy. The Council goes on to add: “Through such cooperation, all believers in Christ are able to learn easily how they can understand each other better and esteem each other more, and how the road to the unity of Christian may be made smooth” (UR 12).

2. Befriending the Other Religions

Old Understanding of Religions

For centuries most Christians believed that Christianity was the only true religion since it alone was divinely instituted. Perhaps the best known exponent of this view was Dr. Henrik Kraemer of Netherlands, who, in 1938, published a book titled: *The Christian Message in a Non-Christian World* (Kraemer 1938). “The main thesis of my book”, he wrote in the Foreword, “is that the Christian Revelation is ... absolutely *sui generis* (Kraemer 1938: ix). Following Barth and Kierkegaard, Kraemer maintained that there is an ‘absolute qualitative difference’ between the Gospel of Christ and all other religions. “When Christianity as a total religious system approaches the non-Christian religions as total religious systems, there is only difference and antithesis” (Kraemer 1938: 131-132 & 115-120). Hence it is not possible to compare Christianity with any other religion. “There is no point of contact: ... there are no bridges from human religious consciousness to Christ” (Kraemer 1938:

131-132). Moreover non-Christian religions are, according to this view, quite incapable of leading human beings to a true knowledge of God or of salvation.

And among Catholics a Church-centred ecclesiology held sway for a long period of time. According to this theology the Church was the only God-appointed means of salvation. There was no salvation outside the Church (Neuner & Dupuis, 2008: 810). The Church possessed the fullness of truth and can teach it infallibly. She was the only authoritative interpreter of the natural Law. By and large the Church's attitude to the other religions was quite negative. It was unthinkable that these religions might be ways of salvation for their followers. In 1867 Pius IX rejected as errors the following:

Everyone is free to embrace and profess the religion which by the light of reason he judges to be true. Men can find the way to eternal salvation and attain eternal salvation by the practice of any religion whatever (Neuner & Dupuis, 2008: 810).

No wonder, then, that Catholic missionaries were not interested in dialogue and collaboration with the followers of other religions. Speaking of them E. C. Dewick has remarked:

They went out with love for non-Christians in their hearts, but not with any thought of appreciating the non-Christian religions. Their purpose was simply to rescue souls from the clutches of heathenism in this world and from the fires of hell in the next. They went to give, and not to receive; to save, not to cooperate (Dewick, 1953: 116).

In all fairness it must be admitted that there were some Catholic thinkers like Cardinal Nicholas of Cusa who adopted a positive approach to the non-Christian religions. But they were not representative of the position generally held by Catholics.

Positive Understanding of Religions

It is in Vatican II that an Ecumenical Council for the first time dealt with the non-Christian religions. While discussing the schema on the Church the Council Fathers requested that non-Christians be treated not globally but according to the religious groups to which they belonged. Hence *Lumen Gentium* deals with the Jews, the Muslims, those who believe in God and then the non-believers (LG 16). *Nostra Aetate* speaks of Hinduism, Buddhism, Islam and Judaism (NA). And Vatican II vindicates religious freedom not only for Christians but also for the followers of other religions (DH 4). Thus recognition is accorded to the world religions.

This is the first step in the Council's effort to befriend the other religions.

The second step is the expression of genuine appreciation of the positive values to be found in these religions – truth and goodness, grace and holiness (LG 16; NA 2; OT 16). Vatican II believes that God is the source of these values. According to the Dogmatic Constitution on the Church, “whatever goodness or truth is found among them is looked upon by the Church ... as given by Him who enlightens all men and women that they may finally have life” (LG 16). Here the text refers to John 1:9 which says that the Word was the true light which enlightens everyone. John is here speaking of the eternal Word and not the incarnate Word. The Decree on the Missionary Activity of the Church regards whatever truth and grace are to be found among the nations “as a secret presence of God” (AG 9).

Hence for the Council these religions are not pure human creations. God is at work in their origin and growth.

This leads to the third step. Vatican II exhorts the children of the Church:

Prudently and lovingly, through dialogue and collaboration with the followers of other religions, and in witness of Christian faith and life, acknowledge, preserve, and promote

the spiritual and moral goods found among these men, as well as the values in their society and culture (NA 3).

The Council looks upon dialogue as a means to arrive at truth through love and as a spiritual pursuit:

We also turn our thoughts to all who acknowledge God and who preserve in their traditions precious elements of religion and humanity. We want frank conversation to compel us all to receive the inspirations of the Spirit faithfully and to measure up to them energetically.

For our part, the desire for such dialogue which can lead to truth through love alone, excludes no one, though an appropriate measure of prudence must undoubtedly be exercised (GS 92).

The Council also encourages collaboration among the followers of different religions:

Since God the Father is the origin and purpose of all men and women, we are all called to be brothers and sisters. Therefore, if we have been summoned to the same destiny, which is both human and divine, we can and we should work together without violence and deceit in order to build up the world in genuine peace (GS 92).

Thus Vatican II looks upon the followers of other religions as partners in our common quest for justice and peace in the world.

3. Befriending the Modern World

Moving Away from the Middle Ages

Right from the beginning the Church's attitude to the world was ambiguous (Neuner, 1981: 449). On the one hand it looked upon the world as an object of God's love, since God created it and continued to care for it. On the other hand it regarded the world as hostile to God, since it had closed itself against God in its sinful self-sufficiency. Both John and Paul, among the New Testament writers, gave expression to this ambiguity (McKenzie, 1994: 942-944). During the centuries of Roman persecution the

Church adopted a very negative attitude to the world. It thought of itself as a community of believers surrounded by a wicked world (Neuner, 1981: 448). Baptism was the moment of decision when a person renounced the spirit of the world and embraced the spirit of Christ (Schillebeeckx, 1981: 56). The Didache has preserved a text which shows that the Eucharistic celebration concluded with the words: “Let grace come, let this world pass away (Kleist, 1988 10:6).

The Church of the Middle ages was somewhat ambivalent in its approach to the world. It fostered a spirituality based on a contempt of the world. As Alfons Auer had pointed out:

The basic attitude of the Middle Ages was one-sidedly that of flight from the world. The monastic ascetical ideal prevailed also in the world; medieval Christianity was predominantly shaped by monks. Its ideal of life had a fascinating effect also upon laymen; one thought he could serve God best and most uncompromisingly when he bade farewell to the world (Auer, 1965: 6).

There was on the other hand an effort made to subjugate the world to the Church or even to absorb it. To quote Auer once again,

In the greatness of the Middle Ages its very limitations become all the more apparent. No other age was able to achieve to the same degree a blending of the terrestrial and heavenly kingdom into a single universal order in which the temporal realms were directly ordered to the spiritual reality of the Church, and even – in order to maintain this order – directly or at least indirectly subjugated to ecclesiastical regulation. This unitary order necessarily resulted in a situation in which temporal matters were not adequately considered with respect to their inherent value nor sufficiently seen as fashioned according to their own laws. In the long run, the sacred order of the Middle Ages amounted to the same thing as Monophysitism (Auer, 1965: 8-9).

In a way the modern phenomenon of secularization is a reaction to this tendency on the part of the Church to absorb the world and not to respect it in its otherness. Gradually human beings, human society and its institutions, the arts and the sciences, work and professions began to assert their autonomy with respect to the Church and to affirm their intrinsic value. However, the Church reacted to this process quite negatively. As Avery Dulles observes,

The papal encyclicals from Gregory XVI (1831-46) to Pius XII (1939-59) continually deplore modern errors. *The Syllabus of Errors*, published by Pius IX in 1864, comes to a climax with Error No. 80: “The Roman pontiff can and should reconcile himself with, and adjust to progress, liberalism, and recent civilization.” In 1907 the Church condemned Modernism, a movement that had begun as an effort by Catholics to bring the Church abreast of the times. Much later, just as World War II was breaking out, Pius XII issued his first encyclical, *Darkness over the Earth* (*Summi Pontificatus*, Oct. 20, 1939), reflecting remnants of this antimodernist mentality (Dulles, 1974: 31).

Positive Attitude to the World

Pope John XXIII had quite a different attitude. In his Apostolic Constitution convoking Vatican II he emphatically declared: “Distrustful souls see only darkness burdening the face of the earth. We, instead, like to reaffirm all our confidence in our Saviour, who has not left the world he redeemed” (John XIII, 1991: 704). And in his opening address to the first session he made it clear that he was not one of those who “in these modern times... can see nothing but prevarication and ruin” (John XVIII, 1061: 712). Pope John’s positive attitude to the modern world has had a great impact on *Gaudium et Spes*. That is probably why it has turned out to be one of the most inspiring documents of the Council.

Right at the beginning the Pastoral Constitution explains how it understands the modern world:

Therefore, the Council focuses its attention on the world of men, the whole human family along with the sum of those realities in the midst of which that family lives. It gazes upon that world which is the theatre of man's history, and carries the marks of his energies, his tragedies, and his triumphs; that world which the Christian sees as created and sustained by its Maker's love, fallen indeed into the bondage of sin, yet emancipated now by Christ (GS 2).

There are three important elements in the Council's understanding of the modern world. This world is a world of human beings together with the subhuman creation in the midst of which they live. It is the scene of their history and bears the mark of their labour and their struggle, their successes and their failures. Though this world fell into sin it has been liberated by Christ. This is a very positive way of looking at the world. It is interesting to note that Vatican II regards the difficulties brought about by the rapid changes taking place in the world as a 'crisis of growth' (GS 4).

All this constitutes the first step in the Council's befriending of the modern world.

The second step is that Vatican II has adopted a positive attitude to the process of secularization. In unmistakable terms it declares:

If by the autonomy of earthly affairs we mean that created things and societies themselves enjoy their own laws and values which must be gradually deciphered, put to use, and regulated by men, then it is entirely right to demand that autonomy. Such is not merely required by modern man, but harmonizes also with the will of the Creator. For by the very circumstance of their having been created, all things are endowed with their own stability, truth, goodness, proper laws, and order. Man must respect these as he isolates them by the appropriate methods of the individual sciences or arts (GS 36).

Such a view leads to the recognition of the freedom and legitimacy of the arts and the sciences. As *Gaudium et Spes* puts it,

The Church is not against the use by human arts and sciences of their own principles and methods in their respective fields; therefore it acknowledges this lawful freedom and affirms the legitimate autonomy of culture and especially of the sciences (GS 59).

The third step that the Council has taken in befriending the modern world is this: It expresses its appreciation of the developments in the world:

The Council, therefore, looks with great respect upon all the true, good, and just elements found in the very wide variety of institutions which the human race has established for itself and constantly continues to establish (GS 42).

Vatican II goes on to add:

The Church further recognizes that worthy elements are found in today's social movements, especially an evolution toward unity, a process of wholesome socialization and of association in civic and economic realms. For the promotion of unity belongs to the innermost nature of the Church, since she is, "by her relationship with Christ, both a sacramental sign and an instrument of intimate union with God, and of the unity of all humankind" (GS 42).

A fourth step is the manifestation of the Council's eagerness to dialogue with the modern world. It believes that "this Council can provide no more eloquent proof of its solidarity with the entire human family with which it is bound up, as well as its respect and love for that family, than by engaging with it in conversation about these various problems" (GS 3).

In this context I would like to quote a pertinent observation made by Avery Dulles:

The Pastoral Constitution, in particular, sought to bring the

Church into dialogue with the world on a basis of mutual respect and reciprocal give-and-take... The Council sees the Church as involved with the world in the tremendous social and cultural transformations of our times, and affirms the Church's solidarity with 'the joys and the hopes, the griefs and the anxieties of the men and women of this age'. Renouncing any attitude of haughty superiority, the Council expresses 'great respect' for "all the true, good and just elements found in the very wide variety of institutions which the human race has established for itself and constantly continues to establish". The Church here professes its readiness to put its talents and resources to work in order to contribute to secular goals such as peace, freedom, justice and human dignity (Dulles, 1971: 11).

What is perhaps most significant in the Pastoral Constitution is that it conceives the role of the Church in the modern world as that of a servant. Inspired by no earthly ambition, the Church wishes only to carry forward the work of Christ who came not to be served but to serve (GS 3). Hence "Christians cannot yearn for anything more ardently than to serve the men and women of the modern world ever more generously and effectively" (GS 93). The document spells out concretely the kind of service that the Church can render to human persons, human communities and human activity in the world (GS 40-43).

Yet another step in the Council's befriending of the modern world is this: It gratefully acknowledges the benefits the Church has received from the world. Vatican II has stated:

Thanks to the experience of past ages, the progress of the sciences, and the treasures hidden in the various forms of human culture, the nature of man himself is more clearly revealed and new roads to truth are opened. These benefits profit the Church, too (GS 44).

The Council goes on to add:

Since the Church has a visible and social structure as a sign of her unity in Christ, she can and ought to be enriched by the

development of human social life. The reason is not that the constitution given her by Christ is defective, but so that she may understand it more penetratingly, express it better, and adjust it more successfully to our times (GS 44).

Conclusion

To conclude: The Second Vatican Council has taken several steps to befriend the non-Catholic Christians and their Churches, the non-Christians and their religions and the modern world. It is up to the Catholic faithful now to imbibe the spirit of this great Council and establish cordial relations with non-Catholic Christians, the followers of other faiths and the modern world.

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Notes

1. Speaking of the members of the other churches the authorities of the Catholic Church use expressions like “perverse opinions and errors”, “extraordinary boldness”, “arrogant claim” etc. See Neuner and Dupuis. 2008: 816.

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Befriending of Science and Religion: The Pursuit of Fulfilment and Happiness according to Sri Aurobindo

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Abstract: This paper tries to understand the need for befriending of so called the opposites, science and religion. In the beginning an effort is made to show how man had put together scientific spirit and spirituality to live a comfortable and happy life. Next, we see how development in science and technology prompted change s in our well-established values. That gave rise to certain values which estranged the relationship between the two. But it is the west which most feels the estrangement between the two. The East has been generally, inclusive and holistic in its approach, at least, Indian tradition is concerned. The purpose of befriending is

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explained, from human progress point of view and leading to happiness, which is our ultimate goal.

Keywords: Science-religion dialogue, Befriending science and religion, Spirituality and culture, Happiness and fulfilment.

“Science investigates, religion interprets. Science gives man knowledge, which is power; religion gives man wisdom, which is control. Science deals mainly with facts; religion deals mainly with values. The two are not rivals.” -Martin Luther King Jr.

Man, indeed is different from all other creatures, that is, his fellow-species on earth, as we observe ourselves from different aspects... As Sri Aurobindo writes in the Life Divine. Inspired by Aurobindo, I attempt understand the need for befriending of “so-called opposites,” science and religion. In the beginning an effort is made to show how man had put together scientific spirit and spirituality to live a comfortable and happy life. Next, we see how development in science and technology prompted change s in our well-established values. That gave rise to certain values which estranged the relationship between the two. But it is the west which most feels the estrangement between the two. The East has been generally, inclusive and holistic in its approach, at least, Indian tradition is concerned. The purpose of befriending is explained, from the point of view of human progress and leading to fullness and happiness, which is our ultimate goal of our lives. A life that encompasses it physical and spiritual dimensions.

Embracing the Physical and Spiritual

“The animal is satisfied with a modicum of necessity; the gods are content with their splendours’. But man cannot rest permanently until he reaches some highest good. He is the greatest of living beings because he is the most discontented, because he feels most the pressure of limitations” (Sethna & Baran, 1997: 31). It is also true that, the other species on earth live in the present moment, whereas man alone lives in three modes of time simultaneously, irrespective of the fact that he

is conscious of it or not. Why is man what he is? Why is he created with this urge to know? Mankind is further marked by differences within itself_ depending on factors such as culture, religion, nationality, wealth, education, temperament, refinement and much more. To link the past with the present and the present with the future is propelled by the basic quest to know and realize oneself. There was a time when this basic quest in man, which may be termed his inner quest, because response to this only could come through an exploration of his consciousness, went hand in hand with his external explorations of his environment, Nature, in search of better living conditions. In the Indian tradition we find the example of rishis or sages, who were an explorer of inner mysteries of life and an architect of life in its social context, capable of leading a seeker along the spiritual path and guiding a king through his pragmatic political crisis. Also he could author an esoteric hymn and be a poet of splendours of life. For these sages, life was a field of experience embracing both the physical world and the spirit.

As we look at the West, we observe that, in the beginning the story was not very different from the East. However, with the advent of philosophy, the knowledge at a certain phase of human development resulted in the formation of two different paths: the path of the spirit and the path of the mundane world. The first meant a total preoccupation with the spirit ignoring the worldly affairs and the second meant a total absorption with the matter, the worldly affairs at the cost of the spirit. It was post-renaissance period during which science developed to such an extent that, it claimed to explain the origin of the universe and man without any recourse to god. Religion, of course, has existed for much longer. However, there is the thesis, according to which science and technology, on the one hand, and religion, on the other, are inversely related. Recent resurgences of religion and religious belief in many parts of the world, however, cast considerable doubt on this thesis.

Western and Indian Civilizations

Advancements in science and technology prompted or brought about tremendous changes in values. The relation between these two great cultural forces has been multi faceted. As mentioned earlier that humanity has many angles and therefore it is mandatory to know all possible aspects of it. There is possibility of science befriending religion, because the two are not exclusive. When both of them are taken as independent of each other, equally powerful, and when they are looked at from extremes, they have always harmed humanity and played havoc with society. Be it consumerism as a by- product of materialism or technology that is misused for selfish gains. Sri Aurobindo foresaw the negative impact of materialism, science and technology on our value system, and rather at the global level, as early as 1916 which he terms as ‘mindless consumerism’ which is the dominant characteristic of our Age. He observes that, human aspiration for happiness, which is a part and parcel of spirituality, was turned into “success” as a value. In the following quote he brings out the ‘economic’ and ‘physical’ barbarism endorsed by modern science:

“[Modern science] has encouraged more or less indirectly by its attitude to life and its discoveries another kind of barbarism, – for it can be called by no other name, – that of the industrial, the commercial, the economic age which is now progressing to its culmination and its close. This economic barbarism is essentially that of the vital man who mistakes the vital being for the self and accepts its satisfaction as the first aim of life Just as the physical barbarian makes the excellence of the body and the development of the physical force, health and prowess his standard and aim, so the vitalistic or economic barbarian makes the satisfaction of wants and desires and the accumulation of possessions his standard and aim. His ideal man is not the cultured or noble or thoughtful or moral or religious, but the successful man. To arrive, to succeed, to produce, to accumulate, to possess is his existence. ... life devoid of beauty and nobility, religion vulgarized or coldly formalized, politics and government turned

into a trade and profession, enjoyment itself made a business, this is commercialism” (Sethna & Baran, 1997: 53-54).

The ripple effect of this barbarism which he predicted on education, religion, politics, is something which we are witnessing today. Aurobindo comments with reference to the concept of civilization and religion from the viewpoint of a common man, “ His idea of civilization is comfort, his idea of morals social respectability, his idea of politics the encouragement of industry, the opening of markets, exploitation and trade following the flag, his idea of religion at best a pietistic formalism or the satisfaction of certain vitalistic emotions” (Sethna & Baran, 1997: 54). The advancement in science made people value education for its utility, to make a man fit for success in competitive world and socialized industrial existence; value science for the useful inventions and knowledge so that he can live a comfortable life. In other words, the great capitalists and the organizers of industry are the supermen of this commercial age.

Like Aurobindo, Rabindranath Tagore also was not willing to accept the western concept of progress. He remarks: “With what is called material progress, property has become intensely individualistic, the method of gaining it has become a matter of science and not of social ethics. It breaks social bonds; it drains the life sap of the community. Its unscrupulous plays havoc all over the world, generating forces that can coax or coerce peoples to deeds of injustice and wholesome horror” (Indrani & Shashinungla, 1975: 58). It is not that Tagore did not have respect for science, rather he advocated limited use of science confined to man’s welfare and not for plundering nature. According to him, science is truth and it gives us freedom in the realm of matter. Although he welcomed western science, yet he wanted science projects to be guided by moral ideas. For Tagore, a world of science minus moral norms is a world of violence and aggression, ‘fit for the world of tigers’” (Indrani & Shashinungla, 1975: 58).

The fast development and ascent to modern civilization during last two centuries was possible because of the exponential growth of knowledge. As far as technology is concerned, there are fascinating prospects for the future. However, the development of a highly technological society does not free us from ethical and moral demands. Science cannot divorce itself from issues which take humanity beyond science itself. The mere technological advancements of which we boast and are proud of, should also take pain to have some insights about functioning of life in general and of nature in particular. Relativity may sometimes be used as the right way to understand reality. Relativity theory seems to be a theory of nature which has explained not only contemporary empirical data but is also suggestive of what ought to be in future. Some of the issues which affect humanity at present and to which science has not provided any satisfactory solution because alone it cannot, include the political, economic, religious and psychological problems of our age. Science cannot overcome racial divisions and religious extremism, it cannot create a world which is at peace. Issues like this are very much connected with culture itself. The loss of decency of humanity is at the heart of the crisis that calls for a discussion of value. What is it that is to be accepted as a value is inseparable from culture, that is created by man.

Culture is a very complex phenomenon. We find that, in the beginning, at the visible level what matters us are the artefacts, constructed social environment, overt behaviour. At the next level, culture is manifested as values, where actions and events are assigned meaning according to what ought to be. Next, these values which are consistently useful are transformed into assumptions, rather unspoken and they constitute deepest level of culture. Our intrinsic nature influences culture. The abovementioned issues are not necessarily the problems that modern science can address, since they are the problems of the heart, of the mind, of attitude and a way of life; as such they fall outside the scope of science as per the view of the scientists.

Religion too, has failed to understand man in totality. In the garb of religious rituals, the poor, the powerless are harassed. When religion that is practiced and preached is not realistic, it becomes an escape from reality. Humanity suffers from evil and it becomes 'ugly'. The culture and values are 'corrupted' by social evils. Hence, science along with other complementary factors can play a very constructive role in correcting religion, transforming it and making it anew. Rather, culture and religion are entangled with values, which deal with all possible aspects of human life. There may be hierarchy of values in particular cultures of the world, as we find one in our own culture. The western world valued the material approach more than the spiritual or looking within, while Indians and the other eastern cultures valued the spiritual aspect more than the material. This is one of the most prominent factor for the technological advance in the Western world. However, it is undeniable that the impact such technology has made on our culture and values, has been negative, showing a kind of dissonance with already established values. The traditional values, which supported Indian civilization for thousands of years, need to be strengthened and perpetuated, as they can build a bridge between the past and the future of our country and between India and rest of the world.

Need for Befriending of Science and Spirituality

There is increasing proximity of both, science and religion, towards explaining and understanding certain basic or foundational issues like_ the nature of reality, origin of the Universe, human behaviour, evolution, moral behaviour and so on. This proximity either may lead to contempt or friendship. The path of contempt or conflict leads to self-limitation, whereas the path of friendship may open up new ways with positive attitude to understand these issues with a new paradigm.

The pressure felt due to the present challenges faced by the society, whether urban, rural, semi-urban or cosmopolitan on the one hand and the aspirations and the prospects of our future society on the other, calls for a friendship or a supportive attitude

between science and spirituality. For instance, the challenge that we face of population explosion, creating healthy societies free from pain and suffering, threats from natural calamities where thousands of people lose their lives, and most important of all is living by the principles of ethics and morality, demand urgent solutions, which the lopsided development of science or spirituality cannot provide. Humanity is forced to look forward for such solutions in the coming together of these two great powers.

According to these great minds like_ M. Gandhi, Vinoba Bhave, Tagore, Sri Aurobindo, the most important thing is religiosity than religion. Religiosity being universal, will free man from institutions, churches, temples, sections and personal Gods. The static religion with, at least some of its age-old rituals and values are a hurdle in path of new paradigm. We do recognize beyond doubt the findings of science as attractive and useful, but the world does not belong to impersonal science, as it tries to capture the world as it is without the intervention of imagination. We are wrong in adopting scientific findings when we give science an Omniscient and Omnipotent status. As R. Tagore points out that, the world belongs to ‘personality’, and human personality is such that it creates new relationships with the world. He accepts dynamism in every sphere of the universe, which constantly rearranges the meaning of things and which is displayed in his creations. The ‘truth’ lies not in the mass of materials, but in their universal relatedness, which only the human mind is able to understand. He observes further that it is possible for human personality to comprehend and transcend the details of the facts, knowledge, feeling, wish and will, as well as the individual’s memory, hope, love, activities and all his belongings. This transcendence takes place through a unity, and this sublimation is a product of love. The realization of the existence of the ‘other’ makes the “I” realize his extension. Tagore says, “I become more in my union with others...” (Indrani & Shashinunpla, 1975: 91).

Philosophers, cognitive scientist and social scientists agree that friendship is an essential ingredient of human happiness. Aristotle classified friendship into three distinct categories: of pleasure, of utility and of virtue. The first one brings direct pleasure while the second, is one where a tangible benefit either economic or political, is possible. According to Aristotle, the highest kind of friendship is that of virtue, which brings happiness. He believed that friends hold a mirror up to each other and through that mirror they can see each other in ways that would not otherwise be accessible to them. It is this reciprocal mirroring that helps them improve themselves. In the similar fashion, in the new paradigm also of religion and science befriending each other, we expect that it will work together for global happiness. The solution to the global issues facing mankind requires an ethical transformation, which lies in the area of human relationships. In the light of interconnectedness and interdependence, that is observed in nature, and proved by quantum science, we should aim at the oneness of religion. The oneness of religion asserts that, individuals must seek education and knowledge that is greater than themselves. We find that the posture of social and behavioural sciences to study the interactions between individuals is a right one. Our greatest joys as well as problems involve human relationships, and successful human relationships involve love and happiness.

Science and spirituality, both the parties involved in this relationship will contribute to the relationship in order to enrich it, since they share a complementary relationship. Care should be taken to see that this relationship does not fall into customary practice or dead habit. It should be dynamic and flexible enough to assimilate the innovative ideas with a positive attitude. This should bring about not only the material and social construction, but also new values catering to our inner life.

The need for befriending of science and spirituality is felt more by the Western world, which believes in sophisticated technology more than the Eastern culture. Sri Aurobindo in his book on 'Foundations of Indian Culture' writes about how a

culture or civilization can be evaluated: “A true happiness in this world is the right terrestrial aim of man, and true happiness lies in the finding and the maintenance of a natural harmony of spirit, mind and body. A culture is to be valued to the extent to which it has discovered the right key of this harmony and organized its expressive motives and movements” (Aurobindo, 1997: 56).

The eastern religion – what may be considered the deeper and more significant elements – are not only compatible with science but enrich its findings. The best evidence of this is science’s response to the religions of the East over the course of the last 200 years. As the French Nobel laureate Romain Rolland said early in the 20th century, “Religious faith in the case of the Hindus has never been allowed to run counter to scientific laws.” The same can be said for Buddhism, which derives from the same Vedic roots.

Also, most of the Hindu gurus, Yoga masters, Buddhist monks and other Asian teachers who came to the West framed their traditions in a science-friendly way. Emphasizing the experiential dimension of spirituality, with its demonstrable influence on individual lives, they presented their teachings as a science of consciousness with a theoretical component and a set of practical applications for applying and testing those theories. Most of the teachers were educated in both their own traditions and the Western canon; they respected science, had actively studied it, and dialogued with Western scientists, many of whom were inspired to study Eastern concepts for both personal and professional reasons.

The cooperation between science and spirituality is most noted today in the field of medicine. There is a growing body of research which suggests that, spirituality does play a role in health matters. The researchers observe that, the religious faith not only promotes overall good health, but also helps in recovery of serious illness. Certainly, science and religion have contributed towards our understanding of this universe in multiple ways, and whatever they have accomplished is truly

impressive. In order that there should be an overall integral development of humanity, perhaps the time has come for science and religion to acknowledge each other's power and influence, join forces and work together in mutual respect to help solve the world's problems. This process should bring about the change in the attitude towards values, as there should be consistency and harmony in the values themselves that we take as foundational in this journey. The goal of all this is the pursuit of happiness of mankind, which is included in spirituality itself.

Conclusion

Science and religion are not negations of each other, rather they are two great forces which have shaped humanity and its culture for thousands of years. It depends upon how our scientists and theologians interpret the working of these forces for common man, that will bring about change in our attitude towards values. The ultimate goal of humanity is happiness and well-being of all, which includes both, our material progress as well as moral development, which is a part and parcel of our quest for spirituality itself.

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“I also expect from you what I have asked all the members of the Church: to come out of yourselves and go forth to the existential peripheries. ‘Go into all the world;’ these were the last words which Jesus spoke to his followers and which he continues to address to us (cf. Mk 16:15). A whole world awaits us: men and women who have lost all hope, families in difficulty, abandoned children, young people without a future, the elderly, sick and abandoned, those who are rich in the world’s goods but impoverished within, men and women looking for a purpose in life, thirsting for the divine...I ask you to work concretely in welcoming refugees, drawing near to the poor, and finding creative ways to catechize, to proclaim the Gospel and to teach others how to pray.” - Pope Francis

Pope Francis on Migrants and Refugees

“But God asks each one of us: ‘Where is the blood of your brother that cries out to me?’ Today no one in the world feels responsible for this; we have lost the sense of fraternal responsibility; we have fallen into the hypocritical attitude of the priest and of the servant of the altar that Jesus speaks about in the parable of the Good Samaritan: We look upon the brother half dead by the roadside, perhaps we think ‘poor guy,’ and we continue on our way, it’s none of our business; and we feel fine with this. We feel at peace with this, we feel fine! The culture of well-being, that makes us think of ourselves, that makes us insensitive to the cries of others, that makes us live in soap bubbles, that are beautiful but are nothing, are illusions of futility, of the transient, that brings indifference to others, that brings even the globalization of indifference. In this world of globalization we have fallen into a globalization of indifference. We are accustomed to the suffering of others, it doesn’t concern us, it’s none of our business.”

“A change of attitude towards migrants and refugees is needed on the part of everyone, moving away from attitudes of defensiveness and fear, indifference and marginalization – all typical of throwaway culture – towards attitudes based on a culture of encounter, the only culture capable of building a better, more just and fraternal world.”

“We ourselves need to see, and then to enable others to see, that migrants and refugees do not only represent a problem to be solved, but are brothers and sisters to be welcomed, respected and loved. They are an occasion that Providence gives us to help build a more just society, a more perfect democracy, a more united country, a more fraternal world and a more open and evangelical Christian community. Migration can offer possibilities for a new evangelization, open vistas for the growth of a new humanity foreshadowed in the paschal mystery: a humanity for which every foreign country is a homeland and every homeland is a foreign country.”

Beyond an Unscientific Bias towards a Scientific Knowing for the Authentic Encounter of the Re- ligious Other: A Special Reference to the Thought of Bernard Lonergan

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Abstract: The issues related to engaging with the other, or how to welcome the other, or how we let the other feel friendly in our religious pluralistic environment. Actually this subject is not new but has been dealt with recently in many academic and also practical meetings since the encounter of the other persons would have happened frequently. However, comparatively this issue is not strange to Asians but historically deeply rooted in Asian way of life due to the rich experience of living together as a member of the community beyond the indifferent awareness to the existence of the other in the present times. Borrowing the basic insights of Bernard

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Lonergan, the author explores the unscientific bias towards scientific knowing and encountering the religious other.

In this process, the author transcends a notional or a descriptive apprehension of what we are anticipating or sensing as, now, we move toward apprehensions of meaning that live in an immaterial way within our acts of understanding. That which is not seen and which can never be seen becomes something which is understood through a form of self-transcendence which is endemic to our understanding. It joins us together as we move from a material order of things toward a familiarity that lives with meaning, intelligibility, and spirit towards knowledge societies embracing religious dimension embodied in our contemporary scientific and technological environment.

Keywords: Bernard Lonergan, Religious Other, Scientific Knowledge, Transcendence as faith in human life

Introduction

The general theme of this article is on the issues how to engage with the other, or how to welcome the other, or how we let the other feel friendly in our religious pluralistic environment. Actually this subject is not new but has been dealt with recently in many academic and also practical meetings since the encounter of the other persons would have happened frequently. However, comparatively this issue is not strange to Asians but historically deeply rooted in Asian way of life due to the rich experience of living together as a member of the community beyond the indifferent awareness to the existence of the other in the present times. This experience might be true in many ways in other places of our globe too.

However the general religious perception of the other would be unfortunately emphasized on the negative side of the Western religious world exposing especially violent issues of the crusade or the modern missionary zeal emerging in the context of the

three religious traditions, Judaism, Christianity and Islam. The image is still going on the same track with a strong bias. At the same time unfortunately the usual image is also continuously witnessing the right aspect of them also in the present life in Europe. The positive side of them is not yet communicated for the balancing perception of them in the ordinary level of the modern human life.

The Western and Eastern Approaches to Religion

This is further strengthened in the modern West. Especially when modern “secularism” attempts to deny or eradicate this point, unfortunately a false unscientific bias is conveyed: a bias that faith is not normal in human life, although this kind of diagnosis is both strange and abnormal in the context of global human history. Thus, for the ultimate security of the human life, without a restoration of this point of view in human life, no one can expect that authentic human encounters or fruitful inter-religious dialogue will emerge within the emergent pluralism of our world. Contemporary secular culture does not concern much about our human spiritual security due to disregarding the fundamental principle of transcendence as faith in human life.

In contrast, the perception of the Eastern religious world is quite distinctively intensified in the ideal image in our ordinary way of life. The negative image of the Eastern religious world, especially Hinduism and Buddhism, is not yet deeply engaged with the ordinary way of life. Unfortunately recently the violent image emerging in Hinduism and Buddhism in Asia is reversing the usual ideal image of the two great traditions. Several examples are witnessing this point sharply in the treatment of religious minority groups, the Hindu, the Christian, and the Muslim in Sri Lanka. Also in India and Burma, the treatment of the Christian and the Muslim would be indicated in the similar way. Apart from these examples, so many cases could be pointed out in Asia.

The Religious Other as Minority

In this situation, we could say that the existence of the religious other as a minority in the major dominant religious context would not be easily accepted not only in the West but also in the East. Unlike the ordinary perception of the Hinduism and the Buddhism, the situation of them is not really telling the key difference from the cumulated image of the three religious relationships, especially the Christian and the Muslim. No matter where they would exist, still in our globe, the existence of other as a minority is witnessing the very similar uncomfortable story in the East and the West.

How could we breakthrough individually or collectively this same scheme of recurrence in our globe? Why is it almost impossible to be transformed further for our human good? Where could we find the some clues to break it apart for the new integration of the existence of other for the further friendly community in our globe? Theoretically many studies have already seemingly accomplished for the solution of the problem in religious studies/theologies, philosophies, economics, political science, sociology, psychology, peace and conflict studies, and other modern academic fields.

Nevertheless the problem is recurring repeatedly. Nowadays it is exposing unimaginable extreme situation. The present international institutions such as UN and NATO and various economic associations are not able to interfere and correct it for the creation of the good order of our world. Rather it is going in further extreme way. The speed does not seem to have any break to be stopped. Many criticisms on the religious extreme matters emerging against the other do suggest a good solution but they are not persuasively compelling. Even religious solutions are suggested diversely but the reality is not changed. The problem is further solidly fixed. For example, doctrinally the Hindu and the Buddhist theory of religious other is superb comparing to the Judeo-Christian oriented theory. The former is more theoretically tolerant than the latter. Historically it contributed much broad

perspective in the relation to the religious other. However, in terms of the practice for the religious other, the latter would be seemingly more appealing in modern times about issues of class equality, human right, and gender issues.

Nevertheless, this point could not be totally generalized due to the difference of the various denominations or the different streams of each religious tradition. Still many different aspects could be found in the Judeo-Christian tradition not to welcome the gender issues and also the deeper relationship of the religious other. The opposite aspect of tolerance on this matter could be found in some branches of the Hinduism and the Buddhism. Practically they would reveal the different point as M. K Gandhi and Ven. Thich Nat Han did in their tradition. So in this paper, I would like to approach the matter of the religious other in our pluralistic global times more focusing on the human agent in any activities of our religious life in relation to the other. In so doing, I will not attempt to articulate a doctrinal perspective of the religious other but more emphasize the common anthropological play ground structurally rooted in our human subject as a common foundation for the authentic engagement with the religious other.

Bernard Lonergan's Contributions

In this essay I would like to articulate this issue for the appropriate encounter of the religious other with a special reference to Bernard Lonergan's thought of bias and scientific knowing. Lonergan does not deal intensively with this issue on them in relation to the encounter of the religious other. Nevertheless, I think that his insight could be authentically applied to the encountering context of the religious other in a pluralistic environment emerging more distinctively in our present global times due to the impact of the recent immigration labor market.

Especially, in this occasion I will raise the question of religion and science and we speak about a scientific knowledge of religion or, in other words, about how a scientific understanding of things

can be combined with a religious understanding of the same things. Some kind of fundamental compatibility towards knowledge societies would seem to be possible if we can determine how determinations of meaning in one discipline or perspective have not to be conflict with determinations that belong to another point of view. Both, in some way, exist together.

As a point of departure, two points constitute a suggestive heuristic with respect to the kind of relation which in fact exists between different human groups if we distinguish scientific groups, on the one hand, from religious or literary groups, on the other hand. Our first point refers to a difference (a contrast); our second, a connection with respect to how one kind of knowledge leads to the other.

Scientific Knowledge as Acquired

As our first point, it is to be noted that scientific knowledge exists as acquired knowledge (Lonergan Institute, 2019: 149). Its catalyst is the asking of questions as we move from what we know to what we would like to know but have yet to know. None of us are strangers to inquiry. We notice ambiguities. We notice tensions or contradictions. What appears to be may not be and so we ask questions and this asking encourages our moving into philosophic and scientific questions. We can also say that the asking of questions encourages us to move into the possibilities of theological understanding and knowledge although no theological understanding can exist, in any real way, apart from our having some kind of religious faith. In distinguishing the being of any kind of knowledge that comes from questions, we speak about *a posteriori* knowledge or, in more metaphysical terms, *a posteriori* apprehensions of being.

Knowledge as Special intuition

But, on the other hand, the experience of visions is something that is reported to us by many and various persons. It comes to us from testimonies of one kind or another where we encounter

a knowledge of things that does not come from the asking of any questions. In an unsolicited way, a knowledge of things is somehow given to us. It is a kind of knowledge that, in some way, we have prior to the asking of any questions, and because we have not sought or worked to have this kind of knowledge, we speak about a kind of knowledge which, in its immediacy, is best described as a species of intuition. It exists as a kind of unmerited gift and, on our side, if we attend to the quality of our subjectivity, we best speak about a receptivity that is purely open and submissive. In this kind of knowledge, we have an *a priori* kind of knowledge or, in more metaphysical terms, an *a priori* apprehension of being (Lonergan Institute, 2019: 145-158).

Turning to point two, in examining the order of our human knowledge, we find that *a priori* kinds of knowledge precede *a posteriori* kinds of knowledge (Lonergan Institute, 2019: 16). If our acquired knowledge of things always move from a knowledge and an understanding of things that we already have and we do not have to acquire it, then, inevitably, we are forced to admit that all acquired knowledge and its acquisition is predicated on the basis of a more primitive, basic kind of knowledge as this exists for us as a kind of gift that comes to us from sources that we might not exactly know or understand. In other words, if we turn our attention of a larger study of *a priori* kinds of knowledge, we discover foundations for scientific and philosophic knowledge that can be traced to the reality and the being of literary and religious roots. If we should refer to the seeing of any visions in a literary or religious context, we refer to condensed, compact apprehensions of meaning and being which have yet to be fully understood. Symbolic apprehensions of meaning and being precede scientific apprehensions of meaning and being and, if we retain this focus and realize its importance, we can begin to understand why literary and religious apprehensions of meaning and being have an importance that is crucial for us as human beings. We begin with these and if we are working with apprehensions of meaning and being which are provocative and

suggestive, we can move into the kind of meaning as this exists emerges in the practice of religion and science.

Concluding Suggestion

Furthermore, I would like to point to the fruitfulness of a larger framework which can be identified if we should raise questions about how or why the growth which exists in our human knowledge of things is something that can be joined to the kind of knowledge which exists if we should refer to a second kind of familiarity or a second kind of knowledge which exists for us through the human experience of visions that can be found if we should refer to how, in various literary or religious contexts, persons sometimes speak about a different kind of seeing that mysteriously belongs to them. It differs from the kind of seeing which belongs to their ordinary or common knowledge of things and it also differs from the kind of seeing which belongs to a scientific seeing of things that belongs to the genesis and the growth of scientific knowledge (Lonergan Institute, 2019: 152-154).

In other words, we transcend a notional or a descriptive apprehension of what we are anticipating or sensing as, now, we move toward apprehensions of meaning that live in an immaterial way within our acts of understanding. That which is not seen and which can never be seen becomes something which is understood through a form of self-transcendence which is endemic to our understanding. It joins us together as we move from a material order of things toward a familiarity that lives with meaning, intelligibility, and spirit towards knowledge societies embracing religious dimension embodied in our contemporary scientific and technological environment.

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Being Human to Nature: A Call from the World of Sciences

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Abstract: This article deals with the clarion call from the contemporary sciences to “befriend” nature; they also remind us that **every human being needs to move towards being human**. The call and the reminder become serious and urgent, more than ever before, as the damages done to the earth and the environment increasingly become more severe and alarming and some of the damages are even irrevocable. Let us analyze the issue from three specific angles, in which contemporary sciences invite every human being to move towards being human: the fact of **mystery**, the need for **meaning in life** and the demand for **wisdom**.

The author expects science to collaborate with other disciplines to enrich humanity. It is high time that we realized, as Philip Clayton declares, “... science alone will never provide the answer” (Clayton, 2006: xvi). To look for meaning of life merely in scientific endeavors will be like

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looking for the right thing in a wrong place, or the wrong thing in a right place... but in both the cases, we will be the losers! *Why should we, as rational beings, who are able to develop sciences, be the losers after all?*

Keywords: Science-religion dialogue, Wisdom, Mystery, Meaning in life

Human beings of the ultramodern society are invited by the contemporary sciences to befriend nature. As the technologies develop in a very rapid manner, the life-styles change drastically, the value systems undergo a lot of changes, the ways how humans look at nature and the environment also change a lot. The changes in the outlook towards nature are unfortunately detrimental to it, and that, in turn, affects not only humans but also all living creatures and the whole of the environment. This article, given this scenario, deals with the clarion call from the contemporary sciences to “befriend” nature; they also remind us that **every human being needs to move towards being human**. The call and the reminder become serious and urgent, more than ever before, as the damages done to the earth and the environment increasingly become more severe and alarming and some of the damages are even irrevocable. Let us analyze the issue from three specific angles, in which contemporary sciences invite every human being to move towards being human: the fact of **MYSTERY**, the need for **MEANING IN LIFE** and the demand for **WISDOM**.

Interconnectedness in Nature

There is a very burning need to befriend the earth and the environment. When I say that we need to befriend nature, I don't mean at all that nature is always hostile to us, nor that we are strangers to it. In fact, we all are very much part of nature. The inter-connectedness between us and nature is so much that, it is said, about fifty minerals, salts and chemical elements, like iron, carbon, oxygen, calcium, potassium, magnesium, iodine

etc., that are in our bodies are also abundantly found in nature, in plants, animals, insects and even in the distant stars, millions and billions of light years away. As we are very much part of nature, the mother earth, for instance, does not reject us when we are buried after we die, nor the atmosphere rejects the smoke that comes out when our bodies are burnt.

All these chemicals and minerals have to be in our body at right quantities and ratio. It is astounding to realize that all these minerals and chemicals are lifeless in themselves but are very essential for us to have life! For instance, the presence of iron in our body – we all know that iron is very necessary for blood production. Nearly 70 % of the body's iron is available in the red blood cells (hemoglobin) and in muscle cells (myoglobin). This hemoglobin does the job of transferring oxygen in the blood from the lungs to the tissues. The presence of the required amount of iron in our body is very important. The deficiency of iron (anemia) causes several bad effects in us like, unusual tiredness (fatigue), paleness, shortness of breath, headaches and dizziness, heart palpitations, dry/damaged hair and skin, swelling and soreness of tongue and mouth, restless leg syndrome (i.e., a strong urge to move the legs when at rest), brittle/spoon-shaped nails, craving for some types of food, feeling anxious, cold hands and feet, more frequent infections and so on. Similarly, the need and the importance of phosphorus in our body is indeed very significant – it builds strong teeth, it is responsible in controlling the mechanism of how our body stores and uses energy up, it helps in reducing muscle pain after exercises, it is important for the process of filtering out waste in our kidneys, it helps to grow, maintain, and repair tissues and cells all over the body, it is helpful in producing DNA and RNA, the genetic building blocks of life. If the amount of phosphorus in our body is less than the required amount it causes bone diseases such as rickets (in children) and osteomalacia (in adults). If there is an improper balance of phosphorus and calcium it may lead to cause osteoporosis.

We are, thus, very much part of nature and nature is part of us. We cannot but be friends to nature. Of course, sometimes when we are struck by natural disasters like earthquakes, floods or tsunamis, we tend to think that nature works out against our survival and well-being. But in many of such cases it can be traced out that nature, in its efforts to maintain its own fine balance, just reacts to our actions; so these natural disasters can be seen just reactions of nature to our actions, which are very often highly detrimental to nature. For instance, at present (May 2020) the whole world is greatly challenged by the invisible (and invincible as of now!) enemy of Covid19. More than 200 countries in the world face the brunt of this alarming threat by this virus; more than 200, 000 have unfortunately lost their lives and more than three million have been affected by this virus; our deep sympathy to those suffering in one way or the other; heartfelt condolences to those who have lost their dear and near ones; sincere prayers that those who died may find the Eternal Rest and hearty appreciation to those who work day and night to cure the affected, to curb the spread of the disease and to find out the vaccine. On the other hand, nature seems to be breathing with ease these days, with less pollution in the air and water; the Mount Everest easily visible from Punjab, a few hundreds of KM away, which was not so earlier, due to heavy pollution in the air; the river Yamuna is cleaner; about one million square KM of hole in the Ozone layer has healed itself. All these remind us that we need to rethink about life-styles and priorities in life. In fact, when we take care of the environment we actually take care of ourselves indirectly!

Needless to say that nature sustains all sorts of lives on the earth – microbes, insects, plants and animals, including humans. It is sheer arrogance (or ignorance!) on our part to think that we, as human beings, have special rights over the natural environment compared to other creatures. The earth has been, and continues to be, a comfortable home and a safe haven for millions and millions types of creatures. Every creature has a right for safe its living on this planet earth. The tendency to demand that humans have more

rights over the natural environment is known as “speciesism” – this idea was first introduced by the English philosopher Richard Ryder (1970s) and later developed by the Australian philosopher Peter Singer. Speciesism is basically a type of discrimination based on species membership; it tries to treat members of one species as morally more significant than members of other species, even when their interests are equivalent. Going along this, humans justify that they have greater moral rights than non-human animals. This kind of attitude finds nothing wrong in killing and using other animals for humans’ well-being. Of course there is a strong inter-dependence among all the creatures; one is eaten by others to survive; the food of one creature becomes the death of another one. So it goes without saying that for our survival we obviously need to depend on plants and animals. All living beings, other than humans, moved by their instincts, are quite sober, natural and considerate in using the natural resources **ONLY** for their survival and sustenance. For instance, an elephant does not generally destroy sugarcane plants or banana trees, unless it goes berserk! When it eats leaves, it eats as much as it can and leaves the other leaves untouched. We don’t find greediness among the animal kingdom and they take from nature just what they need for their survival. Some ‘intelligent’ creatures may store for future, but not for several generations to come, which only humans can do. They don’t eat for luxury, nor for pleasure, nor for taste nor for styles; unfortunately we, who claim to be the most rational and intelligent beings in the universe are doing all these three; still worse, by deliberately doing all these we spoil our health and the fine balanced fabrics of nature.

No other living being is **seen to damage and destroy the earth** and the environment as human beings have recklessly done, and are still doing; the damages are unfortunately on the increase! It is high time that we realized that rivers, oceans, forests, birds, animals, insects, microbes and so on can live without us; in fact they can even live better without us, but we can never live without them. Einstein seems to have said: *If bees disappeared*

off the face of the earth, man would only have four years left to live.” It is quite shocking; we and the whole eco-system depend on these little creatures, because the honey-bees contribute to the growth and maintenance of the plants and trees in nature by the process of pollination in the plants; if we are so fundamentally dependent on other species, and we cannot just think of surviving without them, how on earth can we justify that humans are better and more important species on the earth?

Human Being Vs Being Human!

Being born as a human being is something that has happened to us, we have not chosen or worked for that; but ‘being human’ is a choice that demands a radical change in our attitudes and actions. Biologically and genetically we are, no doubt, human beings, but to be emotionally, psychologically and morally human is our choice; for instance, I can choose to be an immoral person in my words, actions and attitudes. Human beings have to positively act to become human (and humane) in their dealings with one another and nature. When human beings thus become ‘human’ they automatically become wise, humble, considerate and friendly. They become aware of their own finitude and their dependency upon one another and nature for their very continued existence. How to be human towards nature? It is by befriending nature and the environment.

Science with all its recent researches, discoveries and inventions, seem to teach us that it is not enough that we are human beings, but we need to learn how to be human (and humane). We need to learn from science how to be human. Being human involves, among many other, being humble to learn, being considerate to live and let live, and above all, to be responsible in protecting nature and the environment, because, as the most rational beings of all the known creatures in the universe, we have the utmost duty and we are morally bound to save the earth for our future generations.

The modern philosophy of science makes us realize that that

science cannot be value-neutral but value-bound. Value-based science is the need of the hour, as the value-neutral science can easily lead us to self-destruction. Contemporary sciences force us to revisit our very concept of science; it demands us to be wise, not otherwise.

I like to approach the call of contemporary science to 'be human' from three specific angles: the roles played by *Mystery*, *Meaning* and *Wisdom* in contemporary science.

The Fact of MYSTERY

Contemporary science questions the classical understanding of 'reality'. The new discoveries and observations, both in the macro and the micro worlds, challenge the dogmas of scientism and they "radically alter the status of knowledge and the place of the knowing subject" (Magnin, 2006: 140). *The mysterious nature of matter*: Heisenberg's principle of uncertainty and Bohr's principle of complementarity suggest that the actual nature of reality escapes our complete understanding, because, "The elementary particle is neither a wave nor a corpuscle but a 'thing' that combines the two images" (Magnin, 2006: 146). Therefore, at that level, matter ceases to be 'material' and "Matter has lost its substance" (Thuan, 2006: 181). *The Mystery of the 'Fine-tuning'*: The study of biotic coincidences and the anthropic principles seems to suggest that the universe has been very meticulously fine-tuned to be ready to receive conscious human beings; being convinced of this Freeman Dyson asserts that "the universe knew we were coming" (Dyson, 1979: 250) and Paul Davies declares that "We are truly meant to be here" (Davies, 1992: 232). Fine-tuning in the universe, though may not be a proof, but a strong indicator for an intelligent design behind the universe; for instance, the initial density of the universe had to be meticulously fixed to an accuracy of 10^{-60} and this precision is like an archer hitting a one-centimeter-square target placed fifteen billion light-years away (Thuan, 2006: 184). Several scientists-turned theologians, like John Polkinghorne, Arthur Peacock, Ilya Prigogine etc. also find something more to the evolution process

than mere chance. They have gone beyond reductionism and are open to mystical and metaphysical overtones in their approach to reality. Even great minds, like Einstein, are also convinced that such fine-tuning in the universe cannot be the outcome of a mere chance.

If one argues that all these fine-tunings are just fixed by laws of physics, then the question arises: “Where do the laws of physics come from? And why *those* laws rather than some other set?” (Davies, 2006: 31). Therefore, the mystery still remains! Such a realization of mystery in nature makes the investigation of the universe meaningful and thereby gives meaning to for our existence.

The Need for MEANING IN LIFE

One of the fundamental ways to define humans is to see them as ‘seekers of meaning’. As Victor Frankl shows, the search for ‘meaning in life’ becomes more fundamental to life than food, shelter and clothing; for, even if one has enough food, shelter and clothing, one cannot still manage to live, if one does not have meaning in life. Philip Clayton shows that the meaning-quest is related to the very nature of human being and sciences alone will not be sufficient to comprehend human nature, and therefore, the quest for meaning cannot be satisfactorily fulfilled by science alone, though science may contribute something in the process of meaning-seeking.

Though humans are biologically very much a part of creation and share a lot with other creatures, yet they seem to be far different from all of them, in terms of reason, will power, ability to imagine, the exercise of control over natural passion and above all the ability to go beyond the immediate environment. However, we cannot easily define life, nor its meaning or purpose, ***because the “questioner” and the “questioned” are one and the same here.*** Modern neuroscience may succeed in mapping the areas of the brain to find out what happens when one is filled with love or hatred, fear or tranquility; Psychology may come up with

convincing theories about the good effects of love and the bad effects due to its absence. *But science cannot exactly define what love is, and since it is this love that makes one find meaning in life, science can comprehend neither love nor meaning.*

The Demand for WISDOM

As science proceeds we realize that we lose our grip over reality. The classical notions of certainty, causality, absolute measurability and stability are significantly challenged today. We are forced to get reconciled with arbitrary nature of the initial conditions, irreducibility, uncertainty, and unpredictability. By this “we are reminded of the contingency and finite nature of man” (Magnin, 2006: 142). Such realization of our finitude makes us wise and humble. We are cautioned not to meddle with the wisdom of nature that has been there for about fourteen billion years.

If we lose the sense of mystery, if we are not able to find meaning in our existence, and if we don't become wise enough not to ignore the place of values in science, we will have to face the doom of humanity. As Francis Bacon wished science must take us back to the glorious state of pre-fallen state. It should make us wise, not otherwise; unless we are smart and humble enough to learn from nature, nature will teach us some certain things in a hard way. Science is like a sword, having sharp ends on both sides and unless we are careful, we may end up using science as a tool of desolation and it would be like chopping off the very branch of the tree upon which we are sitting. In fact, Claude Levi Strauss cautions us that “the world began without the human being, and will end without him” (Levi-Strauss 1955).

Conclusion

A revised understanding of science, that is, science with the human face, will surely enrich humanity. Enriching humanity would mean, among many other things, making humans more sensible to mysteries, enabling them to find more meaning in their

existence and wiser. Though humans have enormous cognitive power, yet they are cosmically very insignificant in the vast dark universe, known and unknown. As Blasé Pascal has it, “Man is only a reed, more frail than nature, but he is a thinking reed. It does not need the whole universe to wipe him out; a breath, a drop of water, is enough to kill him...” But still humans are more powerful and noble than the universe, because, “he knows that he dies and knows the advantage the universe has over him” (Pascal, 1976: 231 & 145), whereas the universe that kills him does not, cannot know anything.

With due admiration and respect to science, we dearly expect science to collaborate with other disciplines to enrich humanity. It is high time that we realized, as Philip Clayton declares, “... science alone will never provide the answer” (Clayton, 2006: xvi). To look for meaning of life merely in scientific endeavors will be like looking for the right thing in a wrong place, or the wrong thing in a right place... but in both the cases, we will be the losers! *Why should we, as rational beings, who are able to develop sciences, be the losers after all?*

Notes

1. However, from the religious perspectives one may argue that humans are the climax of all creations and they have been created in the image and likeness of God. One may quote the book of Genesis in the Bible that God allowed humans to subdue the whole earth and to have dominion over it; but the scripture scholars seek to interpret that powerful dominion as responsible stewardship, which invites humans to be co-creators with God, in preserving and enriching nature. Genesis 2:15 says, “Then the LORD God took the man and put him into the garden of Eden to cultivate it and keep it”; this makes it clear that human beings must be responsible to take care of it, not to dominate and destroy it for selfish purposes. Be that as it may, but from the nature’s point of view, humans are one among the millions and millions of creatures in the world, though they are the only self-conscious beings.

2. See: https://www.vice.com/en_in/article/d7ezaq/what-would-happen-if-all-the-bees-died-tomorrow. Accessed on 4 May, 2020
3. Of course, from religious and faith perspectives one may say that God has a great plan from eternity that I am born and he knows even before I am formed in the womb of my mother. But still one might argue that I did not actually make any choice to be born!
4. For details see: <http://www.inquiriesjournal.com/articles/660/viktor-frankls-logotherapy-the-search-for-purpose-and-meaning>. Accessed on 4 May, 2020.
5. See: <https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/view/19108279/science-and-the-search-for-meaning-philip-clayton>. Accessed on 4 May, 2020.
6. In spite of all these special and unique features, in terms of sharing the earth's resources we cannot easily justify that we have more rights than the other creatures, as we discussed above.

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“I recognize that globalization has helped many people rise out of poverty, but it has also damned many others to starve to death. It is true that global wealth is growing in absolute terms, but inequalities have also grown and new poverty arisen.- Pope Francis

“When money, instead of man, is at the center of the system, when money becomes an idol, men and women are reduced to simple instruments of a social and economic system, which is characterized, better yet dominated, by profound inequalities. So we discard whatever is not useful to this logic; it is this attitude that discards children and older people, and is now affecting the young.” -Pope Francis

Holistic Befriending of the Other in Buddhism

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Abstract: Buddhist befriending is holistic: it befriends human beings, even enemies, and nature too. In Buddhism one befriends others, in all circumstances and without discrimination, whether they are friends or enemies, offenders and prisoners, the poor and the needy. It also includes other religions and cultures as well as nature. We find several examples in the Buddhist texts, in history and in the contemporary world. This befriending is done with an altruistic spirit, with forbearance, loving friendship and compassion. As in all religions, however, there are exceptions in the texts, in history and in the modern world. Still, overall, Buddhism has been more peace-loving and non-violent than several other religions. Buddhist and Christian befriending do resemble each other, e.g., both are opposed to malice and both go to the extent of loving one's enemy. Although there are similarities, there are also differences between Buddhism and Christianity with regard to the presuppositions, the cultivation, motivation and expression of befriending. While

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divergent world-views result in such differences, Buddhists, Christians and others need to hearken to the call of peace and altruistic love, to heal a broken world and build bridges of friendship and harmony with other human beings and with nature.

Keywords: Forbearance, Altruism, Enemies, Needy, Religions, Cultures, Nature

There are two forms of Buddhism, Hinayana and Mahayana. In Hinayana only one school is living, viz., Theravada, whose original texts are in the Pali language. In Mahayana there are many schools existing, and their original texts in India were in Sanskrit. Buddhist befriending is holistic: it befriends human beings, even enemies, and befriends nature too.

1. Befriending in the Buddhist Texts

A. Befriending Other Human Beings

a. Befriending Others in All Circumstances

In the Theravada scripture, the Buddha exhorts the disputatious monks of Kosambiya to live in mutual respect and harmony both in public and in private, asking them to be friendly in thought, word and deed, being united with one another in virtues as well as in their views. A Theravada text declares that whoever bears enmity even to thieves who sever one's limbs, with a saw, does not carry out the teaching of the Buddha. Even in such a circumstance, one should not be harsh to the thieves or hate them, but rather one should be kind and compassionate and cultivate friendliness (*metta*) towards them as well as towards the whole world. Mahayana texts exhort that one must forgive all types of offences (injury, insult, abuse, criticism), everywhere (in private and in public), at all times (past, present and future), in all circumstances (in sickness or health), in thought (not entertaining angry thoughts), word (not speaking harshly) and deed (not harming physically), without any exception (whether

friend, enemy or indifferent person), and however wicked the offending person or however terrible the injury may be.

In one of his previous lives as a Bodhisatta (in Sanskrit Bodhisattva), Gotama (a Pali form corresponding to the Sanskrit Gautama) Buddha was born as Kundalakumara, who was later known as Khantivadi [Sanskrit Ksantivadin], i.e., “One who preached the doctrine of forbearance”. Angry with Khantivadi, King Kalabu tested his forbearance, inflicting one agonizing torture after another. He first had him scourged all over his body, then had his hands and feet chopped off, and then his nose and ears cut off. Even though the king taunted him after every torment, Khantivadi never got angry, declaring himself to be a preacher and practitioner of forbearance. Finally, the king kicked him on his chest near the heart and walked off in a huff. The commander-in-chief requested Khantivadi to vent his wrath only on the king, but to spare the others and the kingdom. However, instead of taking revenge, Khantivadi uttered a blessing, “Long live the king!”

We notice in such instances that the ideal is not even to feel anger or hatred even in the most trying circumstances. We could say that, strictly speaking, there is nothing to forgive, for there is no offence taken in the first place. The ideal seems to be a sort of stoic attitude of not being perturbed at all.

b. Befriending Others without Discrimination

I have elsewhere shown how the Buddha endeavoured to reinterpret the caste system in terms of virtue and wisdom. Biologically, the human race is a single species: there is no distinction between the castes.

The *Brahmanavagga* of the *Dhammapada* defines a Brahmin as one who has banished sin (*bahitapapo ti brahmano*). The same *vagga* explains further that a person does not become a Brahmin through his family or birth, but by his virtuous life and deep knowledge. In the same vein, the *Vasalasutta* states that it is the wicked, ignorant and violent person who is an outcaste

(*vasala*). It is not by birth (*jacca*) but by deeds (*kammuna*) that one becomes a Brahmin or an outcaste. Thus the Buddha redefines caste in terms of ethical categories.

The Buddha's monastic Order (*sangha*) was open to all castes. There was no discrimination based on birth, occupation, social status or ritual purity. Women, however, were admitted by him only later – and that too, very reluctantly.

It may be remarked that the princely Buddha shows a preference for the Ksatriyas, for he maintains that they are superior to Brahmins, if one were to take lineage into consideration. He points out that a Ksatriya who has fallen into the deepest degradation is superior to a Brahmin who commits similar offences. When the four castes are listed, the Ksatriyas are frequently mentioned before the Brahmins. Is this a prejudice on the part of the Buddha, who was originally from the Ksatriya class, or of his disciples? Ultimately of course he does not put his trust in lineage. In the same *Ambatthasutta* where he makes the Ksatriya superior to the Brahmin, he makes it clear that it is the one who is perfect in wisdom and righteousness that is the best among deities and human beings. In this context, it is unfortunate that the three *Nikayas* among the monks in Sri Lanka are mostly based on caste differences.

By stressing the equality of all castes and reinterpreting the caste system in ethical terms, the Buddha brought new hope and the experience of human dignity to the many Buddhist converts from the scheduled castes who, in their quest for psychological liberation from the shackles of casteism, have followed Dr. Ambedkar into the Buddhist fold.

We may mention in passing that, although there is no discrimination with respect to caste, sexist and other prejudices do survive in the Buddhist Scriptures in keeping with their times. Monks and nuns are superior to the laity, particularly in Theravada. Women are inferior to men; in the Order nuns are subordinate to the monks: e.g., a nun even of a hundred years standing must first salute a monk even if he is just ordained;

she should never rebuke or abuse a monk; monks can admonish nuns, but not vice versa. Still, it is worthy of note that the rights of the wife and of the employee (including wages, bonuses and leave) are emphasized.

c. Befriending Enemies

In the Buddhist texts, one finds many reasons to motivate oneself to avoid resentment towards enemies. Buddhaghosa, a Theravada Buddhist, includes the following reasons in his *Visuddhimagga*: remembering the scriptural passages that exhort one to practise forbearance and avoid hatred, reflecting on the harmful effects of anger on oneself, developing compassion for one's enemies who will suffer in purgatories due to their succumbing to anger, recalling to mind the many examples of the Buddha, who in previous lives as a human adult or child and even as an animal did not entertain the slightest hatred towards his tormentors, reflecting that one's enemy may have been one's loving parents or brothers or sisters or sons or daughters in previous lives, realizing that the one with whom one is angry is not a substantial soul, but merely a series of momentary aggregates of various elements, and therefore one cannot make that person the target of one's anger.

Similarly, Mahayana texts, too, try to motivate one to practise forgiveness. Firstly, one should follow the teaching and example of the Buddhas in forgiveness. The Buddhas will not forgive people unless they forgive others who offend them. Secondly, in reference to the person to be forgiven one may reflect in this manner: the present enemy may have been one's friend, relative, or teacher in a former birth. Since Mahayana Buddhism does not believe in a finite soul, strictly speaking, there is no perpetrator of injuries and insults, nor is any one injured or insulted. All beings are evanescent and subject to pain and suffering, and so one should rather lighten their burden than be angry and unforgiving. The adversaries are conditioned by the results of their deeds (*karman*) in past lives, and are therefore not acting freely. Thirdly, one may also think with regard to oneself in the following vein: one is

suffering insult and injury as a consequence of one's own evil deeds in previous existences; one's enemies are actually one's friends and beneficiaries for they preserve one from such worldly goods as wealth and fame, and give one the golden opportunity to practise forbearance, which leads to salvation. Fourthly, one should ponder over the ill effects of an angry and unforgiving attitude: it results in terrible punishments in various purgatories, and wipes out the merit one has gained through several lives. Hence, it is better to bear up with the comparatively negligible sufferings inflicted on one in this life than face terrible tortures in the future. Revenge always brings evil consequences on oneself. Being at peace with others results in great happiness to oneself. Often one is unforgiving because of pride, which needs to be replaced by the spirit of humble service. Finally, mercy and love urge us to forgive others.

On occasion, the Buddha himself brings about reconciliation. In the Introduction to the *Kunalajataka*, it is reported that when the Koliya and Sakyan tribes were about to engage in a bloody battle over the right to the waters of the river Rohini, the Buddha persuaded them to desist from fighting by making them realize that there was no point in killing warriors of priceless value for the sake of some water that had comparatively little worth. Not all, however, paid heed to the Buddha's mediations. He was unable to persuade the stubborn monk Tissa to ask forgiveness for not welcoming some visiting monks with respect and hospitality. Tissa was unforgiving because he was angry with those monks for having abused him for this fault of omission. In fact, in a previous life too he was not willing to ask pardon.

d. Befriending Offenders and Prisoners

Unlike several Hindu texts that, in addition to expiation and reformatory punishment, also prescribe retributive and deterrent punishment, Theravada texts recommend punishment only after all other means of settling a dispute have been tried out, such as discussion, appeal to reason, repentance, etc., and even then, the punishment to be meted out is more on the milder and lighter side.

Theravada texts do not advocate capital punishment. So also, Mahayana texts are against capital punishment and amputation, and caution that, when punishment is to be administered, it should be with compassion. Justice must be restorative, not retributive. It should also be clarified that, although justice in the near future is not always insisted upon, eventual justice will normally take place, for it is based on the law of *karman*; however, as in devotional Hinduism, divine beings in devotional Mahayana can forgive sins as well as wipe out, at least partially, the punishment due to sins.

e. Befriending Those in Need

Prompted by compassion, the Bodhisattvas give generously not only to relatives, friends and dependents, but also to all those who ask for help, to the poor, the pitiable, the beggars. They give away not only external things like their house, spouses, children, etc., but they also part with their hands, feet, head, limbs, etc.; indeed, they sacrifice everything. They even transfer their own merit to others for their welfare and wellbeing, both physical and spiritual, and even take upon themselves the sufferings of others. They do all this and more at the appropriate time, with respect and the intention of promoting the welfare of all; besides they do not expect anything in return.

Both Theravada and Mahayana texts narrate hundreds of stories portraying the selfless and absolutely generous gifts of property, limb and life by men and women and even animals. Several texts, both in Theravada and in Mahayana, tell the story of the hare who, having no food, offers a guest his own flesh. Similarly, both traditions narrate the story of King Sivi (Sanskrit Sibi) who became blind by donating his eyes. The most famous story, again in both traditions, in this context of selfless and generous giving, is that of Vessantara (Sanskrit Visvantara) who, even after being banished by the king for his excessive generosity, gives away his horses and chariot, and even his children and wife. A Sanskrit Hinayana text narrates the touching story of an

extremely poor woman who gives away even the one piece of cloth that she was wearing.

Mahayana texts emphasize compassion (*karuna*) towards others. I mention a couple of examples. After Vimalakirti accepted from Sudatta the pearl necklace, whose value was a hundred thousand (gold pieces), Vimalakirti divided it into two halves and gave one half to the poor of the town who were disdained by those who were present at the sacrifice offered by Sudatta earlier, and gave the other half to the Tathagata Dusprasaha. Vimalakirti also declared that the donor who, without making any distinctions, impartially, and without expecting any recompense, donates gifts to the poor of the town, who are as worthy of the gifts as the Tathagata, performs the sacrifice completely. Santideva exclaims, “May I relieve the sorrow of all beings, may I be the doctor and attendant of all who are ill, until disease does not arise. With rains of food and drink, may I destroy the agony of hunger and thirst. In the famine of the intermediary ages, may I be drink and food. May I be an imperishable storehouse for poor beings, and may I attend upon them with diverse means of subsistence. I sacrifice, without expectation, my own being, pleasures and auspicious things to accomplish the goal of all beings. Abandoning everything is Nirvana; if all has to be given up by me, it is best that it be given to beings. May I be a protector of the unprotected, the caravan leader for those on a journey, a boat, a bridge, a conduit for those who desire the further Shore. I would be a lamp for those seeking a lamp, a bed for those wishing to have a bed, a slave to those wanting a slave.”

In this context of compassion, we must particularly mention the most popular Bodhisattva Avalokitesvara or Padmapani, who is the very embodiment of compassion, and even goes to the worst purgatory and takes on the sufferings of the tormented beings there. Possibly, because of his great compassion, he became feminine in countries like China and Japan.

f. Befriending People of Other Religions

The Buddha declares that he did not preach the Buddhist religion (Sanskrit *Dharma*) in separate portions: one pertaining to the Disciples' Vehicle, another to the Vehicle of the Pratyekabuddhas and a third for the Mahayana. Whoever makes such distinctions is confused and rejects the true *Dharma* by describing it as divided. Here no distinction is made between various Buddhist traditions.

In reference to other religions, the Buddha assures Nigrodha that, in wanting to teach the Buddhist religion (Pali *Dhamma*), he does not wish to get disciples for himself by alienating people of other religions from their teachers, rules, ways of life and right doctrines or by confirming them in their wrong views; all he intends is to help them get rid of things that cause corruption, suffering and rebirth. At another time, the Buddha tells Dhammika that the one who reviles sages of other traditions who are self-composed and free from passion obtains great demerit (*apunna*). It should be noted, however, that in the very next verse he adds that the one who reviles the Buddha's disciple who is accomplished in views (*ditthi-sampanna*), attains even greater demerit.

B. Befriending Nature

Gotama Buddha died of blood dysentery after eating a dish called *sukara-maddava* (soft pork). Scholars have different opinions as to whether this *sukara* was pork or a vegetarian dish made from such items as a sprout or a mushroom, etc. However, the earliest Pali commentaries identify it as pork. In the *Amagandhasutta* it is pointed out that destruction of life, cutting, binding, injustice, harshness, anger, envy, slander, injury, cruelty, disrespect, greed, hostility, etc. have the foul odour of rotting meat, but not so the eating of meat. When Buddhist monks went on their begging rounds, they were expected to accept whatever was put into their begging bowls. Early Buddhists were therefore not strict vegetarians. Nevertheless, in time Theravadins became increasingly vegetarian. A monk had to avoid eating animals

that were seen or heard by him, or suspected to have been deliberately killed for him. Theravada Buddhists should not be butchers, hunters and fisher folk, and should avoid any job that entails cruelty such as being an executioner or jailer. If they take up such occupations, they are tormentors of others. Buddhism also reacted against the sacrificial killing of animals.

Coming now to Mahayana, the eighth chapter of the *Saddharmalankavatasutra* is wholly dedicated to making people turn away from meat-eating. Although a good part of the chapter is in reference to Bodhisattvas, it is clearly meant for all the Buddha's disciples (*sisya*). In contrast to the earlier exceptions made by Theravada texts, this *sutra* categorically states that it is not true that meat is permissible when it is not killed or caused to be killed by oneself and not deliberately prepared for oneself by another. It further asserts that, even though exceptions have been made here and there in canonical texts (*desanapatha*, lit. directive or instructional texts), in this *sutra* flesh is unconditionally forbidden for all, in whatever form, manner or place. In most of the chapter it puts forward many reasons for avoiding non-vegetarian food. For example, given the fact that transmigration has been going on for a very long time, there cannot be any animal or bird who at one time or another has not been one's own mother or father or some other relative. How then can one bring oneself to eat a living being that is of the same nature as oneself? Flesh, which is born of semen, blood, etc., pollutes one's purity; it brings demerit, leads to rebirth as a carnivorous animal and in various demonic forms; it prevents knowledge, and is an obstacle to salvation (*moksa*). Out of compassion we should refrain from consuming meat, for when an animal sees a meat-eater it is frightened for its life. Flesh has a foul smell even when burned, and spoils one's good name among noble (*arya*) people, whose food is vegetarian; meat-eating invites censure against Buddhism. Looking upon all beings as our very own (child), we should refrain from devouring their flesh. Non-vegetarians suffer from disturbed sleep, terrible dreams and ill health. The consumption of meat successively

results in pride, erroneous imagination, passion, delusion of the mind, and lack of liberation.

Buddhist texts are also against the unnecessary destruction of vegetative life. A monk should abstain from destroying the growth of seeds and vegetables. The destruction of plant-life by monks is a *pacittiya* (“expiation”) type of offence, which requires confession. Monks were of course permitted to eat vegetables, to use twigs to brush their teeth or to use herbal medicines. The basic idea is to avoid unnecessary violence even to plant life and to develop sensitivity to the whole of nature. In fact, it is a *pacittiya* fault even to dig the earth or cause it to be dug: this is in order to avoid doing violence to the living organisms and seeds in the earth.

2. Befriending in Buddhist History

A. Asoka and Honen Befriending Enemies

In the 13th Rock Edict, the Emperor Asoka publicly expresses his remorse and confesses how the carnage at Kalinga caused him great anguish. He also declares that he pardons, as far as it is possible, all those who have wronged him. He makes peace with the people living in the forests. He wishes all beings to be free from injury and to enjoy gentleness or joyousness. He even took care to omit the 13th Edict from the texts carved on the rocks in Kalinga, lest even his words of repentance would serve as a spark to re-ignite adverse emotions in the Kalingas by reviving the memory of his fateful attack on their country.

The father of Honen, the leader of the Japanese Jodo-shu school, was fatally wounded by a gang of robbers who attacked their home. On his deathbed, his father exhorted his son never to take revenge but rather to pray for the salvation of his father as well as of the attackers.

B. Befriending Other Cultures

Already in India Buddhism assumed different forms, even though one kind may have been considered heretical by another. More importantly, when Buddhism spread to other countries in Asia, it took pains to inculturate itself into the different cultures it encountered, evolving into a wide variety of forms with differing beliefs and practices.

Perhaps there is no other world religion that has inculturated itself so much as Buddhism. Already from early times, Mahayana made efforts at translating its Scriptures into different languages. Sri Lankan Buddhists developed the practice of chanting the *Pirith* (chanting of *suttas* for the sake of protection), and participating in the Kandy Perahera, in which statues of Hindu deities of four temples are carried in procession along with the reliquary of the Buddha's tooth. In Burma and Thailand, Buddhists venerate spirits called Nats and Phis respectively, and in both countries, it is the custom for every male to spend some time living the life of a monk. Chinese Buddhism integrated Taoist mythology, and emphasized nature mysticism and faith. Techniques of *wen-ta* (question and answer) and *kung-an* ("riddles") were developed to help achieve liberation (*tun-wu*). In Japan the Tendai school, which synthesized Mahayana and Theravada, reinterpreted ordination as a sacrament. The Jodo schools of Honen and Shinran emphasized faith much more than the corresponding Chinese Ching-t'u school. Zen integrated secular arts like archery and sword-fencing. It went further than China in developing still more the use of "riddles" (*koan*) and in cultivating a greater closeness to nature, manifested, for instance, in bamboo and rock gardens. Although initially Buddhism criticized the religions of Tibet as primitive and barbarous, it soon developed a uniquely Tibetan genre. It adopted the use of prayer-wheels, prayer-flags and prayer-walls, as well as trances and masked dances. Faith in the lama (*blama*) or *guru* was of the utmost importance. Also characteristic of Tibetan Buddhism is the belief in incarnation lamas. For example, the Dalai Lama is the indirect

descent of the *Bodhisattva* Avalokitesvara and the Panchen Lama is the indirect descent of the Buddha Amitabha.

Thus Buddhism did not confine itself to one culture. Its openness, universal outlook and respect for pluralism enabled it to inculturate itself deeply in different cultures. It should be noted that in spite of the two main divisions of Buddhism acculturating themselves to different cultures, each still preserves a certain basic unity. The various Mahayana schools, which have incarnated themselves much more than Theravada, display a wide divergence in practices, rituals, meditational techniques, etc.; however, they differ but little in their philosophical or theological understanding of reality. In this way, each branch of Buddhism is able to maintain a unique unity in diversity.

C. Befriending Nature

In his 5th Pillar Edict King Asoka exempted several animals from slaughter, e.g., parrots, geese, swans, bats, boneless fish, etc., and certain animals when they were pregnant. He also prohibited the killing of fish and certain animals on particular auspicious days. In his 1st Rock Edict he forbade the sacrifice of all animals in his palace. Formerly very many living beings were killed daily for his table; but he decreed that only three would be slain: two peacocks and one deer, and the latter would not be killed invariably. In fact, he said, even these would not be slaughtered in the future.

In Theravada there developed the practice of setting up sanctuaries for birds and animals as well as tanks for fish, where they could move about freely without being hunted or caught. This was called *abhaya-dana* (the gift of fearlessness).

Similar to the case of Theravada, the custom, and even ceremony, of freeing living creatures arose in Mahayana too. It consisted in purchasing birds, animals and fish that had been captured, and setting them free in their own habitats. In China and Japan, too, different kings prohibited the eating of meat and advocated non-violence towards animals, birds and fish. It should

be noted, however, that some Mahayana schools are non-vegetarian, while Theravada is vegetarian.

3. Contemporary Examples of Befriending

A. Befriending Other Human Beings

I shall first give some instances of modern Theravada Buddhists and then move on to present-day Mahayana Buddhists.

a. Ariyaratne of Sri Lanka

Dr. Ahangamage Tudor Ariyaratne of Sri Lanka started his Sarvodaya (Uplift or Awakening of All) Sramadana (Donation of Labour) Movement in Sri Lanka between 1956 and 1958, and nurtured it for many years. Basing himself on traditional Theravada principles and also reinterpreting some of them to give them a social thrust, he set up volunteer work camps for social upliftment. Ariyaratne's Sarvodaya catered to ten fundamental needs of society: a pure and attractive environment, sufficient supply of pure water, basic requirements of clothing, an adequate diet, simple residential facilities, basic health services, communication infrastructure, fuel and other energy needs, a comprehensive education for daily living, and cultural and spiritual development. In every village Sarvodaya tried to set up six groups: pre-school toddlers, schoolchildren, mothers, youth, farmers, and the elderly. Each of these groups is conscientized and helped to participate, in varying degrees, in a holistic and all-round development of the village.

Although Ariyaratne is Sinhalese, he extended his hand of friendship and collaboration to the Tamil Hindus in Sri Lanka. His Sarvodaya played an important role as peace builder in the severe ethnic conflicts of Sri Lanka. It analysed the causes of the conflicts, worked out comprehensive programmes to resolve the problems in a humane manner, encouraged Sinhalese and Tamilians to work together as volunteers in each other's villages, organized peace meditations, peace camps, peace pilgrimages and

marches, and peace meetings and conferences; initiated ways and means for the return and rehabilitation of refugees; and, for both the militants and the armed forces, to lay down their arms and return to civilian life, through techniques of inner transformation. Although Sarvodaya was a Buddhist movement, it was open to others: Tamilians (many of whom were Hindus) too played important leadership roles in Sarvodaya peace initiatives. Tamilians who collaborated with Sarvodaya looked upon it not so much as a Sinhalese Buddhist organization, but a Sri Lankan association. In 1994 Ariyaratne met leaders of the LTTE, in an attempt to bring about reconciliation and peace.

b. Uttarananda of Sri Lanka

The Sri Lankan monk H. Uttarananda, who was a member of the now defunct Humanist Bhikkhus' Association (*Manava-hitavadi Bhikkhu Sangamaya*), proposed a Buddhist-Humanist view of the national ethnic problem in Sri Lanka. Following the typical Buddhist "middle path", he wanted to avoid the two extremes of a Sinhala Buddhist State and a free Eelam State. He acknowledged the inhuman atrocities perpetrated on Tamils in 1983 and thereafter by racist fanatics and governments, and was able to sympathetically understand the exasperated violent reactions of Tamils whose pent up rage boiled over due to the prolonged racist attitudes of successive governments. He called for reconciliation and strengthening of racial unity and peace.

c. The Four Mahanayakes or Patriarchs of Sri Lanka

In a Press Conference in Tokyo on 3rd June 2002, the four Mahanayakes or "Patriarchs" of the Theravada Buddhist Order of Sri Lanka publicly released a Press Statement, which declared that the Order was for peace and development in Sri Lanka and solicited the support of the Japanese people in the peace process and in confidence-building measures which would benefit all three communities affected by the war, viz., the Sinhalese, the Tamils and the Muslims. The Sri Lankan newspaper *The Island* reported that the Mahanayake of Asgiriya conferred his blessings

on both the UNP Government of Ranil Wickremasinghe as well as the LTTE in their efforts to restore peace through peace talks held in Thailand.

d. Sulak Sivaraksa of Thailand

Sulak Sivaraksa of Thailand is, on the one hand, rooted in the Buddhist Scripture. On the other hand, he frequently reinterprets traditional texts and doctrines to give them an explicit social and developmental orientation.

Sivaraksa founded a number of social welfare organizations or voluntary Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), in which people work with dedication for the uplift of the poor, both in the villages and the cities. Inspired by spiritual principles, they reach out to those in need – exploited men, women and children – and help them, through non-violent means, to regain their human dignity and stand on their own feet. They also pay attention to ecology and the environment: they work for integral and sustainable development.

What is particularly notable is that Sivaraksa also engages in interreligious dialogue and cooperative interreligious social action for development. He started the Thai Interreligious Commission for Development. He also participated in the World Conference on Religion and Peace in Melbourne. He collaborated with a number of Catholic and Protestant development organizations in different parts of the world. He mentions several dialogue meetings with Christians, where all were equal, challenging one another in friendship, and working together for social uplift. Over many years, he was able to build bonds of friendship with individual Buddhists of other traditions, as well as with Christians, Jews, Muslims and Hindus in different parts of the world.

e. The Late Maha Ghosananda of Thailand

In war-torn Cambodia, the late Maha Ghosananda of Thailand, five-time Nobel Peace Prize nominee, led nine *Dhammayietras* [Khmer or Cambodian for the Sanskrit *Dharmayatras*] or Pil-

grimaces of Truth to promote peace between rival Cambodian groups. Often opponents met and walked together in the spirit of reconciliation. In his first *Dhammayietra*, he preached repeatedly, “The suffering of Cambodia has been deep. From this suffering comes Great Compassion. Great Compassion makes a peaceful heart. A peaceful heart makes a peaceful person. A peaceful person makes a peaceful family. A peaceful family makes a peaceful community. A peaceful community makes a peaceful nation. A peaceful nation makes a peaceful world”. When, returning from his monastery in Thailand, he paid his first visit to the Sakeo Cambodian refugee camp, he distributed copies of the *Metta-sutta*, a Buddhist Theravada scriptural text on loving kindness or friendship, and exhorted the refugees to forgive their persecutors. A leader of the Khmer Rouge requested Maha Ghosananda to visit Thailand and build a Buddhist temple on the border of Cambodia, and the latter readily agreed. Many were scandalized that he was helping an “enemy”. However, he pointed out that love did not discriminate between good or bad; in fact, it was those who were deviants who needed loving kindness all the more because, often enough, virtue vanished from them because they did not experience the warmth of empathy from others. Quoting Mahatma Gandhi, he said that reconciliation consisted in destroying enmity, not enemies; loving kindness removed ignorance from adversaries as well as from us: we all needed to be freed.

f. Aung San Suu Kyi of Myanmar

Nobel Laureate, Aung San Suu Kyi of Myanmar, was at a public rally at the Shwedagon Pagoda in 1998. She appealed to the people to let bygones be bygones, to manifest their innate ability to forgive, not to abandon their traditional love for the armed forces and to resort to peaceful means of walking hand in hand with the authorities to build a united Burma. When she was freed in 1995, after six years of house arrest by the military, and that, too, in spite of a landslide victory of her party, she expressed appreciation for the conciliatory tenor of the announcement of release by her captors, and highlighted the need for dialogue rather

than confrontation for the restoration of peace. She declared that she did not harbour any bitterness against anyone for the treatment she received during those six long years.

g. The Dalai Lama of Tibet

Let me now turn to Mahayana examples. Relying on Mahayana principles, the Dalai Lama, who was awarded the Nobel Peace Prize, has been advocating social responsibility and concern for nature. He has always embraced the policy of peaceful resistance to the Chinese, who occupied Tibet in 1950. He refers to the Chinese as his brothers and sisters and is motivated by tolerance, compassion and love. While wanting autonomy, he admits the fact that Tibet would continue to be linked with China. In his Nobel Peace Prize Lecture, in speaking of the atrocities committed by the Chinese against Tibetans and their country and culture, he said that he did not speak with a heart filled with hatred or anger against the Chinese for, he added, they too were human beings striving for happiness and were entitled to compassion.

Elsewhere he also points out that enemies are valuable because they help us to advance in spiritual qualities such as forbearance and mental fortitude. He admits that, had he stayed in Lhasa, he might have been isolated and conservative. Hence, he is indebted to the Chinese since his exile helped broaden his perspectives. He felt very sad that Tibetans were infuriated against the Chinese and took part in burning Chinese vehicles. His purpose in narrating the trials and tribulations of the Tibetan people was not out of vindictiveness or hostility towards the Chinese, but in order to inform the public. He also felt that many well-meaning Chinese were simply not aware of what was going on in Tibet.

The Dalai Lama admits, however, that when people exploit the sincerity of a person, it may be necessary to retort. However, although on the surface level an apt reaction is resorted to, there should be an underlying spirit of forbearance, compassion and tolerance, without bearing any ill feelings. Our real enemies are not outside us but inside us, e.g., arrogance, wrath and envy,

and we have to wage a war against these internal foes. World peace cannot be achieved without realizing that we are all sisters and brothers, and without cultivating kindness and compassion. However, this is not possible without inner transformation.

h. Thich Nhat Hahn of Vietnam

The Vietnamese monk Thich Nhat Hanh did not bear any hatred towards the Catholic Diem regime that persecuted him, nor to the Viet Cong or the U.S. soldiers who attacked Vietnam. He could find excuses for the atrocities perpetrated by U.S. soldiers in Vietnam, attributing these to their hard life in the swamps and jungles infested by mosquitoes and other insects, and to their being in constant danger of death. Although initially angry, he did not blame a sea-pirate who had raped a twelve-year old girl, thinking that if he had had the same historical, economic and educational background as that pirate he would probably have behaved in the same way. This attitude of Thich Nhat Hanh is based on the Buddhist doctrine of Dependent or Conditioned Co-production (*pratitya-samutpada*; Pali *patticca-saumuppada*), according to which no being or event arises without a conditioning factor: this (resulting) being or event is because that (preceding) being or event is; this (resulting) being or event is not because that (preceding) being or event is not. It thus helps the Buddhist to pay attention to attenuating circumstances, and hence be more understanding and forgiving.

B. Befriending Nature

A number of Theravada monks in Thailand are giving leadership in befriending nature. Phrakhru Manas Natheepitak, the abbot of Wat Bodharma, is said to be the first who came up with the novel idea of a ceremony that he called Tree Ordination, in which trees are wrapped in the saffron robes of Theravada monks. Many other monks follow this practice. When people see the saffron robes wrapped around the trees, they refrain from felling the trees. Similarly, another monk, Phrakhru Pitak Nanthakun, in addition to a more elaborate Tree Ordination ceremony, also

instituted a ritual for sanctifying the river Nan, an important river in Thailand. This ceremony is modelled on a traditional rite for lengthening the life span of human beings and domestic animals. He, and other monks after him, have conducted this ceremony on different occasions and have reserved certain parts of the river as safe havens for fish so that fish can multiply without human interference.

The Mahayana Buddhist country of Bhutan has a law that 60% of its land would be covered forever with forests. The King and Queen of Bhutan announced the birth of their first child on 5th February 2016. On 6th March 2016 the entire nation celebrated the prince's birth by planting 108000 saplings. In June 2015, a team of 100 volunteers planted 49672 saplings in one hour, setting a Guinness record.

4. Befriending the Others with Friendship and Compassion

Buddhists approach all forms of befriending, of humans as well as nature, in the spirit of friendship (Pali *metta*; Sanskrit *maitri*) and compassion (*karuna*). They are two of the four Buddhist virtues called *Brahma-viharas* (Sublime States or Abidings); the third *Brahma-vihara* is joy (*mudita*) and the fourth is equanimity (Pali *upekkha*; Sanskrit *upeksa*). While Theravada gives more importance to friendship, Mahayana emphasizes compassion more. All the four Sublime States are to be cultivated or developed through meditation.

In Theravada friendship essentially consists in the wish that all beings may be happy. Just as a mother would protect her only child at the risk of her own life, even so one should cultivate unlimited love towards all beings. In Mahayana friendship is a love that consists in the hope, prayer, keen desire for, and joy at, the happiness of others, without passion and the seeking of reward. It is of three kinds depending on whether it is directed towards living beings, phenomena (*dharma*) or no particular object. Hence, both in Theravada as well as in Mahayana, friendship is altruistic

love, and therefore *metta* or *maitri* is also translated as loving kindness.

Compassion includes all altruistic aspects of love. Bodhisattvas feel compassion for living beings like a father for his dear and only son. The wise love all beings more than themselves, or their spouses, children, friends and relatives. Tormented by the sufferings of others, the compassionate ones do not look for their own happiness. Bodhisattvas desire enlightenment first for all beings and not for themselves. In some passages, we notice that the Bodhisattvas act for the benefit of others (*para*) as well as themselves (*atman*). However, in some other passages, we find that the texts speak only of the good of others, and not love for oneself, thus emphasizing altruism much more.

5. Some Exceptions

As in all religions, in Buddhism too, there is doubtless a gap between the ideal and the existential. Here are a few instances:

A. In the Texts

In the Theravada Scripture, the Buddha asserts that no Ajivaka has ever brought suffering to an end [i.e., attained liberation]; nay, in the ninety-one aeons (*kappa*) that he remembers, he does not know of any Ajivaka who reached even the temporary heaven (*sagga*), except one – but he was a believer in *karman* [i.e., he was not an orthodox Ajivaka].

In a Mahayana scriptural text, it is said that those who scorn, and do not have faith in a *sutra* like the *Saddharmapundarikasutra* are destined to fall into Avici (the lowest level of purgatory), and to suffer many other torments, diseases, ill-treatment, etc. In fact, even a whole aeon (*kalpa*) is not enough to enumerate such a person's countless ills.

One of the chronicles of Sri Lanka, the *Mahavamsa*, often portrays the island's Tamilians as enemies of the Sinhalese. Even though he had conquered King Elara, King Dutthagamani was disconsolate for he realized that he had slaughtered millions in the battle. But some Arahants consoled him by telling him that

this action of his would not prevent him from attaining a temporary heaven. He had killed only one and a half human beings, i.e., those who had declared themselves to be Buddhists, fully or partially. The rest were unbelievers and immoral, not worth any more than mere animals. He would bring glory to Buddhism and so should not let his heart be troubled.

B. In History

In Sri Lanka, a Theravada king seized a Mahayana monastery and burnt its scriptural texts. In Burma King Anuruddha (Anawratha) of Punnagama (Pagan) attacked the kingdom of Sudhamapura (Thaton) in order to seize a copy of the Scriptures and the relics of the Buddha, which King Manohari (Manuha) had refused to send him when requested to do so.

The Mahayana Tibetan Dge-lugs-pa (Gelugpa) school – the Dalai Lama belongs to this group – often persecuted other Buddhist schools, attacking and destroying their monasteries and books. Tibetan Buddhists fought many wars against each other. In Japan the monk Nichiren (1222-1282), who founded the militant, nationalistic Mahayana school called Nichirenshu, launched a vituperative attack on all other Buddhist schools, denouncing them as heretics and holding them responsible for the many natural calamities and political troubles of Japan: “Nembutsu is hell; the Zen are devils; Shingon is national ruin; and the Risshu are traitors to the country.” From the sixteenth century right up to the beginning of the twentieth century, the Buddhists rabidly persecuted Shamanism in Mongolia: images and other sacred objects were destroyed and shamans were burnt alive or forced to renounce their faith. In the face of such facts, the assertion of Rahula Walpola, viz., that Buddhism had never persecuted or caused bloodshed in converting others and propagating its faith, will have to be modified.

C. In Modern Times

In the ethnic conflicts in Sri Lanka between the Sinhalese and Tamilians, there were nation-wide riots and massacres; temples

were destroyed and images were desecrated. It is reported that, even in the refugee camps for Tamilians, there are many atrocities against them. At present, Buddhist nationalist groups in Sri Lanka, of which the Bodu Bala Sena (Buddhist Power Army) or BBS and Sinhala Ravaya (Sinhalese Roar) are the most prominent, are leading a hate campaign against people of other religions and doing violence to them. In Myanmar monks played a part in the terrible Buddhist-Muslim riots of 1938. In the Great Recital of the Pali Canon in Burma (Myanmar) in 1954, monks who were not Theravadins were considered as lay people and given lower seats among the laity.

In more recent times the military junta in Myanmar displayed a violent attitude to Aung San Suu Kyi and perpetrated various atrocities on people, such as rape, torture and forced labour. At present, there is widespread persecution of Rohingya Muslims by Buddhists in Myanmar. In Cambodia, Pol Pot and the Khmer Rouge committed extensive genocide.

Let us now mention a couple of examples from Mahayana. The Japanese imperialism and its atrocities, especially in the initial years of their colonial rule in Korea, are well known. Koreans were coerced to work in Japanese factories or drafted as soldiers and sent to the front. Thousands of Korean women were recruited as “comfort women”, virtually as sexual slaves for Japanese soldiers. The Japanese attempted to force Korean Buddhism to merge with Japanese forms of Buddhism. They also advocated the practice of married monks. Later, within Korean Buddhism itself, there was a schism on the issue of married versus celibate monks. The conflict between these two rival groups of monks, which also included physical violence, has a long and chequered history in Korea. In spite of the Dalai Lama’s plea for non-violence, Tibetans, including monks, have been reacting violently against the Chinese regime.

Certainly, the peace-loving, gentle and broad-minded Buddha would not have approved of such fundamentalist, intolerant and belligerent actions on the part of his followers. Sincere Buddhists

will deplore the many forms of Buddhist intolerance. However, Buddhism has shown itself more peace-loving than several other religions. The historian Toynbee wrote, “The three Judaic religions have a record of intolerance, hatred, malice, uncharitableness and persecution that is black by comparison with Buddhism’s record.” Still, Buddhism must once again hearken to the call of the Buddha for friendship, to forget narrowmindedness, go beyond bigotry, and embrace the other in selfless altruism.

6. Comparison with Christian Befriending

Buddhist and Christian befriending do resemble each other, e.g., both are opposed to malice and both go to the extent of loving one’s enemy. However, there are many important differences, springing from their different world-views. Christians forgive others because otherwise God will not forgive them. But Theravada Buddhism does not admit any Supreme Being; hence the motivation is not the same. In Theravada, charity begins at home: one loves or practises friendliness first towards oneself; only then can one extend friendliness towards others.

In Christianity, the person befriended has intrinsic worth: the person is a child of God and has an immortal soul. In Theravada, on the other hand, the one who is befriended is neither created by a God nor has a soul: each individual is just a series of momentary aggregates, subject to the law of *kamma* [Sanskrit *karman*] (results of past deeds), and therefore does not have intrinsic worth, but should still be befriended. In Mahayana the human being has even less worth, for the individual does **not** exist even for one moment; only the Adi (First) Buddha, one of the technical terms for the Supreme and Only Being, exists. Yet, paradoxically, the ideal is to unilaterally befriend others who do not really exist even for a moment, except on the level of ignorance and from the practical point of view. In a sense, according to the doctrine of dependent co-production, dependence exists – which, in modern times, is further interpreted even as interdependence or a sort of interrelatedness – but individuals do not exist. Moreover, the interrelatedness in the Mahayana world-view is on the ontologi-

cal level; ultimately there is absolute identity. As a result, while in Christianity one concentrates on overcoming differences between alienated people, in Mahayana one transcends these differences. Hence in Mahayana one can more easily identify oneself even with the oppressor.

While the cultivation and expression of Christian friendship is, in some measure, spontaneous, personal, and generally emotional, Theravada befriending, even if it comes naturally in the case of those who have attained perfection in it, is developed through a systematic, calculated method and expressed in a more impersonal, detached and emotionally more sedate manner.

Christian befriending is based on the inter-personal, communitarian world-view. In Theravada on the other hand, one can only do good or harm to oneself, for each one is reaping the fruits of one's own past deeds (Pali *kamma* or Sanskrit *karman*). One can help another only indirectly by one's example, by trying not to provoke resentment and anger in others and by the tranquil, detached vibrations of friendship (*metta*) sent out in different directions. Disagreeing with an acrobat, his apprentice pointed out that they would perform their act successfully not by watching out for each other but by each one watching out for himself.

In Christianity, it is often said that God will not forgive us unless we forgive others. In Mahayana, too, the Buddhas will not forgive people unless they forgive others. However, it should be noted that even here there are differences. For example, it is not the Buddhas and Bodhisattvas who are the highest, but it is the Adi Buddha that is the Supreme Being. The dealings of the Mahayana Buddhists, however, are with the former.

The Buddhist doctrine of reincarnation motivates one to forgive and be reconciled, but Christianity does not believe in rebirth. On the other hand, for Christianity the person has intrinsic worth, but this is not the case with Buddhism. Hence the motivation for practising forgiveness and reconciliation is also different in the two traditions.

Unlike Christian befriending, Buddhist befriending is more universal, since it is extended also to nature and not just to human beings. However, possibly due to influence from Buddhism and other Eastern religions, and with a growing awareness of the environment in the West, modern Christianity is moving in the direction of befriending nature too and even making restitution by efforts to heal the earth and by recognizing the rights of animals and plants.

One of the practical differences between Christianity and Buddhism is that Buddhism prescribes meditational techniques to help one develop a befriending disposition: merely making a good resolution is not enough. Christianity, on the other hand, only exhorts people to befriend, forgive and be reconciled, but there are no methods or techniques that enable people to become more befriending and forgiving and more reconciled.

Thus, we see that, while there are similarities in befriending between Christianity and Buddhism, there are many distinctions arising from the divergent world-views not only of Christianity but also of Theravada and Mahayana. These differences are found not only with regard to the presuppositions, but also in reference to the motivation as well as the expression of befriending.

While granting that divergent world-views result in differences with regard to the nature, motivation and expression of befriending, Buddhists, Christians and others need to hearken to the call of peace and altruistic love, to heal a broken world and build bridges of friendship and harmony.

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Notes

1. Kosambiyasutta, in Majjhimanikaya, pt I, 48, p. 393ff. Unless otherwise stated, all references to the Buddhist Sanskrit texts cited by me are to the Darbhanga ed., published by the Mithila Institute, Bihar. However, references to the Dhammapada-atthakatha and the Jataka-atthakatha are from the Dhammagiri edition published by the Vipassana Research Institute, Igatpuri, Maharashtra.
2. Kakacupamasutta, in Majjhimanikaya, pt I, 21.5.20, pp. 172-173.
3. See the texts cited in Har Dayal, *The Bodhisattva Doctrine in Buddhist Sanskrit Literature* (London: Kegan Paul, Trench, Trubner and Co., 1932), pp. 209-210.
4. In Theravada, the term Bodhisatta (Pali form of the word) generally refers to Gotama Buddha in a previous life before he became enlightened. In Mahayana Bodhisattvas (Sanskrit form of the term) are special beings who delay their salvation for the sake of helping others, take on the sufferings of others, transfer their merits to them and give them grace: see ACPI [Association of Christian Philosophers of India] *Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, 2010, s.v. "Bodhisattva", by Noel Sheth, S.J., vol. I, pp. 183-187.
5. Khantivadijatakavannana, in Jataka-atthakatha, 4.2.3, No. 313, vol. 72, pp. 34-37. A Sanskrit version is found in the Ksantijataka in the Jatakamala, 28, pp. 189ff. Unless otherwise stated, all references to the Buddhist Sanskrit texts are from the Bauddha-Samskrta-Granthaval edition, published by the Mithila Institute of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Sanskrit Learning, Darbhanga, Bihar.
6. Noel Sheth, "The Buddha's Attitude to Caste", *Negations* 4 (October-December, 1982): 23-26.
7. Assalayanasutta, in Majjhimanikaya, pt II, 43, pp. 403-413; and Vasetthasutta, in Majjhimanikaya, pt II, 48, pp. 462-468.
8. Dhammapada, v. 388, in Khuddakanikaya, pt I, p. 54.

9. Vasalasutta of Suttanipata, 1.7, in Khuddakanikaya, pt I, pp. 287-290.
10. Ambatthasutta, in Dighanikaya, pt I, 3.6, pp. 84-86.
11. On Ksatriya claims to superiority, see G. S. Ghurye, *Caste and Class in India* (Bombay: The Popular Book Depot, 1950), pp. 71-72.
12. Dighanikaya, pt I, 3.6, p. 86.
13. These are monastic lineages or fraternities.
14. Anthony Fernando, "Contemporary Buddhism in Sri Lanka (Ceylon)" in Dumoulin and Maraldo, eds., *Buddhism in the Modern World* (New York: MacMillan and Co., 1976), p. 66.
15. Adele M. Fiske, "Caste among the Buddhists", in Harjinder Singh, ed., *Caste among Non-Hindus in India* (New Delhi: National Publishing House, 1977), pp. 102-103.
16. See his "Caste in India", and "Annihilation of Caste", in Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar, *Writings and Speeches*, vol. 1 (Bombay: The Education Dept., Government of Maharashtra, 1979), pp. 5-96.
17. Gotamisutta, in Anguttaranikaya, pt III, 8.6.1, pp. 370-371.
18. Singalasutta, in Dighanikaya, pt III, 8.5.28 and 30, pp. 146-147.
19. Visuddhimagga, 9.15-38; see Nyanamoli, *The Path of Purification (Visuddhimagga)*, 2nd ed. (Colombo: A. Semage, 1964), pp. 324-332.
20. It is interesting to note the contrary case in the Hindu Bhagavadgita (2.19), where Krishna urges Arjuna to fight against the Kauravas since the soul – which constitutes the essence of a person and is inactive – is neither a slayer nor is slain.
21. See the texts cited in Dayal, *Bodhisattva Doctrine*, pp. 210-212.
22. Kunalajatakavannana, in *Jataka-atthakatha*, 5.21.4, No. 536, vol. 74, pp. 408-410.
23. Tissatheravathu, in *Dhammapada-atthakatha*, 1.3, pt I, vol.50, pp. 25-29; see Burlingame, *Buddhist Legends*, pt I, pp. 166-170.
24. Unto Tahtinen, *Ahimsa: Nonviolence in Indian Tradition* (London: Rider and Co., 1976), pp. 102-103.
25. *Encyclopedia of Buddhism*, ed. G. P. Malalasekera and others, s.v. "Ahimsa", by Hiraakawa, vol. 1, p. 291.
26. *Jatakamala*, 31, vv. 63 and 65, pp. 227-228; 3, p. 16, lines 16-17.

27. Siksasamuccaya, 1.4, p. 16, lines 2-5.
28. Bodhicaryavatara, with the Panjika Commentary, 10, pp. 283-287
29. Jatakamala, 25, v. 29, p. 173.
30. Mahayanasutralankara, 19, v. 28, p. 158; Siksasamuccaya, 7.14, p. 81, lines 16-17. Note that, in addition to this high selfless ideal, some texts do mention other less lofty motives, such as fame, merit, rebirth in a better state, etc.
31. Jataka-atthakatha, 4.2.6, No. 316, vol. 72, pp. 44-47; Jatakamala, 6, pp. 30-35.
32. Jataka-atthakatha, 15.3, No. 499, vol. 73, pp. 359-370; Avadanasataka, 34, pp. 83-85; Jatakamala 2, pp. 7-15.
33. Jataka-atthakatha, 22.10, No. 547, vol. 76, pp. 227-381; Jatakamala, 9, pp. 55-69; Bodhisattvavadanakalpalata, 23, pp. 172-175.
34. Avadanasataka, 55, p. 140.
35. An epithet of any Buddha, but commonly used as an epithet of Gautama Buddha. The word is generally interpreted as “one who has thus (tatha) either gone (gata) or come (agata)”.
36. L’Enseignement de Vimalakirti (Vimalakirtinirdesa), tr. and annotated by Etienne Lamotte, Bibliotheque du Museon, vol. 51 (Louvain: Publications Universitaires, 1962), pp. 216-217.
37. Santideva, Bodhicaryavatara, ed. by Vidhushekhara Bhattacharya, Bibliotheca Indica: A Collection of Oriental Works, Work 280, Issue 1580 (Calcutta: The Asiatic Society, 1960), III, vv. 6-11, 17-18, pp. 31-34.
38. In Theravada (Pali Pacceka-buddha), they attain liberation by their own effort but do not teach others; in Mahayana (Sanskrit Pratyeka-buddha) they do not teach others in the normal way, but do so through thought-transference. However, both in Theravada as well as in Mahayana, they are inferior to Buddhas and, in Mahayana, where the ideal is to become a Bodhisattva, they are also inferior to Bodhisattvas who, unlike Pratyeka-Buddhas, delay their own salvation for the sake of helping others to attain salvation.
39. Siksasamuccaya, 4.7, p. 56.
40. Dighanikaya, pt III, 2.8.27, p. 44.
41. Dhammikasutta, in Anguttaranikaya, pt III, 6.5.16, p.84.
42. Mahaparinibbanasutta, in Dighanikaya pt II, 3.19.62, p. 98.

43. Edward J. Thomas, *The Life of the Buddha as Legend and History* (London: Kegan Paul, Trench, Trubner and Co., 1927), p. 149, n. 3.
44. Amagandhasutta, in *Suttanipata*, 2.2.22-28, pp. 305-306.
45. This does not mean that they were not sensitive to animal life.
46. Jivakasutta, in *Majjhimanikaya*, pt II, 5.1.2, p. 39.
47. Kandarakasutta, in *Majjhimanikaya*, pt II. 1.4.8, p. 8.
48. Brahmanadhammikasutta, in *Suttanipata*, 2.7.88-93, pp. 313-314.
49. Mamsabhaksanaparivartah, in *Saddharmalankavatarasutra*, 8, p. 103, lines 10-11, 24-26; see also vv. 12 and 19, p. 105. The reference to earlier canonical texts that did make exceptions to pure vegetarianism indicates that Buddhism did permit meat-eating in former times.
50. The somewhat defensive attitude of the text in the face of actual criticism against Buddhists consuming meat seems to indicate that the text's pure vegetarianism is proposed as a reaction to this criticism: see Daisetz Teitaro Suzuki, tr., *The Lankavatara Sutra* (London: Routledge and Kegan Paul, 1932; reprinted 1956), p. 211, n. 1.
51. Culahatthipadopamasutta, in *Majjhimanikaya*, pt I, 27.2.8, p. 230.
52. Really speaking, there is no expiation required, but only confession: see I. B. Horner, trans. *The Book of the Discipline*, vol. 2, *Sacred Books of the Buddhists vol.20* (London: Pali Text Society, 1957), p. 3, n. 4.
53. *Pacittiya*, no.11, pp. 54-56.
54. See Horner, tr., *The Book of the Discipline*, p. 229, n. 4.
55. *Pacittiya*, no. 10, pp. 52-54.
56. Radhagovinda Basak, ed., *Asokan Inscriptions* (Calcutta: Progressive Publishers, 1959), pp. 71-72.
57. Romila Thapar, cited by Rajmohan Gandhi, *Revenge and Reconciliation: Understanding South Asian History* (New Delhi: Penguin Books, 1999), p. 52.
58. Masaharu Anesaki, *History of Japanese Religion: With Special Reference to the Social and Moral Life of the Nation* (London: Kegan Paul, Trench, 1930; reprint ed., Rutland, Vermont and Tokyo, Japan: Charles E. Tuttle, 1963), pp. 171-172.
59. Basak, *Asokan Inscriptions*, p. 103.

60. Basak, Asokan Inscriptions, p. 4.
61. Encyclopedia of Buddhism, ed. G. P. Malalasekera and others, s.v. "Abhaya-dana," by Shuyu Kanaoka, vol. 1, pp. 20-21.
62. Encyclopedia of Buddhism, ed. Malalasekera, and others, s.v. "Ahimsa", by Akira Hirakawa, vol. 1, pp. 291-292.
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64. Ariyaratne, Collected Works, vol. 2, pp. 115-116.
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69. H. Uttarananda, "Sihala Buddhist Monks and the Rights of the Tamils", Dialogue n.s. 18:1-3 (January-December 1991): 6-9, 12-13.
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72. Donald K. Swearer, "Sulak Sivaraksa's Buddhist Vision for Renewing Society", in Engaged Buddhism: Buddhist Liberation Movements in Asia, ed. by Christopher S. Queen and Sallie B. King (Albany: State University of New York Press, 1996), pp. 200-208.
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74. "Letter from Cambodia" [a newsletter], March 2002, p. 1.
75. "Editors' Introduction", in Maha Ghosananda, Step by Step: Meditations on Wisdom and Compassion, ed. by Jane Sharada Mahoney

and Philip Edmonds, with a Foreword by Dith Pran and a Preface by Jack Kornfield (Berkeley, California: Parallax Press, 1992), pp. 17-18.

76. The name of the communist group in Cambodia that carried out a massive genocide under the leadership of Pol Pot.
77. Maha Ghosananda, *Step by Step*, pp. 62, 68-69.
78. Aung San Suu Kyi, *Freedom from Fear and Other Writings*, ed. with an Introduction by Michael Aris, with a Foreword to the first ed. by Vaclav Havel and a Foreword to the second ed. by Desmond Tutu, 2nd rev. ed. (London: Penguin Books, 1995), pp. 195-196.
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88. 108 is a sacred number in some Indian religions, including Buddhism.
89. "Bhutan Celebrates Newborn Prince by Planting 108,000 Trees", report filed on 11th March 2016 by Vishal Arora in *The Diplomat* [Asia-Pacific online newspaper]: <http://thediplomat.com/2016/03/bhutan-celebrates-newborn-prince-by-planting-108000-trees/>, accessed on 22nd March 2016.

90. Suttanipata, 1.8, v. 149, in Khuddakanikaya, pt I, pp. 290-291. This simile occurs in Mahayana texts too: e.g., the love (prema) of all beings as if they were one's only child (Saddharmalankavatarasutra, 8, p. 100, line 6).
91. Siksasmuccaya, 12.20, p. 117, lines 9-13.
92. Saddharmapundarikasutra, 5.44, p. 92, line 24.
93. Mahayanasutralankara, 19, v. 5, p. 154.
94. Jatakamala, 8, p. 43, line 1.
95. Siksasamuccaya, 7.14, p. 81, lines 4-5.
96. Mahayanasutralankara, 16, p.103, line 8.
97. Mahayanasutralankara, 3, v. 12; Bodhicaryavatara, with the Panjika Commentary of Prajnakaramati, 8. v. 173, p. 165.
98. A follower of another religion that existed in the Buddha's and Mahavira's time.
99. Tevijjavacchasutta, in Majjhimanikaya, pt II, 21.2, pp. 174-175.
100. Saddharmapundarikasutra, 3.113-135, pp. 66-68.
101. Those who have attained liberation while living.
102. Mahavamsa, 25; see Wilhelm Geiger, tr., The Mahavamsa: The Great Chronicle of Ceylon (London: Pali Text Society, 1912): pp. 177-178, lines 103-111.
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110. Khantipalo, Tolerance, p. 107.
111. He stayed in a Buddhist monastery for six years, two of which were spent as a monk. Later, however, he joined the Cambodian Communist Party.
112. Robert E. Buswell, The Zen Monastic Experience: Buddhist Practice in Contemporary Korea (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1992), pp. 24-32.
113. He is referring to the three Semitic or Abrahamic religions, Judaism, Christianity and Islam.
114. Arnold Toynbee, Change and Habit: The Challenge of Our Time (London: Oxford University Press, 1966), p. 167.
115. See the Gospel according to Matthew, 6.12; 18.21-35.
116. Sedakasutta, in Samyuttanikaya, 47.19, pt 5, pp. 144-145.

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Mysticism: A Way for Christian-Muslim Dialogue

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Abstract: Sufism and Mystical experience of the Christian East can be a common ground for dialogue. The Semitic religions have many common elements to look into for the dialogue. The Mystical experience of the Sufism (Islam) and mysticism in Christian East one of the elements, where we can come together in dialogue. Both these religions have a spiritual experience in mysticism, where they understand the 'oneness' of God and expression of this 'oneness' is seen in the life of the believer as following the commandments. This experience is not merely an academic, instead it is an intimate and transforming encounter with God, where both experience compassionate and merciful creator. This enables theme to do the service because, they have come across the God as loving creator to whole humanity. .

Keywords: Dialogue, Mysticism, Oneness with God, Sufism, Muslim-Christian Dialogue

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Introduction

Sufism and Mystical experience of the Christian East can be a common ground for Christian, Muslim Dialogue, because there are common elements in both traditions. The mystical experiences of each tradition enable Christians and Muslims to understand each other as children of God. The mystical experience of the early Christian communities and the Sufi mystical experience of brotherhood is one of the paths, which can promote a deep and lasting collaboration between Christians and Muslims. This is because the mystical experiences of the persons of both traditions have several common traits. According to McIntosh we often use the term ‘mysticism’, though this is really something of an academic invention; earlier eras referred to the most intimate and transforming encounter with God as ‘contemplation’ (McIntosh, 1998: 11). If we analyse the goal of every mystic, we realize that it is God. In this essay, I would like to explore some of the possibilities of Christian, Muslim dialogue on the basis of the mystical experience of both religions, which enables ‘interfaith dialogue in the present world’.

1. Early Islam in the Eastern Christian World

“The Middle East and North Africa are the cradle(s) of not only Christianity but also of two other great religions, Judaism and Islam. Despite a mutual origin, pressure is building up on the Christians in this region” (Riemenschneider, 2011: 6). Since its inception Islam has had a great contact with Christianity. ‘Muslim-Christian communication is as old as Islam (Saab, 1964: 43). During the time of the Islamic birth in the Arabian Peninsula and spreading in the eastern provinces of Byzantium, there were lot of conflicts between the Byzantines and the local Christian communities, which had created so many conflicts and wars (Thomas et al., 2006: 1), which, in fact an easy access to the new religion to spread. Indeed, all “The Arab conquests of the Byzantine eastern provinces and the consequent establishment of Muslim dominance foreshadowed the end of the long tradition of Hellenism in western Asia” (Grypeou et al., 2006: 1). But,

one can see both negative and positive the relationship between Christianity and Islam. Though the religions had also cordial in many places since its inception. John of Damascus is an example of the cordial relationship with the Caliph as his secretary followed by his father and grandfather (Thomas, 2005: 11), but he considers Islam as the sum of all heresies.

William Dalrymple, a Scottish historian, made two important observations on Christian Muslim relationship while traveling throughout the Middle East several years ago. First, he observed that while visiting ancient cells of monks near the Monastery of Mar Saba in the Israeli-Occupied West Bank, every cell had a prayer niche almost identical to the mihrab, which is a basic feature of all mosques today (Sharp, 2012: 11). He concluded that, “. . . the prayer niche must be another of those features of the early Christian world which has been lost to modern Western Christianity, yet which is still preserved in Islam” (Sharp, 2012: 11). “Dalrymple’s second observation attests to a truth that Orthodox Christians and Muslims have known instinctively for centuries— that they originally came from one civilization and share the same ancestry” (Sharp, 2012: 12). Though they had a deep relationship with each other. The Islamic tradition as it is developing gradually puts more and more emphasis on the “Arab” nature of Muhammad and Islam. It is true that in the beginning, there is an appeal to commonality—not of ancestry so much as of salvation-history. However, as time goes on, it becomes important for Muslim tradition to distance itself from any dependency on the pre-existing Christian and Jewish “civilizations,” and to trace its ancestry to Abraham back through the line of Ishmael and Hagar.

1.1 Early Islamic Growth in the Middle East

The presence of Christians in the Arab Peninsula had influenced Islam in its creation of Islamic theology. “The confrontation of Christianity with the early theological and political development of Islam addresses broader questions of intercultural relations and reciprocities and their impact on the

formation of religious systems and identities” (Thomas et al., 2006: 4). Early Islam had direct contact with Syriac Christians (Thomas et al., 2006: 4), which separated at the Council of Ephesus in 431 AD (Angold, 2006: 511), as part of the Nestorian heresies and emphases that radical distinctions between the two natures of Jesus Christ, Jacobite Christians (Angold, 2006: 511), which separated at the council of Chalcedon in 451 AD (Angold, 2006: 511), and there were also Arab Christians who had a direct communion with Byzantium church. “Arabic and Syriac Christianity contributed to the emergence and rapid spread of Islam, and especially the specific Christian elements in the cult and faith that were formative upon Islam and became part of its tradition” (Thomas et al., 2006: 4). So, the relationship between the churches in Roman empire as well as Persian empire had influenced theological development of Islamic formation.

The early Muslims also had contacts with Maronite Christians and Alexandrian Christians. Ibn Jubayr, an Arab geographer and poet says, “It is strange how the Christians round Mount Lebanon, when they see any Muslim hermits, bring them food and treat them kindly, saying that these men are dedicated to Great and Glorious God and that they should therefore share with them” (Saab, 1964: 44) Syria is another place where Islam encountered Christianity. The Christianity in Syria was the product Nestorian heresy (Some Christians in Syria would have held a Nestorian position, but Syrian Christianity was not produced by Nestorianism), who separated at the Council of Ephesus from the main church. They were called the Assyrian Church of East. ‘Coming to the development of religious systems within the ‘Syriac Society,’ Toynbee says that the Babylonian challenge produced two religious’ movements: Judaism with its later development, Christianity, and Zoroastrianism (Siddiqi, 1964:118). Ethiopia is another country Islam had connection from the beginning. “Ethiopia became a Christian state in about 300 A.D. Muslims and Christians have been living side by side in the region since the time when the Prophet Mohammad sent some of his followers there for sanctuary in 615 (Shetler &

Yehualashet, 2013: 319). The relationship between these two religions was both cordial as well as conflict type.

1.2 Early Islam with Christianity and Idol Worshipers

In the fourth century, many Arab tribes joined Christianity following the teaching of the Church of the East (Thomas, 2007: 2). The prophetic revelation was given in two places called Mecca and Medina for 23 years. In Mecca, Muhammad had to encounter with Arab paganism where he was emphasizing on morality, but in Medina the situation was different there, he comes across, Judaism and Christianity. “Communication between Christianity and Islam began with the revelation of the Qur’an. As it was revealed to Muhammad in the seventh century in a peninsula, which was partly Christian, communication between Christianity and Islam became an integral part of the Quran” (Saab, 1964: 43). Prophet Muhammad had a very close relationship with Christianity, which was friendliness most of the times, because Muhammad was comfortable with the idea of monotheism which opposite to idol worshippers of the tribes in the Arabian Peninsula. “The Quran describes the Christians as the closest community to Islam” (Saab, 1964: 43) in many times. There were also times Quran critics the Christian theology such as Trinity, which goes against monotheism, Muhammad believes.

1.3 Trinity: Unity of God

“Twice the Quran criticises those who confess the Trinity. Sura 5: 72–73 calls on Christians to give up adding gods to the One True God” (Beaumont, 2012: 111). ‘They have certainly disbelieved who say, “Allah is the Messiah, the son of Mary” while the Messiah has said, “O Children of Israel, worship Allah, my Lord and your Lord. Indeed, he who associates others with Allah - Allah has forbidden him Paradise, and his refuge is the Fire. And there are not for the wrongdoers any helpers.” (Q 5:72) The second passage in which the Trinity is challenged is sūra 4:171. People of the Book, do not exaggerate in your religion. Only speak the truth about God. Christ Jesus, son of Mary, was

the messenger of God, and His word which He cast on Mary, and a spirit from Him. Believe in God and His messengers and do not say “Trinity”; give it up for your own good. Surely God is One God (Beaumont, 2012: 111). These early attitudes of Islam made it very difficult for Christians to encounter Muslims because the revelation which they have received in the Incarnation (Word became Flesh) mystery is the truth to them.

Christians believed that Jesus is the Incarnated Logos (Jn 1;14) “For Christians direct or supernatural revelation came only to the Jewish people and found its fulfilment in Christ in his person and his gospel” (Knowles, 2011: 319). They also believed that the fullness of revelation in Jesus Christ; ‘in the past God spoke to our ancestors through the prophets at many times and in various ways, but in these last days he has spoken to us by his Son, whom he appointed heir of all things, and through whom also he made the universe. (Heb 1:1-2) They would need to defend their belief in God as one essence (*ousia*) in three persons (*hypostases*) which was shared by all denominations of the church in the Middle Eastern territories under Muslim rule. They may have been divided over their understanding of the union of the divine and human in Christ, but they were united in their faith in the Triune God. In a dialogue with the Caliph al-Mahdi- and Timothy I, Patriarch of the East Syrian (Nestorian) Church said, “That Christians believe in ‘three *hypostases* (*aqānīm*) . . . The Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit, which are together one God, one nature, and one essence (*jawhar*)” (Beaumont, 2005: 115). It is the fundamental mystery of Christianity. Timothy explained to the caliph, “Just as the Caliph is one person in his mind and spirit, and these cannot be separated from him, so it is with God and his Word and Spirit” (Beaumont, 2005: 115). He believed that Jesus taught this great mystery clearly in the gospel and we can experience this mystery by studying created things.

“Gregory the Theologian claimed that Abraham received a vision of God, not in his role as deity, but as a man. Augustine of Hippo affirmed Abraham’s understanding of the Unity of the Trinity: while greeting the three strangers, Abraham confessed to

one God in three hypostases” (Strezova, 2014: 176-177). John of Damascus defended Trinity in Damascus, perhaps already at the monastery of Mar Saba near Jerusalem. John reports that Muslims accuse Christians of associating Christ with God in an unacceptable way because Christians say that “Christ is the Son of God and God. John suggests that Christians should quote the Muslim belief that ‘Christ is the Word and Spirit of God’ and say ‘if the Word is in God it is obvious that he is God as well” (Beaumont, 2005: 113).

Abū Qurra (d.c.830), Abū Rā’ita (d.c.835) and Ammār al-Bas. rī (d.c.860) who all attempted to defend and explain the Trinity in Arabic for a Muslim audience that was increasingly involved in debate with Christian intellectuals (Beaumont, 2005: 116). Abū Qurra says, “Christians do not believe in three gods when they say that the Father is God, the Son is God, and the Holy Spirit is God; and that the Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit are one God even though each of them is complete in himself” (Beaumont, 2005: 117). He is very sure that those who negate the Christian teaching object to the Trinity because their reason is confused by the Christian claims that the Father, the Son and the Holy Spirit are three hypostases (*aqānīm*) in one God (*ilah wāhid*), and that each of the hypostases is perfect God in himself (Beaumont, 2005: 117). “But Abū Qurra recognizes that the analogy with three men must not lead to the supposition that the Father, Son and Holy Spirit are separated or differentiated, since they would then be three divine beings rather than one divine being (Beaumont, 2005: 117).” He has supplied *wajh/ wujūh* as a translation of the Greek term *prosōpon* (person) which was a synonym for hypostasis in Greek (Beaumont, 2005: 117). So, he refers to the divine nature in various ways. The three persons (*wujūh*) share the same nonphysical nature (*latafa*). Therefore, each of the persons shares the same essence (*dhāt*). The three persons share the same oneness of divinity (*wāh.idiyya al-lāhūt*) (Beaumont, 2005: 117).

“The first pillar of Islam is essentially a foundational pillar, which forms the backdrop of all the other pillars of Islam. This

pillar consists of two testimonies the utterance of which enters one into the fold of Islam. The first part of the testimony is *Ash-hadu alaa ilaaha ilallah* (to testify there is nothing worthy of worship except” (Mirza & Bakali, 2010: 53). The worship is only to Allah. There are no gods except God. “The central creed of Islam consists of the two testimonies of faith or *Shahddahs*, which state that: There is no god but God, Muhammad is the Messenger of God” (“Common Word between Us and You,” 2008: 243). This testimony is an utterance of pure monotheism negating the belief in all other deities, other than God (Mirza & Bakali, 2010: 53), which was popular among the Arabian tribes. The prophet had come across two types of people in the Arabian Peninsula. In Mecca he had encountered with Arabian Paganism. They were idol worshippers. In Medina, he had to encounter with Judaism and Christianity, which also influenced him to affirm for the monotheism. He was totally against idol worshippers. “God is absolute and therefore devotion to him must be totally sincere” (“Common Word between Us and You,” 2008: 245). The testimony of faith emphasizes: “There is no god but God. it reminds Muslims that their hearts, their individual souls and all the faculties and powers of their souls (or simply their entire hearts and souls) must be totally devoted and attached to God” (“Common Word between Us and You,” 2008: 248). It is the total submission to God. The word *Islam* means submission. The Trinitarian God of Christianity is the sources of unity in the church. This unity of God enables the Christian to engage in dialogue with Islam who profess the same God (Lumen Gentium 16, Nostra Aetate 3). Being a committed Muslim one must able to submit oneself fully God because it is “God who has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and who has called them to live together as brothers and sisters, to fill the earth and make known the values of goodness, love and peace” (Francis & Al-Tayyib, 2019) The ultimate aim is to encounter the creator, who created the whole human beings

1.4 The Quran and Early Christianity

“The Quran is the most important book in the Islamic lands, comparable to the Bible in the Western tradition. Transmitted orally, the text was soon committed to writing, and manuscripts - usually in the codex format - became the most common written work in circulation” (Blair, 2008: xx) Muslims believe that God reveals the word through the Angel Gabriel to Prophet Muhamad, who was illiterate. “That Muhammad was no theologian emerges on every page of the Koran. He was a preacher and a leader, political and military as well as religious”(Knowles, 2011: 318) It is the Arabic version that is considered by Muslims to be the true Quran, the direct word of Allah. No translation is considered to be the Quran or Word of Allah as such, and none has the same status as the original Quran. “The Quran, on the other hand, often appears to consider the Christians as a schismatic Jewish sect. They are included most of the time in what it says People of the Scriptures (*Ahl al-Kitâb*), judged mainly in the light of the Jews. Sometimes, however, Christians are presented in opposition to the Jews”(Ellul, 2007: 361).

In Christianity, the belief is that The Word became flesh and made his dwelling among us (Jn 1:14) in Jesus Christ, through the virgin Mary (Lk 1:27). It is the word, who was with God and he was God himself. (Jn 1:1-14) It is the pure word of God which enables creation. After Islamic rule had been established in the Middle East, the Christians found that the Muslims claim that the Quran is the only pure, all other scriptures are corrupt. (Beaumont, 2005: 195). “The earliest recorded Christian reading of the Qur’an comes from the writing of John of Damascus (d.c.750) who spent his career as a secretary to the Caliph in Damascus” (Beaumont, 2005: 195). John had three issues with Quranic understanding in Christian perspectives. They are: ‘The Quran contains material unworthy of divine revelation (Beaumont, 2005: 195), ‘the Quran shows Muhammad to be less than Muslims claim he is, (Beaumont, 2005: 197), ‘the Quran sometimes supports Christian beliefs (Beaumont, 2005: 198).

1.5 Jesus in Quran

Jesus is considered as a word of Allah in Quran, 'The Messiah, Jesus, the son of Mary, was but a messenger of Allah and His word which He directed to Mary and a soul from Him.' (Quran 4;171) and Quran also approves the virgin birth of Jesus. She said, "How can I have a boy while no man has touched me and I have not been unchaste?" He said, "Thus [it will be]; your Lord says, 'It is easy for Me, and We will make him a sign to the people and a mercy from Us. And it is a matter [already] decreed.'" (Quran 19;20-21). Jesus was also considered as a servant, 'Jesus was not but a servant upon whom We bestowed favour, and We made him an example for the Children of Israel.' (43;59). But the Quran disagrees that Jesus is not created. 'She said, "My Lord, how will I have a child when no man has touched me?" [The angel] said, "Such is Allah; He creates what He wills. When He decrees a matter, He only says to it, 'Be,' and it is.'" (Quran 3;47) the claim of John of Damascus is that "the Arian monk had given Muhammad mixed information about Christianity and this is echoed in the message of Muhammad. Support for Christian teaching can be found in the statement" (Beaumont, 2005: 198). Though John had a very prominent post in as secretary to caliph "John goes on to mock the teachings in the Quran about Christ, particularly that he was not crucified but only 'his shadow', and that he denied before God that he was his son, and continues to criticise Muhammad's unrestrained sexual appetite and what he regards as perverse teachings in various parts of the Quran" (Thomas, 2005: 11). "John thought Islam a false religion, based originally upon an encounter between Muhammad and a heretical Christian monk, from whom he gained some knowledge of the Bible. Thus, Islam can be dismissed as a Christian heresy since it has no integrity in itself, and whatever truthfulness or good it contained derived from the proper source of true teaching in the Bible" (Thomas, 2005: 11). Early Islam had a very deep relationship with Christianity which we have seen in the relationship on religious matters and political matters.

2. Eastern Mysticism and Sufism

“An ascetic and mystical element that was implicitly present in Islam since its very inception became explicit during the first Islamic centuries (the seventh and eighth centuries C.E.)” (Knysh, 2010: 1). Unlike Christian mysticism, the Islamic mysticism has not begun because of any persecution. One can say it has received an inspiration from Christian mysticism, which was popular in the Eastern and Western churches in the seventh and eighth centuries C.E. “This period witnessed the appearance of the first Muslim devotees and “moral athletes,” who formed primitive ascetic communities in the central and eastern lands of Islam, primarily in Mesopotamia, Syria and Eastern Iran”(Knysh, 2010: 1). Many people started following the early mystics as part of being away from the secular sphere and luxuries of the world. “As an outward sign of this pietistic withdrawal, some of them adopted a distinct dress code, which often featured a rough woollen robe.” (Knysh, 2010: 7). These mystics were known as Sufi saints in Islam. The word Sufism is a Latinised word which comes from the Arabic word *suf* which means wool (Knysh, 2010: 5). “By the end of the eighth century C.E., in the central lands of Islam the nick-name *suffiyya* (“wool-people” or “wool-wearers”) became a self-designation of those given to ascetic life and mystical contemplation” (Knysh, 2010: 7). Sufism became a prevalent characteristic of the Muslim social order in the later Middle Ages (12 – 6th Centuries CE).

2.1 Communion as the Community

The mystics in the early Islamic traditions were called “moral athletes” (Knysh, 2010: 7) and they formed as “*tariqas*” or “brotherhood” (Knysh, 2010: 5). Muslim mystics often trace this term to the root *Safà* with the general meaning of “purity;” to the phrase *ahl al-suffa* (“the People of the Bench”), that is, the pious and indigent companions of the Prophet who lived in his mosque” (Knysh, 2010: 7); in other words, we may tend to interpret that these mystics lived in a mosque under a head. The Constitution of the Society of Jesus describes the brotherhood

as ‘union of hearts.’ The ‘union of hearts’ is an expression of sincere communication between persons, which we see in the Acts of the Apostles in the Council of Jerusalem. Peter, as the head of the Apostles, and Paul as the head of the Church of Antioch, discussed and came to a decision on the controversy regarding the law of circumcision. “Certain people came down from Judea to Antioch and were teaching the believers: “Unless you are circumcised, according to the custom taught by Moses, you cannot be saved.” This brought Paul and Barnabas into sharp dispute and debate with them. So, Paul and Barnabas were appointed, along with some other believers, to go up to Jerusalem to see the apostles and elders about this question.” (Acts 15:1-2) “The early Christians considered that the Christian spirituality could not be experienced outside the community, which involved a multiplicity and variety of spiritual charisms” (Zizioulas, 1989: 27) because the Spirit was regarded as “communion” (Zizioulas, 1989: 27). They were living together and expecting the second coming of Christ as one body of Christ. The community life was an essential element among the early Christians. This type of community life was not just a living together under the same roof but it was a life of ‘union of hearts. It was a life of communion among the members. This communion helped them to forget the self and thus enabled them to love one another.

2.2 Self-Renunciation

It was discovered that there were many people who lived in search of a pure life as ascetics in the Arab-Byzantine region (Knysh, 2010: 6). “The acts of penitence and self-renunciation, which their practitioners justified by references to certain Quranic verses and the Prophet’s utterances, may be seen as a reaction against Islam’s newly acquired wealth that often led many faithful to abandon the frugal and heroic ways of self-denial associated with the original Muslim community in Medina” (Knysh, 2010: 2). It was evident from the correspondences of the early Christian hermits in the church. When the church had acquired freedom in the Roman Empire, many of the clerics enjoyed political status

too. They had forgotten the real value of Christ's teaching on self-renunciation, from which "arose a movement that in a variety of ways expressed a rejection of the conventional worldly values (Jean, 1989: 89).

Sufis also realized that many of these Umayyad and their officials were not following the spirit of the Holy Quran, which said, "Whatever you are given in this life is nothing but a temporary provision of this life and its glitter; what God has is better and more lasting. Will you not then understand?" (Quran 28:60). "They argued that the truly God-fearing person should try to save himself by withdrawing from the overbearing world and its sinful and unjust ways. "In an attempt to achieve this goal, the mystic had to contend not only with the corruptive trappings of the world, but also with his own base self (*nafs*), which Sufis see as the seat of egoistic evil lusts and passions impeding their progress towards God." (Knysh, 2010: 10). These ways of life are so much similar to the life adopted by the Christian ways of life in the deserts. Many of these people had very good contacts with the Christians of the Eastern countries like Syria and Constantinople. "This robe set them apart from people wearing more expensive silk or cotton. Wittingly or not, the early Muslim *religiosi* thereby came to resemble Christian monks and ascetics, who also donned coarse woollen clothes as a symbol of penitence and contempt for worldly luxuries" (Knysh, 2010: 7).

"Sufi movement developed a strict code of behaviour which encouraged repentance, abstinence from worldly delights, frugal living and voluntary poverty" (Knysh, 2010: 9), as we see among the early Christian hermits. "During the first century of Abbasid rule, renunciation was a widespread form of piety in Muslim communities. Renunciants (*zahid*) and pietists (*abid, andnasik*) of this period were not organised into a single homogeneous movement but came in different colours and stripes" (Karamustafa, 2007: 1). Self-renunciation is an important act of getting into the mystical life. The incarnation mystery of the Christian spirituality is a basis for the renunciation because being God, Jesus emptied himself and not considered himself equal to

God (Phil 2:7). instead, he renounced everything and entered into the world of human race. The person who has renounced himself has to enter into this stage where he tries to understand this mystery. Every mystic has to go through this experience in his life.

2.3 Purification

A person who desires to renounce everything in the world has to be purified. In each religion, there is a process called purification in different ways. “Mystics in every religious tradition have tended to describe the different steps on the way that leads toward God by the image of the Path. The Christian tripartite division of the *via purgativa*, the *via contemplativa*, and the *via illuminativa* is, to some extent, the same as the Islamic definition of *shari’a*, *tariqa*, and *haqiqa*” (Schimmel, 2011: 98). Naturally these paths are narrow and difficult to go through. In other words, these difficulties experienced by the person can be called the process of purification. The early mystics in the church left the cities in order to purify themselves. They were also doing the works of charity in the form of discourses and giving advices to the common people. The personal purification is very important in the mystical life. “Most of early Muslim ascetics emphasized personal purity, moral uprightness, fear of God and strict compliance with the letter of the Divine Law, there were those who carried their search of God’s pleasure a bit further” (Knysh, 2010: 8). In Sufism, “the ascetics, on the other hand, were allowed to practice self-imposed strictures which they deemed as preparation for the imminent Final Reckoning” (Knysh, 2010: 9). This purification process will make one to experience the ultimate or the absolute.

2.4 Union with the Absolute

The union of hearts among the mystics enables them to be one with the Heart of the Absolute. Mysticism is an experience of a Devotee “Seeing One’s Own Face in the Face of God” (Nelstrop & Podmore, 2016: 1). It will enable the person to “ascend beyond

cataphatic knowledge of God towards divine union, the divine idea became its entitlement and reality” (Nelstrop & Podmore, 2016: 1): This is one of the concepts called ‘Deification’ in Eastern Christianity and ‘Becoming Another Christ’ in Western Christianity. This personal experience can make these devotees from the two traditions of Sufis and Christian faith can engage in interfaith commitment in life.” Whatever be the Sufi approach to renunciation and to the question of how far to detach themselves from mainstream social life, some prominent renunciants and the renunciant communities that formed around them began to direct their energies increasingly to the cultivation of the inner life. This inward turn manifested itself especially in new discourses on spiritual states, stages of spiritual development, closeness to God, and love; it also led to a clear emphasis on ‘knowledge of the interior’ (*ilmal-batin*) acquired through ardent examination and training of the human soul” (Karamustafa, 2007: 2). The human soul forgets himself or herself and become one with the absolute. In the early church we come across the mystics forgetting themselves out of love towards the other. St. Ignatius of Antioch’s martyrdom story reminds us that even in suffering the name of Jesus was inscribed in his heart. “There is nothing left to distract the lover from God—the spiritual eye sees nothing but Him when the eye of the body is closed. He is enough for the loving soul: “O my Lord, whatever share of this world Thou dost bestow on me, bestow it on Thine enemies, and whatever share of the next world Thou doest give me, give it to Thy friends — Thou art enough for me” (Schimmel, 2011: 40). As the mystic feels that he is close to the heart of the absolute because he gets the awareness that his/her image and likeness (Gen 1:26) are the same as the creator. “The true knowledge of God was to be obtained by obedience to the uttermost” (Knysh, 2010: 36). The lost image and likeness has to regain through obedience.

2.5 Service and Love

“*Al-mu'min mir'at al-mu'min*, the faithful is the mirror of the faithful” — that is a Prophetic tradition that the Sufis considered

an excellent maxim for social intercourse” (Schimmel, 2011: 228). Sufi saint is the one who experiences the union of heart with the absolute and live in the world. He has the moral responsibility of looking after the other as the greatest commandment Christ gave to the rich man, “Love the Lord your God with all your heart and with all your soul and with all your mind.” This is the first and greatest commandment. And the second is like it: ‘Love your neighbour as yourself. All the Law and the Prophets hang on these two commandments.’ (Mt 22:36-40). The practical application of this maxim can be clearly seen in the Sufi history and leads to the one of the movement’s most nice aspects, namely, to the fraternal love, which originally came to exist among the Sufis of one community.

The parable of Good Samaritan is an example of a Christian commitment to the other which is emphasized much in Sufism. “Even Antony the Hermit recognized his total ignorance of divine mysteries and of the scriptures, and whose supreme value was love towards his neighbour” (Jean, 1989: 93). Service to humanity has always been one of the first phases in the preliminary steps of the path, but throughout his life it remains the true Sufi obligation (Schimmel, 2011: 228). For, “whoever excuses himself from the service of his brethren, God will give him a humiliation from which he cannot be rescued.” (Schimmel, 2011: 229). In Sufism the service to the other is considered as divine encounter. They were commonly referred to as *nussàk* (devout [men]), *zuhhàd* (world renouncers or ascetics), *ubbàd* (worshippers)—terms that roughly correspond to the Latin concept of *virii religiosi* (Knysh, 2010: 6). These religious men are not called to be under a roof for pious practice alone; instead, they have to go out into the world in order to do their work. “More than just fulfilling their religious duties, they paid close attention to the underlying motives of their actions and sought to impregnate them with a deeper spiritual meaning. This goal was achieved through a meticulous contemplation on the Qur’anic revelation, a thorough imitation of the Prophet’s piety, introspection as well as voluntary poverty and self-mortification.” (Knysh, 2010: 6). Love of God and love

of neighbour are essential practices in Christianity. Christians cannot isolate themselves from service to others.

“The Sufis distinguish three organs of spiritual communication: the heart (*qalb*), which knows God; the spirit (*ruh*), which loves Him; and the inmost ground of the soul (*sirr*), which contemplates Him” (Nicholson, 2007: 49). Christian mystics also invite the people of God into contemplation where the communication of the devotee to God is enable through heart and mind. Experiencing God is an innermost happiness of a mystics which can be seen in the both traditions. “Mystics of every race and creed have described the progress of the spiritual life as a journey or a pilgrimage” (Nicholson, 2007: 21) One can see this progress of spiritual journey in both these great traditions.

3. Towards Interfaith Befriending

The Pontifical Council for Interreligious Dialogue (PCID) aims at “the promotion of interreligious dialogue in accordance with the spirit of the Second Vatican Council, in particular the declaration “*Nostra Aetate*”. The PCID wants to have a good relationship among Christians and Muslims. “It promotes mutual understanding, respect and collaboration between Catholics and the followers of others religious traditions” (“The Pontifical Council for Interreligious Dialogue,” n.d.). There are two things very important in our interfaith dialogue. They are heart to heart relationship and participating in mutual Experiences.

3.1 Heart to Heart Relationship

“Too often the past missionary activity of Catholicism has been neither metanoia to new consciousness, new life and orientation, nor a life of grace and being graced, but a forced and imposed proselytism which Jesus himself rejected participating in mutual experience” (Cenkner, 1997: 130). Vatican Council II opened a new horizon for dialogue. In other words, one can say it was a heart-to-heart relationship because the Council encourages the Catholics to enter into dialogue with an open heart.

One document of Vatican Council II, *Ad Gentes* 9, acknowledged truth and grace in other religions in both the people and the traditions themselves. Other documents, *Lumen Gentium* 17 and *Gaudium et Spes* 11, spoke of the spirit of God filling the universe, even in the rituals and cultures of other faiths. Yet another, *Nostra Aetate* 2, called Catholics explicitly to interreligious dialogue and cooperation. (Cenkner, 1997: 132).

Pope Francis in his address to inter religious meeting in Abu Dhabi emphasized that one cannot understand God, the creator, without understanding human beings. Every human life is sacred. Everyone is important in the eyes of God. (“Apostolic Journey to the United Arab Emirates: Interreligious Meeting at the Founder’s Memorial (Abu Dhabi, 4 February 2019) | Francis,” 2019). God cannot be partial to anyone in particular because he created everyone in his image and likeness. The one who received the image from God can easily identify the other as the image of God. There will be mutual understanding from the Heart. Once a mystic identified this reality of God and the other, which will enable him to go ahead with relationship with the other.

But in reality, there is a lot of violence perpetrated between Christians and Islam. There are attacks in Syria. The migration into the European continent is another difficulties the western Christianity faces. The PCID gives a certain solution on such violence. Its message to Muslims for the end of Ramadam (18 May 2018) says:

To prevent and overcome these negative consequences, it is important that we Christians and Muslims recall the religious and moral values that we share, while acknowledging our differences. By recognizing what we hold in common and by showing respect for our legitimate differences, we can more firmly establish a solid foundation for peaceful relations, moving from competition and confrontation to an effective cooperation for the common good. This particularly assist those most in need, and allows us to offer a credible witness

to the Almighty's love for the whole of humanity. ("Message to Muslims for the End of Ramadam," The Holy See 2018).

Muslims and Christians frequently can meet in formal and informal ways as neighbours and friends. They can participate in festivals. They can organize inter faith prayers, even though Muslims and Christians worship separately in the mosques and churches, they join together. They can collaborate in social works. Coexistence does not mean giving up distinctive identities. Every religion has a distinct identity which will enable to appreciate the other. The document Human Fraternity speaks on dialogue as Dialogue, understanding and the widespread promotion of a culture of tolerance, acceptance of others and of living together peacefully would contribute significantly to reducing many economic, social, political and environmental problems that weigh so heavily on a large part of humanity; Dialogue among believers means coming together in the vast space of spiritual, human and shared social values and, from here, transmitting the highest moral virtues that religions aim for. It also means avoiding unproductive discussions; The protection of places of worship – synagogues, churches and mosques – is a duty guaranteed by religions, human values, laws and international agreements. Every attempt to attack places of worship or threaten them by violent assaults, bombings or destruction, is a deviation from the teachings of religions as well as a clear violation of international law (Francis & Al-Tayyib, 2019).

This kind of dialogue is possible if one really has faith in God. The document affirms that, everyone was created by same God. "In the name of God who has created all human beings equal in rights, duties and dignity, and who has called them to live together as brothers and sisters, to fill the earth and make known the values of goodness, love and peace" (Francis & Al-Tayyib, 2019). Being the children of same God, we brother and sisters. We are called to be the keepers of the other. The document says, "In the name of innocent human life that God has forbidden to kill, affirming that whoever kills a person is like one who kills the

whole of humanity, and that whoever saves a person is like one who saves the whole of humanity” (Francis & Al-Tayyib, 2019).

3.2 Participating in Mutual Experiences

One has to enter into the space of the other in order to have religious experience of other. This religious experience will enable one to understand who he is. Entering into the space of other is a difficult task. The one who enters may not be accepted by the other. The incarnation spirituality gives a hope for the Christians to enter into the space of other. Jesus entered into the human space in order to be part of humanity in every sense. “A major challenge is creating spaces and means for “rubbing shoulders with diverse people in an increasingly pluralistic world. “Not only is there a call to “rub shoulders” with diverse peoples, but the call is to love our neighbours—our religious neighbours—in ways that push relational boundaries. Miroslav Volf argues that living with the “other” in peace is “an expression of our God given humanity” (King, 2016: 203). Human beings are created as social beings. There is a communication between all of them. The isolated human being cannot live a proper life. It is same with the isolated religion. No religion can live as an isolated entity. Every religion has a connection with other religion(s). The mutual sharing of religious experience of mysticism will enrich the other. This will enable to flourish and nurture the identity of the other and enable to go forward in a peaceful life and well-being. “Interfaith dialogue has emerged as a major means for interacting with peoples of different faiths that work toward achieving such goals.” (King, 2016: 204). *Nostra Aetate* is an invitation to Christians to enter into this dialogue of experiences.

The Church regards with esteem also the Moslems. They adore the one God, living and subsisting in Himself; merciful and all- powerful, the Creator of heaven and earth, who has spoken to men; they take pains to submit wholeheartedly to even His inscrutable decrees, just as Abraham, with whom the faith of Islam takes pleasure in linking itself, submitted to God. Though they do not acknowledge Jesus as God,

they revere Him as a prophet. They also honor Mary, His virgin Mother; at times they even call on her with devotion. In addition, they await the day of judgment when God will render their deserts to all those who have been raised up from the dead. Finally, they value the moral life and worship God especially through prayer, almsgiving and fasting (Nostra Aetate 3).

“Since in the course of centuries not a few quarrels and hostilities have arisen between Christians and Moslems, this sacred synod urges all to forget the past and to work sincerely for mutual understanding and to preserve as well as to promote together for the benefit of all mankind social justice and moral welfare, as well as peace and freedom” (King, 2016: 204).

The courage of otherness is the heart of dialogue, which is based on sincerity of intentions. Dialogue is indeed compromised by pretence, which increases distance and suspicion: we cannot proclaim fraternity and then act in the opposite way. “The man who lies to himself and listens to his own lie comes to such a pass that he cannot distinguish the truth within him, or around him, and so loses all respect for himself and for others” (King, 2016: 204). The mutual sharing of experience can come from inter religious prayer. Faith in God is an essential element in the interfaith dialogue. Faith leads a believer to see in the other a brother or sister to be supported and loved. The document signed by His Holiness Pope Francis and the Grand Imam of Al-Azhar Ahmad Al-Tayyeb on ‘Human Fraternity’ goes like this, “Through faith in God, who has created the universe, creatures and all human beings (equal on account of his mercy), believers are called to express this human fraternity by safeguarding creation and the entire universe and supporting all persons, especially the poorest and those most in need” (Francis & Al-Tayyib, 2019). *Lumen Gentium* 16 says: “But the plan of salvation also includes those who acknowledge the Creator, in the first place amongst are Muslims; these profess to hold the faith of Abraham and together with us they adore the one merciful God who will judge humanity on the last day” (Lumen Gentium 16). Reconciliation,

a form of cooperation, requires some collective action Presuming an essential harmony of underlying interests between both faith communities, proponents of interreligious collective action for reconciliation seek to awaken similarly minded activists from different religious background (Francis & Al-Tayyib, 2019).

The common word between Christians and Muslims states,

The future of the world depends on peace between Muslims and Christians. The basis for this peace and understanding already exists. It is part of the very foundational principles of both faiths: love of the One God, and love of the neighbor. These principles are found over and over again in the sacred texts of Islam and Christianity. The Unity of God, the necessity of love for Him, and the necessity of love of the neighbor is thus the common ground between Islam and Christianity (Malik, 2013: 204).

The love commandment is given important in the statement. This is only possible through mutual participation and sharing. “ACW calls for future relations between Muslims and Christians to be predicated on acknowledging the primacy of the two commandments of love. These ethically salient affirmations suggest increased commitment to human equality and dignity and collaboration for the common” (“Common Word between Us and You,” 2008: 458).

Conclusion

The eastern Christians in the early Muslims’ kingdoms experienced freedom in many occasions. We have good examples as John of Damascus as the secretary to the caliph and Patriarch Timothy I had a very personal theological debate with the Caliph Al-Mahdi. There were also Arabic Christian theologians like Abū Qurra, Abū Rā’ita and Ammār al-Basrī who defend the unity of God in Arabic terms in order to create peaceful relationship in the Middle East countries. Dialogue is the place where we can find a common ground in order to work together. The focus must be given to more in common grounds of similarities rather than

disputes. Jesus is considered as a word of God and a prophet. The oneness of God will enable one to understand the Islamic and Christian mysticism as a common ground for dialogue.

There is a lot of misunderstanding and conflict among peoples of differing faiths in the twenty-first century, very particularly among Muslims and Christians. These misunderstandings and conflicts challenged not only religious sphere but also academic level, which moved peacebuilding and interfaith dialogue to the top of academic agendas. The basic need of the human being is love; in other words, every human being wants to live in harmony and peace. Most of the time, the means one takes to acquire peace and harmony is violence and conflicts. People believe that, if one destroys one's enemy, one can live in harmony. But it is impossible. The quest for living at peace with one another made theologians and missiologists to explore a theological ground, with a view to creating understanding and encouraging human encounters that foster respect and dignity for all peoples. "Peacebuilding is considered a relational approach to increase dialogue, mutual understanding, and trust between two conflicting groups. In praxis, peacebuilding reframes contexts of violence as opportunities to improve upon broken relationships and increase awareness of areas of commonalities and mutual interests" (Malik, 2013: 204). The mysticism invites the common people to engage in interfaith dialogue of life and experiences. Mysticism in both traditions emphasize on the oneness of God, who is compassionate and merciful. Mystics make their hearts awoken and experience the oneness of God within their hearts. The contemplation enables one to enter into this level of mystical experience. Love is the fundamental law among the mystics; love of one self, love of God and love of neighbour. The one who has experienced love cannot hate anyone, that is the challenge of mysticism; and it leads to service.

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Book Reviews

Xavier, S. Basil. . Basil's Ethnophilosophising in India: A Study on Arunthathiyars (Series I). New Delhi: Authors Press, 2020. ISBN: 978-93-89824-88-9. pp. 376. Hardbound. ₹ 1400, \$ 70.

This book is the outcome of the author's strenuous research conducted on ethnophilosophy of Arunthathiyars, Ethnophilosophy consists of shared beliefs, values and traditional wisdom of an ethnic group. It is found in their wise-sayings, proverbs, stories, mythology, rituals and religion. Ethnophilosophy is considered as a property of a community rather than an activity of an individual.

One of the most marginalised sub-sections among Dalits in the State, Arunthathiyars have largely remained underdeveloped with poor literacy. They cluster caste groups ,previously called as chakkiliyars and some more caste names and are one of the oldest caste groups, known to be first inhabitants of southern India and Tamil Nadu, according to DNA research done by Indian Academy of Sciences.

The first part deals with the ethnographic data of Arunthathiyars who are mostly scavengers and cobblers, the 'dalits of the dalits' in Tamil Nadu. Their counterparts in the other parts of India may be Madhigas, Mangs, Bhangis, Chamars, Mochis and others.

The second part deals with ethnophilosophy which is culled out from their mythical, religious, ritual, historical, professional and identity consciousness. This is the study of their 'collective consciousness'. It is an enquiry on 'popular consciousness'. Hence

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it is a research on “folk” philosophy, philosophy of ‘little tradition’, ‘subaltern’ philosophy and philosophy of the ‘periphery’ or ‘margin’.

This book tries to excavate the ethnophilosophy of Arunthathiyars by delving deeper into their folk/popular consciousness (348). The ethnography of Arunthathiyars presented in the third chapter is based on works in Tamil and on author’s own research in five districts of Tamil Nadu. The fourth chapter deals with the ethnography of Arunthathiyars culled out critically from Western missionaries and colonial officials (p. 350).

The next chapters deal with the mythical, religious, ritual, historical, professional and identity consciousness of Arunthathiyars . In this book the false history of Arunthathiyars is deconstructed and the true history is constructed.

The author shows successfully that the cult and worships turn out to be the “weapons of the weak” (p. 350). The author notes that in the 19th and 20th centuries Arunthathiyars are identified as cobblers and scavengers. The author argues that in the past Arunthathiyars were leather artisans who enjoyed high social status (p. 352). Later when the British explored hide and skin to England the indigenous and college leather industries of Arunthathiyars became extinct and destroyed their profession.

The book also proves that scavenging was not their traditional job. When their profession collapsed and when they were made paupers by the policies of the colonial government, they were forced to take up scavenging, as discussed in the section “anthropology of scavenging.” The book succeeds in a new kind of “identity construction” for the Arunthathiyars . It also deals with the relationship between construction of identity and their popular consciousness.

From a philosophical point of view, the book laments that only classical (‘great tradition’) is considered philosophy and the ordinary people’s world-views and consciousness are not taken seriously by researchers.

The author proves conclusively that the Arunthathiyars did not come from Andhra Pradesh but were original inhabitants of Tamil Nadu and they fought against the colonial powers, a fact largely ignored by the historians of freedom struggle (p. 355).

The author also shows that Arunthathiyars are the “subaltern

scientists” since their technological knowledge and craftsmanship were “outstanding and excellent” (p. 356). The scientific role of salt in keeping the wet skin from rotting was discovered by them several centuries ago. Their role in constructing irrigation bucket was commendable.

The data and facts obtained are philosophically interpreted towards the end of the book. It also talks of “boundary situation” and how boundaries are crossed (p. 353). The crossing of social boundaries and the resultant cruelty of the ‘upper’ caste is also discussed in the book.

The author Dr S. Basil Xavier is Principal Arul Anandar College (Autonomous), gold medallist in MA Philosophy (Univ of Pondicherry) and a Jesuit priest belonging to Madurai Province.

On the whole we can say that the book is a significant step towards the study of subaltern philosophy, the need for developing a subaltern consciousness and identity, which alone can liberate people from their internal and external bondage. This book makes a significant contribution to the Arunthathiyar community! Thus this critical book is highly recommended for students and scholars of philosophy, sociology, anthropology, theology and ethnography.

Goretti Amaladoss, Maria. (2020). Awake: Empower the Dropout. Palayamkottai: St. Xavier College of Education. ISBN: 978-93-84192-14-3. pp. xxiv=390 ₹200/-

“The empowerment of women through education: a comparative study of high school educated women and women dropouts at Kancheepuram in Tamil Nadu, under the guidance of Dr. Myrtle Barse.

Education widens one’s understanding, imagination and creativity and makes a person confident of facing life and its issues, in the end, bringing about peace, progress and prosperity for all. (xix-xx)

This work consists of 10 sections. After the introduction, the second chapter situates the status of women in Tamil Nadu and particularly in Kancheepuram district. The next chapter deals with issues related to empowerment of women as a process. The fourth chapter deals with the impact of education on women empowerment. The author affirms that education “essentially involves opening

the mind, enhancing self-esteem and self confidence, building a sense of positive self-worth, accessing information and tools of knowledge and acquiring the ability to negotiate with this unequal and unjust world from a position of strength” (45). Rosenberg’s self-esteem scale is used in the study. The next chapter deals with the drawbacks of dropout women and education. The causes of dropout are elaborately discussed (p. 335).

The next chapter deals with the socio-economic and religious backgrounds of the women in the field of study. The seventh chapter explores the levels of self-esteem among the educated and drop-out women in a detailed manner. The eight chapter studies the knowledge levels of both dropout and educated women in terms of six parameters: health, hygiene, family planning, human rights and politico-economic system. The author points out that school education was mostly “delinked from “actual life, especially that of women” (p. 47).

The patriarchal structure of Indian society and culture is studied in the next chapter. The author shows that education of women facilitates the freedom of movement and is an important indicator of women empowerment. The author also shows that women have favorable attitude towards girl’s education. The final chapter focusses again on patriarchy that is accepted as way of life in Kancheepuram. For instance women-beating is accepted as a norm even by women themselves (345). The study points out that NGOs have played a crucial role in empowering and uplifting the women, in spite of the patriarchal mindset.

The study shows unambiguously that “education is an effective instrument of social and economic development and national integration” (p. 347).

This well-documented and researched work is a significant contribution to the situation of women in Kancheepuram and Tamil Nadu. This book is highly recommended for those involved in gender studies. Scholars of sociology, anthropology, social work, and ethnography will find the book highly rewarding.

Kuruvilla Pandikattu

Pandikattu, Kuruvilla. *Light for Life: Spiritual Insights for Contemporary World.* New Delhi: ISPCK, 2019. ISBN: 9789388945639; pp: 266 ₹ 295.

Can we be true to our own selves? Do we necessarily make compromises in living? How does God accompany us in our life journey? What is the role of spiritual depth in encountering our lives in its intensity? How does faith in God help us relate to fellow human beings better? These are some of the questions this book, meant to encourage us to live genuinely, deals with. In this way these are spiritual inputs for contemporary men and women.

As we know, life is a series of experiences contributing to our own self-understanding. This helps us to embrace the whole of reality gradually. The light that comes to us helps us to live our lives more deeply and fully. Thus the enlightened people were those who lived their ambiguous lives deeply and fully. They embraced the pain and found it deeply satisfying and painful. They rejoiced in everything, including in suffering and pain. Thus, to be alive is to be open to the tragic and ecstatic dimensions of our day to day life. Such an experience, even in its bitterness, will enlighten us. The light that emerges from life is symbolically seen as leading to our own fullness. These articles try to convey this sense of a committed and concerned spirituality that does justice to living together.

As such, these short essays are meant for a general audience, who may or may not be organisationally religious. They are meant to inspire a band of young men and women to think deeply about themselves, leading to deeper insights and wisdom.

Open-minded and visionary, these articles are meant to touch the daily life of busy people who are fully involved in the struggle and success of daily life. Mostly limited to 625 words, these articles attempt to provide them with both roots and wings: roots that will give them a sense of belonging to the rich Indian heritage and wings that will take them forward based on the spiritual depth.

Though the author gladly acknowledges his Christian commitment, he does not impose it on the audience. Trying to be objective and philosophical, as much as possible, the articles are an open invitation to search for deeper meaning and widen vision.

For clarity and convenience, these articles are roughly divided into nine Sections. The Spiritual Adventure; Socially Committed; Yearning for the Divine; Experiencing the Divine; Realising Human Values; Living Creatively; Light and Shadows; Psychological Depth of Being; Learning from Life

These articles presuppose that spiritual life has to be based on day to day experiences of ordinary people, and so God has to be found in our daily life. When we reflect on daily events, we can indeed be open to the most profound mystery that guides us forward. A cautious and courageous attitude is necessary for this search. Truly optimistic and open-ended, these articles urge the readers to find the depth of existence in the ordinary things of the world and thus make the sacred emerge from the mundane. In that sense, even though some of us refuse to believe in God, as a species, we can claim to be a sacred species capable of experiencing the depth of light and love: the only one who can and needs to make such a claim.

Thus the title “Light for Life” implies that we can always find traces of light even in the utmost darkness that we experience, which is the basic claim and understanding of the Christian faith. This gives us hope and joy in the shadows that accompany us. May the insights in this book offers rays of light in our lives, sometimes burdened and heavy! For we are always in search of the Divine. Or more correctly, the Divine is in search of us! At every moment! In all situations! So, the glimpse of light at every moment of life (and death)! That enables us hopeful and joyful. Highly recommended for thinking Christians to nourish their souls.

Shabin K. CST

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